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D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

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Document short abstract	<p>The deliverable covers three data sets: the exploitable project results that have been generated in time period M1-M46, partners' exploitation plans that are built upon achieved results within the project, and a narrative on business model generation and delivered business canvases.</p> <p>Cities2030 partners have uploaded results' exploitation plans into 5 target fields: academic, industrial and business, financial and market, societal, and policy and governance.</p> <p>The Intellectual property rights are assessed both on the results owners' and user's side.</p>
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Disclaimer

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Document history

Version	Date	Main Changes	Authors
v.0	14.11.2022	SLEAN requests WP leaders' contribution to the deliverable D7.5 i.e. to enter WPs' exploitable results descriptions into tables 1-8. Deadline 30.11.2022.	WP 1-8 leaders and task leaders
v.0	15.11.2022	SLEAN requests Living Labs and "5 special missions" contribution to the deliverable D7.5 i.e. to enter exploitable results descriptions into an excel sheet which is in ANNEX A. Deadline 31.12.2022	Living Labs 5 special missions
v.0	1.12.2022	SLEAN requests all partners' contributions by 31.12.2022 to the deliverable D7.5 i.e. to enter partner profiles in table 10 and partners' exploitation plans into tables 11- 15.	All Cities2030 partners
v.0	2.1.2023	The 1st edition ready for peer-review. Document covers the project results issued in months M1-M27.	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14 Viktorija Jankuloska, AGFT P27, WP leaders,

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			Living Labs, All partners
v.0	10.1.2023	Peer- review and feedback: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is a highly complex document, to which most partners (in charge with this set of tasks) brought their contribution. However, the contribution of other partners is also necessary since they can provide the system picture of exploitable results and plans. The deliverable can work as both a report and action plan. In light of this, all societal levels have been covered, and the deliverable discourse has been built by appealing to strategies and systemic instruments. This systemic nature provides a good integration of the deliverable and actions concerned with other deliverables, actions and strategies of the project. WP9 Ethics was not included in the chapter 2 and it is proposed to be added into the second edition. We recommend going to the operation and strategic alignment phase. 	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, ARFI P29
v.0	11.1.2023	D7.5 Submission to the coordinator. The coordinator submits the deliverable to the Agency by the end of M28 (31.1.2023) complying with GA articles 19 and 41.2, CA 6.4.2 and D8.1.	SLEAN P14
v.1	30/01/2023	P02 EPC collects and integrates the missing contributions of P13 AGRIA, P39 RTU and P40 GITAG and submit the finalised document for a final check to the peer-reviewer P29.	P02 EPC
v.1	7.2.2023	The PMO performs a final formal check before up-loading the file in the SEDIA portal	P01 UNIVE, P02 EPC
v.1	1.3.2023	PMO had not uploaded into SEDIA at all the ANNEX A. PMO uploaded only the main document, although the editor sent the ANNEX A by email to the PMO on 11.1.2023. The deliverable was approved by the Agency.	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14
v.2	13.2.2023	D7.5, edition 2 opened for editing	SLEAN P14
v.2	11.10.2023	A request for WP1-8 leaders to documentate work package results to chapter 2.	SLEAN P14
v.2	18.10.2023	WP leaders are urged to update WP results. All project partners are urged to update/complement exploitation plans of results. Deadline 31.10.2023	SLEAN P14

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v.2	1.11.2023	The 2nd edition is ready for peer-review. Document covers the project results issued in months M1-M37.	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14 Viktorija Jankuloska, AGFT P27, WP leaders, Living Labs, All partners
v.2	13.11.2023	Peer- review and feedback: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is one of the most important deliverables to support living & policy labs in building their strategy to integrate on the societal level within urban and city region food systems. • It includes a description of activities at the level of the academic community, in the business environment, at the level of administration and governance and in civil society. • At the same time it includes an action plan to integrate the living & policy lab actions within these four dimensions of the societal system. • The annex A is a very important document too, because it presents the networking of the living & policy labs alliance of the Cities2030 project. We strongly recommend to emphasise the connection of the annex with the main document. • The document is well structured, presented in an accessible way for public beneficiaries and for stakeholders, but for the coordinators of the living & policy labs too. • The document is a good starting point for future strategies, methodologies and action plans on the living & policy lab level. At the same time it is a good document to build action plans in post-implementation activities of the Cities2030 project at living & policy labs level. • At the same time, in accordance with the development of the Cities2030 project, additions can be made in the deliverable. 	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, ARFI P29
v.2	14.11.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All other partners of the consortium have contributed to the deliverable as proposed by the editor, except the two partners which are: 7-UNRF, EREVNITIKO IDRIMA P.L. and 36-UCC, UNION OF CYPRUS COMMUNITIES. Because the two partners have ignored their obligation at both editions, the editor of the deliverable expects the project coordinator to intervene and ensure that the two partners will contribute to the last third edition (M47). • The editor, Tuula Löytty P14 SLEAN, delivered the deliverable D7.5, edition 2 and an Annex A by email attachment to the coordinator (email: cities2030@unive.it) and to the 	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14

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		<p>peer-reviewer: Mr Codrin Dinu Vasiliu (email: codrindinuvasilu@gmail.com) on 14.11.2023. The Coordinator has 12 working days to check and finetune the deliverable for submission into SEDIA.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The coordinator will upload the deliverable and the Annex A (part 1 and part 2) to the EU-portal SEDIA by the end of M38 (30.11.2023) complying with GA articles 19 and 41.2, CA 6.4.2 and D8.1, and respecting strictly the submission deadline. 	
v.2	21.11.2023	The PMO performs a final formal check and final editing of the document	P01 UNIVE, P02 EPC
v.3	22.11.2023	D7.5, edition 3 opened for editing	SLEAN P14
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v.3	10.6.2024	All project partners are urged to update/complement exploitation plans of results. Deadline 11.7.2024	SLEAN P14
v.3	15.7.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The 3rd edition is ready for peer-review by 20.7.2024. The document covers the project results and partners' exploitation plans which beneficiaries have reported in project months M1-M46. 	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14 Viktorija Ilieva, AGFT P27, WP leaders, Living Labs, All partners
v.3	24.7.2024	<p>D7.5 Deliverable is very important to the Cities2030 project for at least the following reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It synthesises the knowledge transfer actions and methodologies within the project, emphasising their consolidated, systemic character and with important effects in socio-economic ecosystems. It establishes very useful tools for the post-factum actions generated by the Cities2030 project, ensuring important resources for the sustainability of the actions, strategies, and tools carried out within the project. <p>The information used was obtained mainly through participatory knowledge and innovation actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cities2030 partners have uploaded results' exploitation plans into 5 target fields: academic, industrial and business, financial and market, societal, and policy and governance. 	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, ARFI P29

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		<p>Another important aspect that must be specified is that the D7.5 report can also be used as a strategic document for the living labs within the project, in future actions and in the projects in which they will be involved after October 2024.</p> <p>I recommend publication on the project website and its promotion as widely as possible among the direct and indirect beneficiaries of the project. The report must also be promoted to the European Commission, to emphasise the importance of the actions and results of the Cities2030 project in the socio-economic ecosystems.</p>	
v.3	26.7.2024	The editor of the deliverable will submit the deliverable D7.5, edition 3/3, the Annex A (part 1 and part 2) and Annex B to the coordinator.	Tuula Löytty, SLEAN P14
v.3	31.8.2024	<p>The PMO performs a final formal check and final editing of the document.</p> <p>The coordinator will upload the deliverable and the Annex A (part 1 and part 2) and Annex B to the EU-portal SEDIA by the end of M47 (31.8.2024) complying with GA articles 19 and 41.2, CA 6.4.2 and D8.1, and respecting strictly the submission deadline.</p>	P01 UNIVE, P02 EPC

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Executive Summary

Cities2030 is a collaborative innovation project whose sustainability strategy is based on maximum openness and exploitation, taking into account the necessary intellectual property rights at both project and individual partner level.

The document presents the results of eight work packages, policy labs and living labs, categorised according to their innovation, exploitation and impact. It presents comprehensive exploitation plans in five clusters: academic, industrial and business, financial and market, societal, and policy and governance. Finally, the document discusses the Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the project outputs, risk assessment strategies and the project's overarching business model using the Business Model Canvas framework.

Chapter 2 and ANNEX A describe the project deliverables.

Chapter 3 presents the consortium partners.

Chapter 4 outlines the partners' exploitation and IPR strategies.

Chapter 5 and ANNEX B discuss the business model development process.

This third and final edition of deliverable D7.5 presents the WP 1-8 results, the results of the policy and living lab activities, and the structured and informative exploitation and business plans for the project results. The third edition covers the project implementation months M1-M46.

1. Introduction

1.1 Cities2030 results and Key Exploitable Results (KER)

According to the Horizon2020 program text¹, a result is defined as:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached right, including intellectual property rights”.

A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its potential to be exploited. This means that KER is anticipated to make use and derive benefits at city region food system or act as an input to policy, systemic development, transformative innovation, consolidated capacity building, knowledge transfer, entrepreneurial brokerage, communities of practice building, further research or education.

In Cities2030, the aim is to deliver results accordingly with the TRL Model: Technical Readiness Level from 5 to 8 depending on the nature of the solution (ref: GA: (a).11 Positioning). To enhance the novel solutions deployment the TRL 7-9 is the target.

Project results are described and classified in chapter 2. The profiles of generated results are of four types:

¹ EU Grants, Annotated Grant Agreement

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

1. the results that are addressed to project "internal" purposes to assist and facilitate progress,
2. results that are generated at Policy Labs pilot measures in WP4 and which will be introduced in next editions,
3. results that are generated at Living Labs pilot measures in WP5 and which are embraced in ANNEX A, and
4. results that originated from the cooperation between multiple work packages.

1.2 Exploitation planning strategy

The main aim of exploitation in CITIES2030 is to ensure the sustainability of the project's results beyond the project end and to demonstrate how the project has influenced the EU Urban Food System Environment landscape. The sustainability actions and capacity building strategies are constant objectives for the Cities2030 project.

Each beneficiary must — up to four years after the project — take measures aiming to ensure 'exploitation' of its results. In the time period 1.11.2024 - 31.10.2028 the 41 consortium partners from 19 countries committed to exploitation actions to maximise impacts and secure continuity.

Exploitation includes multiple forms, for instance:

- Financial exploitation, building products, projects, or services based on the project results;
- Research & Innovation development, by engaging new projects (EU-funded or sponsored by other sources), based on the experiences gained in the project;
- Education, e.g. courses, at the university level or in continuing education, etc.;
- Community-building around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions;
- Knowledge transfer, from academia to industry, by collaboration or via employees;
- Contributions to open-source projects and standardisation, providing access to the framework and encouraging its broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties.

The consortium has identified a series of general exploitation points as a prelude to each individual partner's exploitation strategy. The exploitation points are divided into 5 clusters.

Deliverable D7.5 outlines a procedure for collating, analysing, and managing results, and planning the exploitation of results. The procedure contains elements as such:

- the result owner's foreseen exploitation plan,
- the result owner's assessment of IPR, describing and profiling of results,
- partners' precise and informative exploitation plans that reflect the partner's profile, and partners' assessment of IPR.

The project results and partners' exploitation plans are to be issued in three waves at deliverable D7.5 on project months M28, M38, and M47.

- The first wave covers the results achieved in months M1-M27,
- The second wave covers the results in months M1-M37,
- The third wave covers the months M1-M46.

2. Exploitable results

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The project reports its exploitable results, and IPR and exploitation strategy. This description covers the following data in the tables 1-9:

- The result identification number encompasses the work package number and result identification number which is used only in this document
- Project result name and description
- KER-types, that are defined by
 1. Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms);
 2. Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.
 3. ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.
 4. Other Intangible Results (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies);
 5. Services (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines);
- KER index of the result: In order to prioritise Cities2030 results and select KERs, the owner of the result assesses the result on three criteria: degree of innovation, exploitability, and impact. The criterion can get a score of 1, 3 or 9:
 - Score 1 means e.g., low degree innovation, or low possibility to exploit it,
 - Score 3 means e.g., medium impact,
 - Score 9 means high possibility to exploit.
- The result KER index is a multiple of scores. KER index can vary from 1 up to 729. The higher the KER index is, the more innovative, exploitable, and impactful the result is.
- TRL level: *“Technology readiness levels are levels on a scale that can be used for estimating the maturity of a given technology. There are nine levels, which each represent a state in the development of technology, from the first thoughts to the final technology”*². TRLs measure the maturity level of technology throughout its research, development and deployment phase progression.
 - TRL 1: Basic principles observed
 - TRL 2: Technology concept formulated
 - TRL 3: Experimental proof of concept
 - TRL 4: Technology validated in lab
 - TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
 - TRL 6: Technology pilot demonstrated in relevant environment
 - TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment
 - TRL 8: System complete and qualified
 - TRL 9: System proven in operational environment
- Result owner(s): Indicate who are the owners of the results. The owner can be an individual partner or a team of partners.
- IPR strategy: Define if there are any limitations that may apply on project results for exploitation. Information of what (if any) IPR protection mechanisms is needed. Options are e.g. Open, Industrial

² Technical Readiness Levels explained at S3Food project: <https://s3food.eu/technology-readiness-levels/>

Secret, Patent, Copyright, Software licence, Open Source, Creative Commons Licence, lesser General Public Licence, B2B Agreement.

- Foreseen exploitation: Results owners introduce how they foresee the results to be exploited by project partners or by other means.

By the end of the project the project Coordinator selects Key Exploitable Results and enters them into EU portal³ and/or Horizon Results Platform⁴ and/or European Open Science Cloud⁵.

2.1 WP1 - Impact

WP1's main aim is to provide a comprehensive framework, methodology, and tool to secure the project impact assessment aligned with the Cities2030 project proposal, including already existing food-related policies such as MUFPP (criteria from The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact Monitoring Framework Handbook); FOOD 2030 in various impact directions:

- social;
- environmental;
- economic;
- technological;
- legal, policy, security and management;
- culture and values.

The partners in WP1 have developed the IMA (Impact Assessment Methodology) to explore the previous research in this field in order to apply the most appropriate impact assessment strategy by validation and verification approaches.

Table 1: WP1 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy Foreseen Exploitation
1	1	The digital impact assessment tool developed on the UNIPARK platform https://www.unipark.de/ . This digital tool is developed to collect and monitor the various impact dimensions created by each project partner and partnership on local, regional, national, EU and global levels.	TRL 7 KER index 81	P39 (RTU)	IPR Strategy: open Foreseen exploitation will be updated in the next editions.
1	2	Impact assessment strategy (PIAAS) is peer-reviewed academic articles' based document helping to identify the impact assessment methodology and approach.	TRL 9 KER index 91	P30 RTU P5 IAAD P25 LLF P27 AGFT P30 ICTM	IPR Strategy: project Cities2030

³ EU portal: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>

⁴ Horizon Results Platform

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

⁵ European Open Science Cloud, <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

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2.2 WP2 - CRFS PHILOSOPHY: ethics, RRI and gender approach

WP2's main aim is to provide a comprehensive framework to secure the project development and results are aligned with the European Union idea of an inclusive, innovative and reflective society. The partners in WP2 have developed the philosophy guidelines with the house of Cities 2030 ethics as main result. This graphical representation of the ethical vision of the project serves as the ethical background supporting the subsequent activities of the project.

Furthermore, the activities in WP2 have allowed partners involved to improve their knowledge in the key three covered in this work package: ethics, gender approach and responsible research and innovation (RRI) in the scope of CRFS.

In summary, the ethical framework of Cities2030 contributes to the creation of new and sound evidence for policy makers in relation to urban food systems in support of policy development and improved social inclusion and equity of all actors of the food systems.

Table 2: WP2 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
2	1	The House of Cities2030 ethics. It is a graphical representation of the ethical vision of the project, comprising the Base (Ethical values), Pillars (activities and means) and Dome (impacts, outcomes and results) according to European normative ethical theories.	TRL 3 KER 81	P14 SINNO P13 AGRIA P14 SLEAN	IPR Strategy: open Foreseen exploitation will be updated in the next editions.
2	2	Knowledge acquired in ethics, gender approach and responsible research and innovation (RRI) applied to CRFS. This knowledge has served as the basis for the WP2 whitepapers to be delivered on M28, M29 and M30.	TRL 3 KER 27	P1 UNIVE P4 VIVES P5 IAAD P13 AGRIA P14 SLEAN P19 SINNO P26 GGP	IPR Strategy: open Foreseen exploitation will be updated in the next editions.

2.3 WP3 - CRFS INTELLIGENCE: structured and actionable knowledge

The CRFS Intelligence of WP3 outlines an advanced KNOWLEDGE FRAMEWORK related to City Regions Food Systems, policies, sources, data, and indicators. The knowledge framework is issued to facilitate co-creation and participatory reflection processes to support capacity building programs, CRFS lab prototyping, and labs' activities to innovate policies and practices within CRFS pilot contexts. To support this objective, the actionable knowledge frame is integrated into both WP3 Observatory and the WP6 Click Platform and made available for partners through the internal management system (notably the Correlate platform).

The co-generation process among experts, researchers, practitioners, agents, and stakeholders of the food system arena (Cities2030 Alliance) encompasses a wide range of results, including methodologies, studies, research, practices, data, and indicators. In this process, qualitative and quantitative approaches are

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combined to detect vulnerabilities, obstacles, potentials, and solutions for CRFS sustainable development in the Pilot contexts.

Table 3: WP3 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
3	1	Cities 2030 Observatory. Aims to serve as an open knowledge repository gathering existing policies, policy briefs, scientific literature, official statistics and insights from food-related EU projects. ICT Software Digital solution.	TRL 7 KER index 9	P1 UNIVE P11 QUA	Open. The Cities 2030 Observatory will be available for four years after the Cities 2030 end date. The Observatory content is fed to the platform via a content management system (CMS), which – via user accreditation – will allow interested institutions and relevant stakeholders to update content on a regular basis. The Observatory codebase and database can swiftly migrate from P11 to interested parties' hosting services.
3	2	FILL (Food for Iasi Living Lab) is the first living lab for urban systems development built in the Romanian North-East Development Region. Now, in 2024, FILL is one of the most important actors within the region, changing the system, contributing to the consolidated building capacity of the region, involved in transformative innovation and knowledge transfer (www.fill.rdrp.org).	TRL 9 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	Food for Iasi Living Lab represents an innovative hub, which supports the collaboration between the main actors in the North-East Region of Romania, for the sustainable and sustainable development of urban and rural food systems.
3	3	Systems Thinking Laboratory was developed with the support of FILL (Food for Iasi Living Lab) and it is an epistemological component of the RDRP & ARFI Knowledge Ecosystem (https://rdrp.org/systems-thinking/).	TRL 6 KER index 81	P29 ARFI	The research laboratory to explore, learn, debate, and understand the philosophy, ethics, and epistemology behind the Systems Thinking Theories. This laboratory is in close synergy with Cities2030, and RURALITIES projects, FILL, and RoRuralia Living & Policy Labs.
3	4	KAPIMS Knowledge and Action Pillars for Iceberg Model Systems is the toolkit developed by SLEAN and ARFI, based on the Systems Thinking Report developed within Cities2030 project. KAPIMS is in the TRL3 phase but it was already used	TRL 3 KER index 3	P29 ARFI P14 SLEAN	KAPIMS is based on the report D3.3 Systems Thinking Methodology. Generate the project system thinking framework, Tuula Löytty, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Lucian Tanasă, Mark

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		within SHERPA and RURALITIES projects (https://rdrp.org/concept/kapims/) .			Koetse, Justine Vanhalst, Kyriakos E. Georgiou, Edna Yamasaki, Demet Osmancelebioglu, Bruno da Silva, Sebastian Doboş, Kalle Karlsson, Cities2030 Project, 2021
3	5	The Knowledge Management Research Laboratory is built within the FILL ecosystem, and it supports knowledge development and transfer for organisational capacity building within the RDRP & ARFI Knowledge Ecosystem (https://fill.rdrp.org/knowledge-management-laboratory/) .	TRL 7 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	The main activities are workshops for horizontal knowledge transfer and support for new projects development.
3	6	Living Labs Development Laboratory is built within the FILL ecosystem, and it supports the capacity building for living, co-creation, innovation and policy labs in Romania. FILL is already invited by ENoLL and UEFISCDI (national research governmental organisation) to organise workshops for the Romanian and European new living labs (https://fill.rdrp.org/living-labs-development-laboratory/) .	TRL 7 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	Living Labs Development Laboratory is the exploratory space for scientific research, co-creation, experimenting to support the specific knowledge and actions to support the sustainability and resilience of the living labs as innovative participatory ecosystems.
3	7	3 new research and knowledge transfer laboratories are in the TRL3 phase of development within FILL ecosystem: Urban & CRF Systems Laboratory, Open Science Laboratory, Responsible Research and Innovation (https://fill.rdrp.org/research/) .	TRL3 KER INDEX 81	P29 ARFI	The FILL laboratories are built to support the production and transfer of knowledge for the development of urban and rural systems.
3	8	Systems Thinking Encyclopedia is a research project started within Cities2030 project and that will continue within RURALITIES and Cesar2030 projects (https://rdrp.org/systems-thinking-vocabulary/) .	TRL3 KER index 81	P29 ARFI	Systems Thinking Encyclopedia will be an important support for implementing systems thinking theories, methodologies, models and practices within the living & policy labs ecosystem.

2.4 WP4 - CRFS ALLIANCE: cities' empowerment and synergies

Work package 4 focuses on CRFS policies and aims to sufficiently activate CRFS actors through several activities, including capacity building, leveraging MUFPP+ (Milan Urban Food Policy Pact) and policy

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assessments. Policy labs are supported in the designing, piloting and ex ante assessment of the effectiveness of CRFS policies through multiple mechanisms.

Lab partners are informed through a seminar series that addresses specific topics relevant to current phases of lab development. Apart from process-specific information, these sessions cover detailed information on the application of core concepts such as system resilience, systems thinking, open policy creation and building upon the MUFPP+.

Cities2030 living labs have two dimensions of knowledge and actions:

- The living lab dimension, that is mainly oriented on experimentation, innovation and work in direct collaboration with stakeholders and beneficiaries;
- The policy lab dimension, that is mainly oriented on capacity building for policy and strategy making.

Additionally, policy lab partners are supported in the production of action plans that set out the CRFS context, particularly the policy context, on which concrete policy action is formulated. Support consists of document templates, information sessions and ongoing support sessions. The processes of CRFS policy assessment are expanded on by a peer network that facilitates best-practice identification.

Table 4a: WP4 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
4	1	Policy lab action plans. This is a collection of data and texts provided by partners in a semi-structured format on CRFS policy contexts. Data includes stakeholder lists, SWOT analysis, lists of CRFS-related policies, policy gap identification, and a definition of SMART goals/SMART tasks.	KER 1	P33 IVM	IPR Strategy: Open access This data provides detailed insight into CRFS policy creation and the context in which these processes take place. Exploitation by follower labs will lead to more informed decision-making and tailored CRFS policies.
4	2	Peer network. Groups of policy lab partners have been built across relevant policy lab themes. CRFS labs assign a leader for each theme group. This network aims to provide support and facilitate expert meetings and best practice identification.	KER 1	P33 IVM	IPR Strategy: Open access The identification of best practices facilitates effective policy creation by follower labs and will inform research activities on food system transformation.
4	3	Capacity building programme A capacity building program that provides CRFS partners with tools to stay informed, skilled and able to appropriately inform CRFS stakeholders.	KER 1	P33 IVM	IPR Strategy: Open access Training materials can be used across CRFS to inform partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action, supporting the realisation of good practices.

Table 4b: Exploitable results that are associated to policy labs and policy framework

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WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Living Lab Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
4	1	LLINN Platform as a support for European Living Labs INN permanent symposium. . The symposium network support debates and dissemination for policy knowledge achieved within the Cities2030 project (www.linn.rdrp.org)	TRL8 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	Romanian Living Lab (FILL - Food for Iasi Living Lab) developed the RDRP knowledge Ecosystem as a support for capacity building for FILL to implement its present and project postimplementation actions. The LLINN platform is built and will be the digital hub for LLINN the first symposium in november 2023. The next editions are programmed already for 2024 (2 editions) and 2025 (2 editions).
4	2	Food for Iasi Living Lab, RoRuralia living & policy lab, and RDRP research platform developed three synergic research laboratories on participatory governance within RDRP Knowledge Ecosystem. The RDRP research platform represents the core for the research strategies. Furthur FILL and RoRuralia laboratories experiment and continue these research results within urban and rural systems (www.rdrp.org).	TRL8 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	Integrated knowledge and action to develop policies, strategies and participatory governance within urban, rural and region systems.
4	3	FILL (Food for Iasi Living Lab), RoRuralia living & policy lab, SLEAN, and RDRP assisted Building Cesar Action. Building Cesar Action is the action to build Cesar2030 Center of Excellence in Socio-Economics of Food Resilience. The BCA put together 10 Romanian partners from academia and universities, 218 researcher community, 464 stakeholder community, 4 clusters of excellence, 24 new Living Labs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://rb.gy/90f213 • www.cesar2030.eu 	TRL7 KER index 729	P29 ARFI P14 SLEAN	Cesar 2030 is built on the basis of Systems Thinking philosophy and integrates 24 Living Labs, in order to support all the societal dimensions for resilient and sustainable food ecosystems.
4	4	FILL (Food for Iasi Living Lab) supported the building of the RoRuralia Living & Policy Lab within the RURALITIES project. FILL and RURALITIES are working together since 2022, integrated within RDRP and ARFI Knowledge Ecosystem	TRL7 KER index 729	P29 ARFI	Designed as a collaborative and innovative hub, RoRuralia Living Lab aims primarily at connecting stakeholders from the Romanian North-East Development Region for identifying and assessing the

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		(www.roruralia.rdrp.org), as the main actors within the living lab community for urban and rural systems in the Romanian North-East Development Region.			particular issues of the rural and urban systems.
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2.5 WP5 - CRFS ANGELS: innovation, synergies and investment action

Work package 5 is implemented in the city's or region's innovation framework. The mechanism and operating platform is the CRFS Living Lab (LL). The WP5 aim is to co-create, test, validate and implement improvements, best practices, and feasible, desirable and profitable innovations that provide value to city region inhabitants and authorities, and advance the transition towards sustainable CRFS.

WP5 tackles and contributes to 7 of the 12 challenging scopes of actions (see GA, Annex, section 1.2) to generate and deploy an actionable roadmap to structure, accelerate and sustain transforming urban food systems and ecosystems (UFSE), and to deliver frameworks for the production of policies (e.g. action plans) and innovations (e.g. supporting instruments), towards the democratisation and implementation of sustainable urban food system practice, which will be piloted in real-scale in cities and regions.

WP5 results are introduced in two result baskets differentiated by their own target group.

The first basket, that includes internal results, is explained in the Table 5. The main and first target group of these results consist in the Cities2030 partners, who act as Living Lab-operators. Task leaders of WP5 have elaborated the results with and for partners to support and facilitate their actions in the urban food system sustainable transition and to promote the dynamics of Living Labs.

Table 5: WP5 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
5	1	Extended Innovation Pattern (EIP) which encompasses: An Innovation Pattern for food system exploration, innovation action planning and implementation. A Handbook for partners. Guidance in digital format. Diverse mentoring and reflection sessions. Progress and performance monitoring procedure. Type:Scientific innovation, Other intangible results and good/ promising practices. Source: D5.2 and D5.5	TRL 6 KER index 3	P14 SLEAN	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: The result needs to be simplified and improved to be more acceptable and adoptable. After modifications, the components of the result or even the whole solution can be exploited in various research and innovation actions, but tailored to fit into the need and target group.
5	2	Work force of 10+ CRFS Living Lab Innovation Facilitators CRFS Living Labs have nominated an Innovation Facilitator to initiate and	TRL 7 KER index 27	P6 INAGRO	IPR Strategy: Not applicable Foreseen Exploitation:Innovation Facilitators are agents and actors at open innovation workshops and

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		<p>arrange open innovation actions e.g. brainstorming sessions, dialogues, workshops, events for assessment/lessons learned etc. The Innovation Facilitator's Training Package (see below) is addressed to newcomers to empower and support them.</p> <p>Type: Good/promising practice LINK</p>			<p>activities where participants are invited to ideate, brainstorm, assess challenges and problems, and also give their ideas to solve problems. Living Lab Innovation Facilitators' role is to engage and motivate participants and advance dynamics at Living Lab innovation action.</p>
5	3	<p>Living Lab Innovation Facilitators Training Package.</p> <p>A capacity-building concept that covers interviews, a need analysis, a training set that responds to an identified need, open access to training materials, and personal mentoring.</p> <p>Type: Good/promising practice LINK</p>	<p>TRL 9 KER index 27</p>	<p>P6 INAGRO</p>	<p>IPR Strategy: open source.</p> <p>Foreseen Exploitation: The concept can be replicated and applied as a good practice when it is needed to build capacity for any topic.</p> <p>The Living Labs can exploit and apply the concept and issued materials when they train new Innovation Facilitators in their lab.</p> <p>The participants can exploit and apply the concept and issued materials when they enhance open innovation dynamics in any context e.g. participatory budgeting.</p>
5	4	<p>Analysis of establishment of Living Lab and three preparational phases of Extended Innovation Pattern.</p> <p>The qualitative and quantitative analysis of problems that CRFS Living Labs experienced when they established the Living Lab and applied the three first phases of the Extended Innovation Pattern. The analysis revealed the key pain points of the open innovation dynamics and orchestrating Living Lab. The analysis assesses the root causes and impacts of problems. The analysis report is shared on the Cities2030 Community platform forum.</p> <p>Type: research methodology, other intangible result LINK</p>	<p>TRL 3 KER index 27</p>	<p>P14 SLEAN</p>	<p>IPR strategy: open</p> <p>Foreseen Exploitation: The methodology to gather data by semi-structured interview and to carry out qualitative and quantitative analysis is replicable in another context.</p> <p>The observations about challenges and problems in Living Lab implementation ought to be taken into account and build more targeted capacity and know-how for Living Lab facilitators and coordinators.</p>
5	5	<p>Establishment of piloting FOOD 2030 Living Labs for 18 city regions. FOOD2030 Living Labs are prototypes. Source: D5.5 and LINK</p>	<p>TRL7 KER-index 81</p>	<p>Piloting Living Labs</p>	<p>IPR strategy: Living Labs operations comply with the principle of open innovation ecosystem.</p> <p>Foreseen Exploitation: All Living Labs</p>

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					continue to foster FOOD2030 policy at their setting.
5	6	A database on the Living Labs performance, innovation actions (capacity building, experiments, funding, other measures, system thinking pilot) and results (improvements, good practices, innovations, lessons learned) to be used for further research actions.	TRL 6 KER-index 81	P14 SLEAN (the platform)	IPR strategy: Research data delivered by Living Labs shall be managed and made available following the FAIR principles (F = findable, A = accessible, I = interoperable and R = reusable) within beneficiaries. Foreseen Exploitation: Commonly produced data set is open to beneficiaries' analysis and studies and further developments

The second basket covers the results that are accomplished by Living Labs in their local setting. Living Labs carry out multiple experiments, capacity-building actions, and other innovation actions, e.g. related to investments and funding, in their urban food environment. The results of these actions are classified as improvements, best or promising practices, innovations, or other results e.g. capacity building products.

Result type 1	COUNTA / Result type 1
Improvement	24
Good/promising practice	50
Innovation	28
Other exploitable result	8
Yhteensä	110

Living Labs' results

2.6 WP6 - CRFS BLOCKCHAIN: Single Click CRFS Platform

WP6 will gather, design, and develop the main components and technological tools to establish a data-driven CRFS management platform for data collection, analysis and representation in multiple interfaces. An initial requirement acquisition will lead to the proposal of a common technical architecture for CITIES2030, for which supporting data sets will be incorporated to be considered for data analysis and representation. Particularly, a service-based open collaboration space has been incorporated, to be used by CITIES2030 participants to improve their multi-stakeholder dialogue processes. In this space, blockchain technology is employed to provide some proof of concepts of token-based monetization processes, and reflect multi-stakeholder interaction in a reliable and transparent way. Documentation is available for policy labs and living labs to develop their own solutions with assistance from WP6.

WP6 results are introduced in the following table:

Table 6: WP6 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
6	1	Combined Development Methodology: Agile work methodology with 3 stages. In each of these stages, a specific agile and open sub-methodology is used, which allows at all times to offer the rest of WPs a product and technological solution that is viable and usable by PL and LL. These methodologies are Design thinking, Lean Startup and Scrum. Type: Scientific innovation	TRL 8 KER index 3	P20 UPM	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: The components of the result or even the whole solution can be exploited in various

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WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
		https://cities2030project.eu/deliverable/d6-1-s2c-p-single-click-platform-design-and-reference-architecture/			research and innovation actions, but tailored to fit into the need and target group.
6	2	Sentiment analysis: This component uses techniques from the theory of causality and Causal Machine Learning (causal ML). This is dedicated to analyse social networks to understand opinions, requirements and intentions of the users and consumers. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030project.eu/sentiment-analysis/	TRL 7 KER index 3	P35 Uni.Lu	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: This has been exploited as scientific exploitation with publications already accepted.
6	3	Geospatial information and services: Based on state-of-the-art technologies and common and standardised application interfaces in commercial products and in the world of research. This component shows the geographical distribution of the different agents throughout the different CRFS on a map system and can be divided into two entities. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030project.eu/single-click-crfs-platform/	TRL 7 KER index 3	P20 UPM	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: Exploitable through scientific exploitation
6	4	Good practices dashboard: good practices component brings a map-based platform to allow the introduction of innovation activities by any Cities2030 partner, so that a catalogue of information can be compiled, for filtering, searching and consulting. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://good-practices.gisai.eu/	TRL 7 KER index 3	P20 UPM	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: Academic exploitation / dissemination. This topic is part of numerous master's and bachelors's thesis that have been published at UPM.
6	5	SSRI-MAA tool: social space monitoring tool. This provides key functionality to manage SSRI and their stakeholders, working groups and actions. It also provides KPIs and data acquisition tools. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://maa.socialinnolabs.org/	TRL 7 KER index 9	P19 SINNO	IPR Strategy: Proprietary solution. Licence to be decided upon demand. Foreseen Exploitation: SSRI-MMA is part of SINNO's industrial exploitation plan, in collaboration with industrial members of

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WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
					SINNO's network.
6	6	Blockchain for Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC): The platform enables to prove that products are sustainable, original, safety and ethically sourced. The architecture of the system enables data capturing and monitoring from all parts of the supply chain Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030project.eu/bc-for-sfsc/	TRL 7 KER index 9	P30 ITC	IPR Strategy: Proprietary solution. Licence to be decided upon demand. Foreseen Exploitation: ITC as owner of this solution will commercially exploit this product.
6	7	Tool for private communications: Privately, decentralised blockchain-based app that allows communication between actors in a private manner, with the maxims of anonymity and integrity. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030project.eu/private-communications	TRL 6 KER index 3	P20 UPM	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use. Foreseen Exploitation: This has been exploited by means of software (patent) registration.
6	8	S2CP Dashboard: Web interface for transforming and combining geographic data and preferences (value judgements) to obtain information for decision making. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030.primelayer.pt/	TRL 7 KER index 3	P37 PRIM	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use. Foreseen Exploitation: PRIM as owner of this solution will commercially exploit this product.
6	9	Data mining and sentiment analysis: this web interface can retrieve information from various review and comment sites, and perform an individual or aggregate analysis of the information. It provides a friendly interface and a usage statistics provisioning component. Type: ICT Software Digital solution https://cities2030project.eu/data-mining/	TRL 6 KER index 3	P20 UPM	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen Exploitation: This will be exploited by means of software (patent) registration

2.7 WP7 - CRFS BEACON: Dissemination, exploitation, communication synergies

The current WP is led by ARFI (P29) and co-lead by EPC (P2). WP7 aims at securing the public disclosure of the results of the project with an impact-driven strategy, with a focus on generating momentum at specific stages via synergies with other food-related and urban-related events, initiatives and projects. Also, WP7 ideate and implement a structured framework of strategic and targeted measures for publicising dissemination actions to the diverse and comprehensive target audiences. WP7 framework covers dissemination, communication exploitation of results and synergies and develops with two way exchange

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mechanisms, driven by the transfer of information from CITIES2030 and by the uptake from targeted audiences to integrate CITIES2030. All in all, WP7 delivers an actionable and deployable mechanism to secure the project impact.

WP7, by its very nature, does not create innovative tools within the project framework, but basically it creates the ground and the network to make exploitable the project results obtained within the scope of other Work Packages.

Table 7: WP7 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
7	1	Cities2030 website The website of the project (cities2030.eu) that encompasses digital tools for branding the project, communication and dissemination of the results of the project.	TRL 8 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	2	Cities2030 Communicators Community	TRL 5 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use.
7	3	Cities2030 Facebook Network. Social Media Supporting Document This is a handbook that encompasses information related to using Facebook within the information and dissemination objectives of the Cities2030 project.	TRL 8 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	4	Cities2030 dissemination package Digital kit for information, communication and dissemination	TRL9 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use.
7	5	1 Scientific article: Effects of COVID-19 pandemic on sustainable consumption patterns. Evidence from Iasi County, Romania, authors: Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Simona-Roxana Ulman, Lucian Tanasă, Cristina Cautisanu	TRL 8 KER index 3	Authors of the article	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	6	Public digital newsletter	TRL 3 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	7	D.7.1 Dissemination, exploitation, communication and synergies strategy	TRL 8 KER index 3	P5 IAAD	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use.
7	8	D.7.3 Synergies action plan	TRL 8 KER index 3	P5 IAAD	IPR Strategy: Cities2030 internal use.
7	9	D7.4 Innovation and Intellectual Property management plan and reporting Report that structures a framework for	TRL 4 KER index 3	P29 ARFI	IPR Strategy: open source.

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WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
		innovation and Intellectual Property (IP) management.			
7	10	D7.5 Exploitation of results plan Report that comprises an actionable and deployable agenda that incorporates an action plan, describes and structures a strategy to facilitate and encourage the exploitation of the project outputs and ensure the sustainability after the project's scope.	TRL 3 KER index 3	P14 SLEAN	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	11	Food for Iași Living Lab Developing the platform Food for Iasi Living Lab as a hub for synergies of Iasi living lab that is coupled with activities run by the Romanian Academy, Iași City Hall, and, Rural Development Research Platform in Iași city.	TRL 8 KER index 3	P29 ARFI P28 IASI	IPR Strategy: open source.
7	12	Festivalul Cireșelor		P29 ARFI P28 Iasi	
7	13	Piata de Weekend		P29 ARFI P28 Iasi	
7	14	Festivalul de Degustare a Cireșelor		P29 ARFI USV Iasi	
7	15	Glasholder evening. These are a series of networking events held twice a year. They focus on short talks by researchers/government/food producers about a certain theme in greenhouse horticulture (e.g. energy, water, IPM) followed by a networking event and pitches of companies	TRL 9	P6 INAG	IPR Strategy: open source. Foreseen exploitation: this will continue to be organized after the project ends.

2.8 WP8 - LEAN-AGILE GOVERNANCE: data-driven digital management

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The scope of WP8 is to ensure an agile and effective management of the project as a whole, adopting a results-oriented approach and ensuring the smooth and sound execution of the work within the budget defined and at the highest quality standards. Considering the wide and challenging size of the consortium, the agile approach is provided by a rapid and flexible response to changes and evolving priorities and situations that might be faced during project implementation. More in detail, the project management boards (ExeCom, PMO, Secretariat and General Assembly) have established an operative framework of specific procedures, plans and tools for the day-to-day management that have been set since project start and are defined in the Project Implementation Guidelines (D8.1).

Table 8: WP8 associated exploitable results

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result.	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
8	1	Data-Driven Digital Management Platform. A software as a service application giving the users an instant transparent and augmented layer over other online and actionable content, files and pages, stored in and across unconnected and scattered private and public online platforms Total eXperience (TX) related research for public boards. LINK	TRL 7 KER 729	P31 CORR	IPR strategy: will be updated in the next editions Foreseen exploitation: Proprietary solution and trademarked, which we will further develop into a best practice and preferred tool for global web users. Our business plan describes strategic measures and actions to prepare for hyper growth.

2.8 Common and transversal results of work packages

In table 9 the project outlines the exploitable results that are produced by two or more work packages, the results that are not associated with any specific task or work package, and the results that are fully transversal.

Table 9: Exploitable results that fall between and beyond work packages

WP	No	Name of the Result. Brief description. Type of the result. Contributing WPs	TRL-level KER index	Owner(s)	IPR Strategy. Foreseen Exploitation
1-8	1	Food System Dialogues Facilitation Food System Dialogues Guideline based on UN format, adapted to the context of Cities2030 project; supporting materials and templates used in the process of preparing and carrying out independent types of FSD events, which are locally led and locally based. Summary report of FSDs organised within Cities2030 project - list of specific topics/focus themes regarding food transformation	TRL 1 KER 9.	P26 GGP P27 AGFT	R Strategy: open source. Foreseen exploitation: Further use of prepared materials to facilitate the organisation of FSD events as part of organisational annual plans and programs (project partners and others) beyond the project lifetime, thus contributing to the total number of FSDs events taken place across Europe and the

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		<p>chosen in different local contexts and main findings from the conducted discussions. (WP5 and beyond)</p> <p>Link: https://1drv.ms/f/c/cdb8729d7bceaa77/EneqznudcrgggM15AAAAAABwjPQdOrHwowkDJFSnUOU7w?e=EQgJS5</p>			<p>world, as well as raising awareness about the contribution of FSDs to international consensus on how to pursue food systems transformations in line with the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda.</p>
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2.9 Summary of results

Living Labs, Policy Lab and Working Packages have produced and documented **161 results** in the project period of M1-M46.

- The results of each work package are outlined in the below table 10: 47 documented results.
- The results of Policy Labs' efforts at work package 4 are summarised in table 11: 4 documented results.
- The results of Living Labs' efforts at work package 5 are summarised in table 12: 110 documented results.

When it comes to qualitative analysis, results owners have assessed and reflected the results in various manners, and registered the conclusions and lessons learned into digital files and platforms. This information is partly seen at [Cities2030 Community platform](#) and in the ANNEX A of this deliverable.

Table 10: Cumulative results of work packages

Work package no.	Results in the period M1-M27, D7.5 edition 1	Results in the period M1-M37, D7.5 edition 2	Results in the period M1-M46, D7.5 edition 3
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	1	1	8
4	3	3	3
5	4	6	6
6	8	8	9
7	11	11	15
8	1	1	1
Common work	0	0	1
Total	32	34	47

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Table 11: Cumulative results of Policy Labs' efforts at the work package 4 which are described in the Table 4b

Time period	Improvements	Good practices	Innovations	Other exploitable results	Total
M1-M27 D7.5 edition 1	0	0	0	0	0
M1-M37 D7.5 edition 2	0	0	2	0	2
M1-M46 D7.5 edition 3	0	0	4	0	4

Table 12: Cumulative results of Living Labs' efforts at the work package 5 which are described in the ANNEX A, part 2

Time period	Improvements	Good practices	Innovations	Other exploitable results	Total
M1-M27 D7.5 edition 1	11	22	12	2	47
M1-M37 D7.5 edition 2	17	37	18	5	77
M1-M46 D7.5 edition 3	24	50	28	8	110

3. Project partners' profiles

Table 13 outlines beneficiaries' profiles which give background and justification to partners' exploitation plans that are introduced in the next chapter 4.

The table also presents the contributors of this deliverable and beneficiary staff member(s) who are responsible for the exploitation of the project results for the next 4 years after Cities2030 ends.

Table 13: Beneficiary, staff members and profile description

No. and short name	Beneficiary	Responsible staff member(s)	Beneficiary profile description
1-UNIVE	Ca' Foscari University of Venice	Nicola Camatti Daniele Sferra Selma Vaska	UNIVE actively participates in EU programs for education, training and research, partnering with worldwide institutions. Its scientific staff has relevant competencies related to regional economics and development, SME studies, reuse of cultural Heritage, sustainable tourism development, quantitative and qualitative analysis, and service designing. In these fields, it accounts for a vast experience in the management of cooperation projects.

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No. and short name	Beneficiary	Responsible staff member(s)	Beneficiary profile description
2-EPC	EPC - European Project Consulting Srl	Raffella Lioce Francesca Borga	European Project Consulting srl is an Italian SME who cooperate and support Public Administrators and Local Authorities mainly in the fields of territorial development, growth opportunities, land and environmental management, stakeholders involvement and participatory processes, European cooperation and Project Management.
3-BRUG	GEMEENTE BE STUUR BRUGGE	Karine De Batselier	The city of Bruges drew up a strategy (Bruggesmaakt) to promote sustainable food. In addition to the social dimension, there is a strong focus on avoiding the production/waste of surplus food, farm to fork, city agriculture, Fair Trade and education (less meat, sustainable fish,..) The City of Bruges emphasised its ambition in this respect by signing the Urban Food Policy Pact and the Glasgow Food and Climate declaration (2021). This food strategy is made up in cocreation with the Bruges FoodLab.
3a-BRUG	LTP - Riddersstove	Annelies Fleurbaey Lieven Astaes	The core business of Riddersstove is to prepare and to distribute ready meals to elderly people in the CRFS of the Bruges region. As a non-profit organisation we have experience in implementing innovations in our part of the food-supply chain with impact on the quality of life of our target group and also with impact on the actors we linked with to increase the sustainability of our CRFS.
3a-BRUG	LTP - Mintus	Stéphanie Del Cioppo	Mintus is a welfare organisation that is close to the care recipient in the Bruges region.
4-VIVES	VIVES University College	Barbara Plovie Annelien Desplenter Indra Vanoverbeke Sam Vandamme	VIVES is a state-recognized and state-financed higher education institution. The aim of our research is to ensure that our teaching remains of a high quality. Through our research, we also want to contribute to innovations in professional practice and have a regional, provincial, and national impact on the knowledge infrastructure and economic and social development.
5-IAAD	ISTANBUL EUROPEAN RESEARCH ASSOCIATION	Bruno Da Silva	İstanbul Avrupa Araştırmaları Derneği (IAAD) is a not-for-profit project-based civil society organisation situated in Istanbul, Türkiye, and aims at contributing to initiatives driven by the radical vision of science-enabled technologies aiming at generating more Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies.
6-INAG	INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EVAP	Maarten Ameye Simon Craeye Muriel Derycke Celine Simoen	The core business of Inagro is to perform applied research and to transfer knowledge to the stakeholders within the agrofood chain through communication, demonstration and consultancy. Inagro seeks to improve sustainability of local food production systems and to detect new opportunities for farmer businesses. As such, Inagro is a key actor within the regional and international Agriculture Innovation and Knowledge System (AKIS).
7-UNRF	EREVNITIKO IDRIMA P.L. (UNRF)		<i>the partner has not provided the data</i>
8-VEGO	Razvojna agencije Grada Velika Gorica VE-GO-RA	Violeta Crnogaj	VEGORA is a local business development agency with a purpose of business, financial and legal counselling and technical assistance. The organisation is a public institution established by the City of Velika Gorica, Croatia, in 2015, with the intention for coordinating projects regarding socio-economics and territorial development as well as individual support and technical support to public and private initiatives.
9-INVE	Inventivna rjesenja	TBD	A small enterprise founded in 2007. and covers areas such as - consulting in fruit growing technologies and fruit processing technologies, fruit

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No. and short name	Beneficiary	Responsible staff member(s)	Beneficiary profile description
			growing (with an accent on bio program and possibilities of shortening food chains), research, development and introduction of fresh fruit growing technologies in a particular ecosystem, work on improvement of supply chains and recycling of biowaste from food processing and more.
10-VEJLE	VEJLE KOMMUNE	Ida Drevald Per Mandrup	Culinary Institute by Vejle Erhverv: As Vejles big food investment our main purpose is to place food at the top of the agenda through guidance and help for both big and small companies. We work with everything from holistic sensory, food development, product development, conceptualization to planning large food events. We also host workshops for our public kitchens to boost skills in climate-friendly cooking and work with talent development within gastronomy for culinary students and school students.
11-QUA	Quantitas	Giuseppe Castiello Jacopo Trabona	Quantitas S.r.l. is an innovative SME working in the field of advanced data analytics. It is specialised in the production of web-based tools for data processing, data enrichment, and data automation as well as in the development of domain-specific observatories for both private and public institutions.
12-INTO	Into Seinäjoki Oy	Sanna Kankaanpää Anu Portti	Into Seinäjoki Ltd. is a development company of the city of Seinäjoki, developing both the operating environment and the business development of start-ups and companies seeking growth. Has built various national and international networks and operating methods, and has created several business development innovation tools. Supports city transformation towards a sustainable and resilient food system.
13-AGRIA	ProAgria Etelä-Pohjanmaa ry	Terhi Välisalo, Asta Asunmaa	Rural Women's Advisory Organisation is a well-known rural developer. It offers expert services, planning, training and development services in the fields of food and environment. We have over 100 member associations. The organisation is legally a part of ProAgria Etelä-Pohjanmaa ry. ProAgria is a Finnish expert organisation providing specialists and services to farmers and other rural entrepreneurs.
14-SLEAN	SMART & LEAN HUB OY	Tuula Löytty	SME, that contributes to rural and urban areas' transformation towards sustainability, resilience, and agility. Interest in exploring and deploying novel innovations and nudge systemic transition. Beneficiary out capacity building and consultation assignments addressed to public and private bodies.
15-BRH	Magistrat der Stadt Bremerhaven	Claudia Harms	The maritime character of Bremerhaven is, among others, reflected in its broad scientific landscape. In both basic and applied research, the city is home to renowned institutions in the fields of oceanography, climate research, port management, maritime transport and logistics, wind energy and, for example, the food and fish industries. Close cooperation with industry is a high priority for all institutes.
16-TTZ	Verein zur Förderung. d. Technologietransfers a.d. HS Bhv e.V.	Linda Böhm	ttz Bremerhaven is an independent research service provider and conducts application-oriented research and development. An international team of experts works here in the fields of food and resource efficiency. TTZ is an engine for innovation. Its maxim is research for a better quality of life. Together with companies, they bring research results to application.
17-BIOZ	BIOZOON GMBH	Darleen Genuttis	Biozoon is a specialist company in the field of powder products for food application, especially in the field of dysphagia and malnutrition management. With the necessary market knowledge and technological

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			skills, they develop, manufacture and market high-value, top-quality products both for private and commercial customers.
18-QUAR	AYUNTAMIENTO DE QUART DE POBLET	Dana Maini, Alberto Martinez	Quart de Poblet is a municipality located in the Valencian region, Spain. The municipality has more than 24,000 inhabitants and its area is 19,6 km ² . The main tasks of the European Projects Department are aimed to support the different areas of the City Council with the development and execution of projects, drafting and managing projects under different European programs.
19-SINNO	SOCIAL INNOLABS	Miguel Ángel Navarro	Social Innolabs is a non profit organisation aiming at serving as a catalyst between technology and society by encouraging the collaboration of different actors in participatory innovation models and the development of products that improve the quality of life of citizens on an ethical basis.
20-UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID	Ramón Alcarria, Borja Bordel	The Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) is the oldest and largest Spanish technical university, with more than 4.000 faculty members, around 38.000 undergraduate students and 6.000 postgraduates. UPM participates in the project through the GISAI research group, which has extensive experience in provision of computer systems solutions and IT infrastructure.
21-WIT	WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	Micheal Crotty	South East Technological University is the first technological university in south east Ireland and was formerly known as Waterford Institute of Technology. Its Walton Institute, since 1996, has undertaken futuristic next-generation technologies, to verify their capabilities and applicability for today's society, and to work in collaboration with industry to ensure their commercialisation.
22-MATIS	MATIS OHF	Viggó Marteinsson René Groben	Matís is a government-owned Icelandic food and biotech R&D company. Its focus lies on value creation, food safety and public health, working with partners in industry, academia and public authorities in Iceland and abroad. Matís has expertise and facilities for research and services in a broad range of related fields from microbiology to chemical analyses and aquaculture research.
23-FFI	FUTURE FOOD INSTITUTE	Virginia Cepollina; Elisa Carioli; Sara Roversi	The Future Food Institute is an international social enterprise and the cornerstone of the Future Food Ecosystem, a collection of research labs, partnerships, initiatives, platforms, networks, entrepreneurial projects and academic programs, aiming to build a more equitable world, grounded in integral ecological regeneration, through enlightening a world-class breed of innovators, boosting entrepreneurial potential, and improving agri-food expertise and tradition. Knowledge, Community, Innovation are its three pillars of action.
24-VPR	VIDZEME PLANNING REGION	Lienite Priedaja, Lelde Abele	VPR is a Regional administrative authority under supervision of the Ministry of Environment Protection and Regional development of Latvia. VPR ensures regional strategic and spatial planning and encourages cooperation between municipalities, governmental institutions, entrepreneurs, NGO's. VPR promotes and supports food innovation measures, bridging food enterprises and other stakeholders, connecting food with regional development issues and food based tourism development.
25-LLF	LATVIAN LAUKU FORUMS (LLF)	Aiva Apša Kļišeniece Zane Siliņa	Latvian Rural Forum (Latvijas Lauku forums) is an umbrella non-profit organization that unites more than 80 rural NGOs, including both local community organizations and local action groups that implement LEADER

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			approach in Latvia. The aim of LRF is to promote sustainable development of Latvian rural territories.
26-GGP	ASSOCIATION GREEN GROWTH PLATFORM SKOPJE	Natasha Ristovska	Green Growth Platform (GGP) is an NGO focused on the introduction of green growth concept in the field of agriculture, rural development and environment. GGP specific competencies are in the area of large scale piloting (policy and technology), education and training, complex analysis (policy, industry), business and investment modelling, project management, communication and dissemination.
27-AGFT	AG FUTURA TECHNOLOGIES DOOEL SKOPJE	Viktorija Jankuloska, Nadica Angjushveva Tosikj, Darko Jancheski	AgFutura Technologies is an innovative SME, dedicated to support the agri-food industry with innovative solutions. AGFT has an extensive experience in the development and implementation of projects from different programs and is one of the first companies that has introduced the concept of digital and precision agriculture in the countries of the Balkan region.
28-IASI	CITY HALL OF IASI	Bianca Ghica	Our current objective is to continue the efforts of the previous period of programs supporting the city to overcome existing barriers to food system transformation, promote to build integrated, sustainable and safe urban food system policies/strategies and to solve problems of common interest
29-ARFI	Academia Română – Filiala Iasi	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Ioan Sebastian Bruma, Lucian Tanasa, Meda Galea, Lavinia Bejan, Simona Roxana Ulman, Cristina Căuțișanu, Mihai Chițea, Iuliana Groza, Mărioara Rusu, Sebastian Doboș	Romanian Academy - Iasi Branch is the main academic institution in the North-East Development Region Of Romania. Our main goal is scientific research, yet innovation and knowledge transfer are other key objectives. Our mission in the Cities2030 project is to develop an urban food system focused on the relation between urban consumers and local producers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARFI developed Food for Iasi Living Lab (FILL) within the Cities2030 project. FILL is the most active and important living lab working in the domain of urban systems within Romanian North-East Development Region. • ARFI developed a synergy with RDRP, assisting the building of RoRuralia Living & Policy Lab within RURALITIES project (www.roruralia.rdrp.org) • In the Cities2030 project, ARFI coordinated Building Cesar Action, a sustainable action for the development of Cesar Center of Excellence with 24 new living labs (www.cesar2030.eu) .
30-ICTM	ITC – INNOV. TECHNOLOGY CLUSTER MURSKA SOBOTA	Tomaz Zadavec Aleksandra Kocet Sasa Straus Daniel Copot Tomaz Bokan	ITC is a non-profit Business Support Organisation located in the North-Eastern part of Slovenia. ITC's main focus is to bring together target groups (such as SMEs, food system actors, farmers and other rural actors) and turn them into being "Smart", thus creating a unique Europe-wide innovation-based ecosystem, supporting the shift towards more resilient, healthy and environmentally, socially, economically sustainable rural areas.
31-CORR	Correlate AS	Ole Goethe	Correlate is a Norwegian SME developing Software as a Services tools for context creation, sharing, communication and publishing.
32-VIZ	COMUNE DI VICENZA	Mara Mignone Fabio Cestonaro	Municipality of Vicenza - It is the local public entity governing the city of Vicenza, which is located in the North-East of Italy, in the Veneto Region. With specific reference to the issues addressed by Cities2030, the Municipality is responsible for safeguarding public health and carrying out the tasks assigned by the legal framework on waste, local hygiene, and pollution.
32a-LaVi	LTP - La Vigna	Massimo Carta Chiara Guglielmi	The International Library is an Institute of documentation specialized in agricultural and rural world culture studies. The Library conserves more

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			than 62.000 books (some of them dated back to '400) on food, wine and agriculture. It represents a real-life LIVING LAB where citizens meet researchers, where knowledge is preserved and developed to prompt open thinking and establish an open innovation environment.
33-IVM	STICHTING VU	Suzanne van Osch Mark Koetse	The Institute for Environmental Studies (IVM) is nested in the Vrije Universiteit (VU) Amsterdam. IVM aims to contribute to sustainable development through excellent scientific research and teaching. A unique feature of the institute is the capacity to cut through the complexity of natural-societal systems through novel interdisciplinary approaches.
34-MOM S	Mestna občina Murska Sobota	Simon Sukič Vida Lukač Tadej Pirc	Murska Sobota is the business and economic centre of the Pomurje region. 120.000 people are living in the Region of Pomurje. The regional development agency is working closely with the Municipality Murska Sobota to include all 27 municipalities in several stakeholders from the region in the CITIES2030 project.
35-Uni.lu	UNIVERSITÉ DU LUXEMBOURG	prof. Thomas Engel, Aurel Machalek, Melanie Sengupta	The University of Luxembourg is a multilingual, and international University, strongly focused on research. The University of Luxembourg, as one of the Luxembourg government's research-driven institutions, aims to drive and foster outreach and awareness of its research results among all relevant stakeholders from government to industry players and standardisation bodies.
36-UCC	UNION OF CYPRUS COMMUNITIES		<i>the partner has not provided the data</i>
37-PRIM	Primelayer, Unipessoal, Lda	Pedro Caridade	PRIMELAYER was founded in 2006 as a spin-off from University of Coimbra for the use and application of GIS methodologies in the public sector. The main activities have been focused on the public sector mostly oriented for verticals such as education, social, sports and cartography. Special activities on earth observation are also integrated in GIS platforms, creating analytics for multiple sectors.
38-IUAV	Università Iuav di Venezia	prof. Maria Chiara Tosi	The Iuav University of Venice is a place of teaching, advanced training and research in the field of design of spaces and environments inhabited by man and is the only university in Italy entirely dedicated to teaching and research in the field of design disciplines: Architecture, Planning and Urbanism, Design, Arts, Fashion, Theatre and Performing Arts.
39-RTU	RĪGAS TEHNISKA UNIVERSITĀTE	Iveta Cirule, Elīna Mīkelsone	Riga Technical University (RTU) is the oldest higher technical educational establishment in the Baltic States, the direct predecessor of which – Riga Polytechnicum – started operating on 14 October 1862. RTU is a modern internationally recognized university, the only polytechnic university in Latvia and the largest university in the country – it educates and trains almost 15 thousand students. RTU is focused on becoming a third generation university that not only provides high quality education, but also conducts advanced research and ensures innovation and technology transfer, practically implementing scientific discoveries.
40-CITAG	Cité de l'Agriculture	Jean-Baptiste Rostaing Louis Roland	La Cité de l'agriculture is a Marseille (France) based non-profit working on issues related to food justice and urban agriculture. Through both field projects (an urban farm and various initiatives that aim at reducing inequalities in food access) and think tank activities (consultancy, project incubation, political advocacy, documentation and research) it strives towards a vital transition of our agricultural and food systems.

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41-HARL	Gemeente Haarlem	Christiana van Lammeren, Rudie de Vries, Stephan Kooijman	The city of Haarlem is a municipality in the Netherlands. With 160.000 habitants it's in the category of middle sized cities. The municipality of Haarlem has initiated an extensive sustainability program that focuses on climate adaptation, energy transition and circular economy.

4. The exploitation plans of the results that are issued in project months M1 - M46

Cities2030 Grant Agreement (GA) article 28 defines partners' obligation to exploit project results.

All consortium partners have committed to this obligation by signing the GA.

ARTICLE 28 — EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

28.1 Obligation to exploit the results

Each beneficiary must — up to four years after the period set out in Article 3 — take measures aiming to ensure 'exploitation' of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing; see Article 30) by: (a) using them in further research activities (outside the action); (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process; (c) creating and providing a service, or (d) using them in standardisation activities.

The preparatory phase in results exploitation is to define project results (see chapter 2) and prepare a precise and informative plan on how to exploit results beyond the project framework.

The exploitation plans are divided into 5 clusters: academic, industrial and business, financial and market, societal, and policy and governance. The following chapters encompasses all Cities2030 partners' exploitation plans per cluster.

4.1 Academic exploitation plans

Academic exploitation plans include research and innovation actions at large. In addition it includes the offering of courses and seminars with topics related to the project. Through that, the project can attract researchers and new students to work on and improve the ideas of the project.

Another area of focus for the academic partners within Cities2030 is the exploitation of their work and project results through contributions to open-source software. Its maintenance presents an equally important objective to ensure that the results of Cities2030 will remain available and relevant long after the project terminates.

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The availability of the Cities2030 framework is expected to be a valuable asset for all academic partners in terms of building new partnerships, engaging in future projects, and acquiring further funding at the national and EU level.

In the Table 14 partners describe how they plan to exploit results in further participative research and open science activities, open source, open data, openknowledge, EOSC, FAIR data, etc..

Table 14: Academic exploitation plans

Partner	Academic exploitation plans: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
1-UNIVE	Under the WP3 tasks, we plan to exploit the results mainly through scientific articles. We will contribute to the scientific community and society at large by publishing articles in well-reputed open access Journals.
2-EPC	Not applicable
3-BRUG	Not applicable
3a-BRUG	WP3, WP4, WP5: our expertise in the field will be further shared, we want to set up a durable, sustainable and valuable cooperation with academic partners (VIVES). As Riddersstove is a member of Flanders Food, an organisation of all actors in the food industry and food supply chain, we participate at events where this knowledge can be exchanged.
3a-BRUG	Not applicable
4-VIVES	WP3: The currently achieved results will be implemented in the education for students at bachelor level. The aim of our research is to ensure that our teaching remains of a high quality in terms of subject matter and is in line with current issues in professional practice WP5: s
5-IAAD	Not applicable
6-INAG	WP3: stakeholder engagement => continuous engagement of stakeholders in new living lab projects, WP5: We will further exploit the training material made for workshop techniques and utilize them in research projects with academic partners who need input from food producers.
7-UNRF	Not applicable
8-VEGO	Not applicable
9-INVE	Not applicable
10-VEJLE	WP4, WP5 - Our goal is to Create activities and events that create political awareness throughout Vejle Municipality. We want to strengthen local food producers. We will pass on our results to private companies and public institutions.
11-QUA	Quantitas being mainly active in WP3, we aim at exploiting Cities 2030 Observatory-related results. As the Observatory grows in scope and content, it will likely be able to attract an increasing number of researchers and academic interest in the large plethora of food-related policies, scientific papers, and EU projects, and statistical data it aggregate. As the partner hosting the Observatory website, Quantitas commits to the technical maintenance of the Observatory for the whole duration of the exploitation period in the afterlife of the project.
12-INTO	WP5 / Healthy Snacks : Scientific communities have been engaged in this living lab design, planning, implementing and exploitation. As Into is not an academic institution, members from the Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences, and the Universities of Turku, Tampere and Vaasa have been directly

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Partner	<p>Academic exploitation plans:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	<p>engaged through their expertise and guidance. The main aim of connecting with scientific and research communities was to promote awareness of healthy nutrition of children and develop through co-creation approaches the actual living lab actions. Students have supported the actions by creating surveys, data collection and by creating a “Handbook for Healthy Snacks Canteen”. This living lab continues to work directly with academics and professionals in close contact for long-term exploitation of project results via the Healthy Kids of Seinäjoki steering committee.</p> <p>WP5 / Food Business Club: See below, in cooperation with P13 WP5 / School Canteens in to Restaurants: See below, in cooperation with P13 WP5 / Kids’s food festival: See below, in co-operation with P13</p>
13-AGRI A	<p><u>WP5/ Food business club:</u> A new hobby possibility of making small food related business is created for the youngsters of ages 12-16. The youngsters learn to do business, know more about food chain, get food-related networks and have a fun hobby with some income. A hobby club is established and it is located in school after the school day (-> Finnish Hobby Model). There is an adult facilitating the work in the club. <u>WP5 / School canteens into school restaurants:</u> Attention to school restaurant other aspects than practicality and nutrition has been arisen by a pilot example. One pilot school’s restaurant has been modified to meet the other needs of the pupils. The actual target group is the pupils but another target group is the ones that hold the power to change school restaurants as the school’s principal and the city’s food service leaders. The needs and wishes of the pupils are asked by survey and by a workshop. The changes in canteen’s physical environment and practices are mainly integrated into the school’s study program, but some small investments can be done from the school budget. If bigger changes are needed the process of additional financing will need the city’s special decision. <u>WP5/ Kids’ food festival:</u> The children are more aware of the food’s route from field to fork, understand possibilities to grow their own food and know how easily it can be started. The target group is the children mainly of ages 7-10 years old. The capacity building experiment takes place in already existing children’s art and culture festival “Pikkuprovinssi”. The results will be delivered in blog text on the internet and in straight contacts with other food education organisations. Will have a new exciting content of food education. The Sapere method is used and all senses stimulated.</p>
14-SLEAN	<p>WP5/1: SLEAN will exploit the concept of Extended Innovation Pattern (EIP) or parts of it, the associated Handbook, and the experience of executing and implementing task 5.2 in the context of the Cities2030 consortium. Research results are to be exploited in further research activities of organisation and as background to be brought into a new collaborative research project. No issue with IPR.</p>
15-BRH	<p>By 2030, Bremerhaven wants to have reached 50 % of the citizens with information about regional and sustainable food. Our city administration works closely with (residents) initiatives, researchers, SMEs and food producers to realise a sustainable food system. We focus on promoting a sustainable and healthy food choice and prevent/reduce food waste and stimulating biodiversity through e.g. citizen science initiatives on food issues.</p> <p>In the coming years we will intensify cooperation with initiatives in Bremerhaven. A climate protection programme is currently in progress on federal state level, also including actions / measures concerning regional and sustainable food supply. We particularly focus on Community catering, as this allows us to reach a high number of residents and provide good leverage on the way to a stable CRFS. (WP 4, 5,7, Living Lab Bremerhaven in close cooperation with P 16 TTZ and P17 BIOZ.)</p>
16-TTZ	<p>The closeness to Bremerhaven University of Applied Sciences means that project content will also be incorporated into education. Student assistants working in the project and thus become multipliers in the course of the work. The impulses from CITIES2030 are currently leading to work on proposals related to Citizen Sciences and CRFS. (WP 4, 5,7, Living Lab Bremerhaven in close cooperation with P15 BRH and P17 BIOZ.)</p>

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Partner	<p>Academic exploitation plans:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
17-BIOZ	Cooperation with academics towards research exploitation by means of scientific publications. (WP 4, 5,7, Living Lab Bremerhaven in close cooperation with P15 BRH and P 16 TTZ.)
18-QUAR	Not applicable
19-SINNO	SINNO will collaborate with UPM (P20) in scientific exploitation for Multi Actor Approach Tool and related initiatives like IEEE SCF Summit 2023
20-UPM	UPM (P20) is mainly dedicated to scientific exploitation, highlighting the novel aspects of the S2CP components that are being developed according to the CDM methodology. To do that the organisation will publish communications to national and international congresses and also scientific contributions to scientific journals, indexed in Journal Citation reports (JCR), which is a high-quality and well-recognized citation index. So far, UPM has published 1 research paper in a high-impact scientific journal (with press release as well) as well as three communications published in international conference proceedings. Also, UPM have participated in the organisation of CISTI2022 conference, and in the elaboration and publication of 18 bachelor's and master's dissertation with developments aligned with Cities2030 WP6 work. Also, the Privately software has been IPR-registered.
21-WIT	WIT (P21) will also focus on academic exploitation of aspects of the S3CP platform. Of interest is the provenance, management and verification of data used within the S2CP platform which can be used to support data governance. Additionally, we plan to exploit the results of a regional community survey on food choices, Sustainability, climate action and future food systems. The organisation will publish scientific material to well renowned journals and conferences.
22-MATIS	Matís will contribute to publications and reports of other partners as well as aiming to academically exploit results from its work through scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals.
23-FFI	FFI plans to actively contribute to the elaboration of the System Thinking paper under WP3. In the next months, further participative research and activities will be increased also in support of the Regenerative Agriculture Academy, that we are planning to kick off in the Paideia Campus Living Lab by connecting local regenerative farmers, youth and other stakeholders from the agri-food system (innovators, startups, etc). Also the increase in collaborations and partnership with local universities and schools will represent a crucial occasion to widen the reach of educational and academic results, in the fields of nutrition, wellbeing, anthropological studies, regenerative agriculture.
24-VPR	The Vidzeme planning region is already collaborating and will continue to work with universities on an initiative that includes building short food chains, building and improving the local food ecosystem, as well as promoting research leading to the creation of a data and informative base to promote legislative change.
25-LLF	LLF will participate in preparing an article on Systems thinking methodology (methodology developed by P14 SLEAN), sharing experience of using STM for different stakeholders groups.
26-GGP	White papers on ethics, gender and RRI (WP2), Cities2030 Observatory (WP3), Good practices dashboard (WP6) and Scientific articles (WP7) will be shared with relevant academic institutions within our network for educational and research purposes.
27-AGFT	Prepared materials for capacity building on exploitation and business modelling (WP5): AGFT will integrate these materials into our guest lectures at universities, focusing on sustainable food systems and innovative business models.
28-IASI	Educational activities: Workshop in schools for raising awareness about healthy food provided on the short food supply chains. The target group is the children mainly of ages 7-10 years old.
29-ARFI	Scientific research: We plan to write and publish 3 scientific papers in ISI Web of Science indexed journals, in an open access system. The papers are the result of research made within the project and in collaboration with both stakeholders and experts. We also aim to take part in scientific events with

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Partner	<p>Academic exploitation plans:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	<p>communications of the research results. Systems thinking methodology exploitation: the methodology developed by P14 SLEAN in collaboration with P29 ARFI will be experimented and adjusted to new developments, contexts.</p>
30-ICTM	<p>WP1: Research on the impact approach to the project WP5: Structuring and developing strategies to run its own living lab called Green Point, with a scientific approach to the user experience and user involvement. WP6: ITC contributes to the development of the S2CP components ITC is developing the blockchain based tool for the traceability of the food products from farm to fork.</p>
31-CORR	<p>All project participants are encouraged to use, share and exploit collaborative knowledge sharing and publishing with open access mode. We provide free licences suitable for students for structuring scattered content and enabling them for sharing of knowledge in conceptual modes.</p>
32-VIZ	<p>Not applicable</p>
32a-LaVi	<p>The International Library La Vigna, thanks to the members of its scientific council, will contribute to the publication of scientific articles in open access. Furthermore, the dissemination of issues related to the CRFS will continue through seminars and workshops aimed at the academic world, local entrepreneurs and consumers in general.</p>
33-IVM	<p>Not applicable</p>
34-MOM S	<p>In the coming years Murska Sobota will intensify cooperation with initiatives in the Pomurje region and will try to introduce sustainable models of food production to the Pomurje region, which will be founded on the principles of circular economy, to mitigate climate change and to adjust to the scarcity of resources.</p>
35-Uni.lu	<p>Educational Activities Involvement of Students: Engage students enrolled in the Bachelor's degree program in Computer Science to actively participate in Bachelor Semester Projects. These projects will serve as a practical training ground for students to apply their classroom learning in real-world scenarios. Student Contributions to WP6: Students will contribute to Work Package 6 (WP6), which is dedicated to developing a 'Single Click CRFS (Cross-Referencing and Fact-Checking System) Platform'. This platform comprises multiple technological modules, including but not limited to Sentiment Analysis. Target Group: The primary focus will be on enriching the educational experience for researchers and students in the computer science domain.</p> <p>Research Activities Sentiment Analysis Research: Conduct comprehensive studies to explore the potential and limitations of Sentiment Analysis technologies. Aim to contribute original research papers to prestigious academic journals. Blockchain Technology Research: Delve into the evolving landscape of Blockchain technology, particularly its applications and implications in securing information and ensuring integrity. Workshops and Conferences: Organise and participate in workshops, seminars, and research conferences related to Sentiment Analysis and Blockchain technology. The objective is to create a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange. Publication in Standardisation Bodies: Commit to publishing results in recognized standardisation deliverables, including initiating work items in the ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) ISG (Industry Specification Group) IPE (Identity and Privacy Enhancement) group. Target Group: This facet of the exploitation plan aims to engage and disseminate information to the wider research community and experts in the relevant fields.</p> <p>Exploitation plan summary: We will conduct extensive research on Sentiment Analysis and Blockchain technologies, aiming to publish our findings in top-tier academic journals and present at major</p>

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Partner	<p>Academic exploitation plans:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	<p>conferences. We will organise and participate in workshops and seminars to foster collaborative knowledge exchange. Our research results will also be submitted to recognised standardisation bodies like ETSI ISG IPE, where we will initiate new work items. Through outreach and public lectures, we will engage with the broader research community and establish collaborative projects with other institutions, ensuring wide dissemination and impact of our work.</p>
36-UCC	Not applicable
37-PRIM	Not applicable
38-IUAV	<p>Educational activities: Iuav currently proposes several didactic paths aimed at exploring urban and territorial transformations related to food and their spatial implications. In the three-year degree course in Architecture, an integrated design workshop between urban planning and geography is proposed, in which students are called upon to work on the context of Vicenza, producing materials for analysing and reading the territory and developing product or process innovation projects. In the international master's programme in Planning for transition the teaching proposal is oriented towards the development of food policies for the context of the Venice lagoon, integrating the disciplines of economic evaluation, planning and service design. Finally, Iuav offers a two-week summer workshop for international students from different disciplinary fields, with the aim of co-constructing a Food Atlas of the Venice Lagoon together with local actors. All these educational activities took place during the academic year 2021/2022 and will be repeated for the period 2022/2023.</p> <p>Dissemination activities: Iuav regularly participates in national and international conferences related to the disciplines of architecture, urban design and planning, proposing reflections on urban issues related to food and sharing progress and partial results of the ongoing research for the Cities2030 project. Iuav plans to propose two articles in scientific journals by the end of 2023.</p>
39-RTU	<p>RTU Team will lead the development of at least two peer-reviewed research articles regarding the main duty of RTU in Cities2030 scope - impact assessment, WP1.</p> <p>The first article will be developed about CITIES2030 PIAAS (deliverable 1.2.) methodology applied in project, as well as development of impact collection digital tool structure and first exercise conducted in December 2022- January 2023 to collect the impact created by partnership by December 2022. The second article will be devoted to overall results of impact assessment progress presenting the dynamic of impact creation process. The article will comprise the data analysis both quantitative and qualitative for 4 reporting periods (till December 2022, December 2023, December 2024, December 2025). Additionally, these results and impact methodology will be presented in at least 3 international conferences in 2023, 2024, 2025. The additional publications may be drafted in cooperation with WP5 Team and Living Labs on Living Labs' created impact.</p> <p>Main target groups and users - academia, researchers in social science and humanities focusing on impact assessment and sustainability, food system actors from Penta Helix network (business, academia, public, NGOs, civil society), doctoral students, other large scale EU funded projects (programmes Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe 2021 -2027, etc.) research teams focusing on impact assessment and/or food systems. IPR assessment - according to RTU research policy rules articles published by RTU staff (Employment contract) as authors or co-authors will remain as RTU intellectual property. The publication will contain a concise reference to projects, will be published as open - access publications.</p>
40-CITAG	<p>CITAG does a lot of research internally, in order to regularly measure the impact of its projects. There will be several academic articles published on the results of CITAG's WP4 and WP5 actions.</p> <p>In addition, CITAG closely works with several scholars specialised in urban agriculture. This opens opportunities for further academic exploitation, although precise actions are still to be defined.</p> <p>WP4, guide Capri : the guide from the Capri urban farm will be used as a dissemination tool and shared with academics studying urban agriculture. WP4, farm land in Marseille : the farm land mapping in</p>

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Partner	Academic exploitation plans: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	Marseille will be used as a communication and policy tool once finished, and shared with academics studying urban agriculture. WP5, chilli pepper production : our opportunity study on a mutualized transformation tool will be shared with academics studying this subject and with policy makers. WP5 : local CRFS observatory : we plan on sharing the data collected with local academics and policy makers.
41-HARL	WP4 , WP 5 , WP7: By 2030, Haarlem wants to have reached 50 % off the habitants with information about more plant based, local and organic food. Haarlem works closely with (residents) initiatives and entrepreneurs to realise a sustainable food system. HARL focus on reducing food waste, promoting a sustainable and healthy food choice and preventing/reducing food waste and stimulating biodiversity through urban farming initiatives. In the coming years we will intensify cooperation with initiatives in Haarlem. A circular economy action program will follow at the end of 2022. This is a practical translation of the goals from the Sustainability Roadmap. The Action Program encompasses the actions necessary up to and including 2025 to achieve these goals. We will have a special focus on inclusion, to make sure sustainable food is accessible for everybody. Our expertise in the field will be further shared, we want to set up a durable, sustainable and valuable cooperation with academic partners (IVM, Aeres Hogeschool, Inholland, Novacollege en de Koepel in Haarlem).

4.2 Industrial and business exploitation plans

Cities2030 innovative solutions provide a competitive advantage while enlarging the market footprint, knowledge base, and services portfolio of the beneficiaries and companies involved.

The engagement activities raise awareness of the benefits of implementing sustainable CRFS measures across a diverse spectrum of agents. This will establish trust and form a valuable cohort of early adopters to accelerate the exploitation of the results in the EU.

In Table 15 partners describe possibilities in developing, creating, or marketing demand and need-driven solutions, products, services or processes, multi-actor dynamics, integrated cross/multi-sectoral value-chains, etc..

Table 15: Industrial exploitation plans

Partner	Industrial and business exploitation plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
1-UNIVE	Not applicable
2-EPC	Thanks to the expertise acquired during project implementation, EPC will be able to support small and medium municipalities willing to join the MUFPP or to start a path to raise awareness on sustainable CRFS measures in their territory, accompanying the institution throughout the process (stakeholder engagement, identification of possible sources of EU funding, etc..) Likewise, the Living Lab approach implemented in cities2030 CFRS Labs, can be exploited by EPC in other EU funded projects with different thematics, such as urban regeneration, climate change, risks and adaptation.

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3-BRUG	The city will further encourage local businesses and organisations to implement the basic principles of our food policy, taking into account the experiences towards our target group from the Bruges living lab, 65+ and the sustainable meal deliveries from Riddersstove.
3a-BRUG	WP5: we will engage and involve industrial stakeholders (such as delivery businesses and interest groups) in the preparation and implementation of the experimental challenges. In the case one of our experiments in our living lab is successful, we will try to scale up this best practice towards our suppliers or non-profit colleagues in a shared profit model.
3a-BRUG	Our experiences with the living lab experiments (WP5) will be further shared in other service centres. More specific info on experiments to be updated in next editions.
4-VIVES	WP5: we will engage and involve industrial stakeholders (such as delivery businesses and interest groups) in the preparation and implementation of the experimental challenges.
5-IAAD	Not applicable
6-INAG	WP5
7-UNRF	Not applicable
8-VEGO	WP5 -LL: Rural laboratory for local producers. We plan to establish an informal educational program aimed to strengthen the capacity of agricultural producers. Exploitation plan - to organise a series of education and presentation of innovations. Initially, the target group are farmers from the City and the surrounding municipalities, with the possibility of expansion to the entire county and beyond. Considering the established relations with stakeholders, among whom there is a large number of consultants and lecturers, the sustainability of the project results is planned to be ensured by continuous organisation of lectures, in regular cycles. IPR not applicable.
9-INVE	WP5 -LL: Rural laboratory for local producers. We plan to establish an informal educational program aimed to strengthen the capacity of agricultural producers. Exploitation plan - to organise a series of education and presentation of innovations. Initially, the target group are farmers from the City and the surrounding municipalities, with the possibility of expansion to the entire county and beyond. Considering the established relations with stakeholders, among whom there is a large number of consultants and lecturers, the sustainability of the project results is planned to be ensured by continuous organisation of lectures, in regular cycles. IPR not applicable.
10-VEJLE	WP3, WP5, WP4: We will create "gastro days", where we bring together local businesses, entrepreneurs etc. The focus is to promote and implement food policy in Vejle Municipality.
11-QUA	Not applicable
12-INTO	<u>WP5 / Healthy Snacks</u> : The city will further encourage regional development of healthy and sustainable nutrition for children in via pursuit of active co-creation with sport clubs, schools, parents and children and multi-disciplinary design. Innovative need-driven solutions to improve healthy snacks for children will create competitive advantages for sport clubs, while taking food production companies involved in the multi-actor ecosystem.
13-AGRIA	WP5 / School canteens into school restaurants: The school that will be planned and built/renovated or schools that just want to improve their studying environment in the canteen (lunch in Finland is considered as an educational time as well), can take the pilot model as an example for their actions. The decision makers of school buildings are the target group: school principal and city's technical and education departments but also students' and parents' boards. WP5/ Kids' food festival: The idea is free to use also for profit-seeking festivals. The children's awareness of food may lead to change the consumers behaviour in the future and change the food business. WP5/ Food business club: The youngsters train to be food business entrepreneurs. This paves the way for working/making food business later in the youngsters' lives. The intention is to widen the existing Finnish Hobby mode so that the business hobby clubs will get more financing.
14-SLEANN	Lahti Living Lab SMARTY: IoT-equipped food waste composter: Lahti Living Lab's operation as a participatory and multi-actor testbed for technology development encourages the development of small-scale testbed services further. The testbed service can be addressed to a private business customers or regional

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	<p>development companies. Communication and promotion about small-scale Lahti Living Lab testbed service. RDI funding initiatives. The testbed service has no IPR issues.</p> <p>Living Lab: Partner continues the exploitation of participatory and open innovation ecosystem - Lahti Living Lab - to foster FOOD2030 policy with Lahti city, Regional Council of Päijät-Häme and local food industry and value chain actors, particularly, particularly SMEs and local food companies.</p>
15-BRH	<p>The city will further encourage regional development of regional, healthy and sustainable nutrition for community catering via pursuit of active co-creation with the regional food board, schools, administration/ health department and multi-disciplinary groups of actors and experts</p> <p>BRH will also take into account the experiences from our target group of the Bremerhaven living lab and the experiences and learning activities listed in table: Challenges, innovation actions and innovation action results.</p>
16-TTZ	<p>TTZ cooperates with well-known German associations (e.g. NaGeb, GDL) and will promote the results of CITIS2030 in the network. TTZ will increase efforts in designing services and processes in support of the food council and the local community and will take into account the experiences from our target group of the Bremerhaven living lab and the experiences and learning activities listed in table: Challenges, innovation actions and innovation action results. TTZ is currently launching activities to make current innovations in food production accessible to smaller, regional companies.</p>
17-BIOZ	<p>Product exploitation as well as potential processes, services and know-how generated from stakeholder involvement and specific innovation potential of cities on food and food related technologies. BIOZ will also take into account the experiences from our target group of the Bremerhaven living lab and the experiences and learning activities listed in table: Challenges, innovation actions and innovation action results.</p>
18-QUAR	<p>WP3: The city will create a cooperation group with stakeholders (local businesses, large companies, entrepreneurs, etc.) in order to promote and implement the food policy.</p>
19-SINNO	<p>SINNO will co-design and elaborate industrial exploitation plans with industrial members of SINNO deploying services developed in CITIES 2030 and it will monitor social spaces, living labs and policy labs evolution using MAA Tool for industrial stakeholders</p>
20-UPM	<p>Components that are exclusively produced by UPM's personnel, related to the Cities2030 scope, will be subject to IPR ownership registration. UPM has already registered our software "private communication component, Privately". To do that, UPM has counted to the Research Results Transfer Office (OTRI) which facilitates the registration process with the regional patent and trademark office. UPM plans to register at least two more software components in the last year of the project.</p>
21-WIT	<p>The components and algorithms solely developed by SETU, related to data governance will be subject to SETU IPR policy. We plan to further exploit these in future work relating to reducing food waste.</p>
22-MATIS	<p>Not applicable</p>
23-FFI	<p>The Paideia Campus Living Lab will increase efforts in designing services and processes in support of the local community, also thank to the recently signed agreement with ADI, the Industrial Design Association that brings together designers, companies, researchers, teachers, critics, and journalists since 1956 around design issues: design, consumption, recycling, education. Specific attention will also be paid to "feeding" the sense of community and local pride, starting from the value of sustainable diets such as the Mediterranean diet, and the implementation and support of new business models able to counteract brain drains, depopulation and concretely supporting regenerative agricultural practices from the local area.</p>
24-VPR	<p><u>WP5/Food Hackathon</u>: Promotion and exploitation of innovative action results generated during LL to produce and provide in the market sustainable food products, thus creating preconditions for securing healthy and sustainable food and strengthening regional producers/processors and short local food chains.</p>
25-LLF	<p>Not applicable</p>
26-GGP	<p>Not applicable</p>
27-AGFT	<p>The initial Business Model Canvases prepared within WP5 are a great foundation for all CRFS Labs to build on to further develop the CRFS Labs' exploitable outcomes into market ready solutions, by engaging with industry leaders, innovation managers, business development experts, and consultants.</p>

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28-IASI	Not applicable
29-ARFI	Scientific research for shortening the food chains and increasing the access to the markets for the local producers.
30-ICTM	Component of the S2CP that is addressing the traceability application is a subject of IPR. Usage of the DIH AGRIFOOD platform is also a subject of IPR and discussion among the partnership.
31-CORR	Correlate Software as a Services target digital individuals, students, workers, freelancers, teams and organisations who need tools for organising, sharing and managing knowledge in context. We plan to enable Cities2030 participants with a function to publish their correlated files and content in contextual boards sharing with all project stakeholders.
32-VIZ	Not applicable
32a-LaVi	Not applicable
33-IVM	Not applicable
34-MOMS	Not applicable
35-Uni.l u	Industrial & Business activities: one key exploitation is the cooperation with a real Blockchain company called UNISOT in Norway to build the Blockchain pilot for Cities2030 for a couple of test pilots in the project and then use the experience and knowledge to build in-house expertise to propose new Blockchain projects not only for the Food Supply chain but for all kind of logistics supply chains and more specifically for the Autonomous vehicular supply chain with a view of motivating a start-up to focus on this new field. Actively seek partnerships with industries that have a mutual interest in Sentiment Analysis and Blockchain technology. Joint research projects could be funded by both the university and the industrial partners.
36-UCC	Not applicable
37-PRIM	Not applicable
38-IUAV	<u>Activation and promotion of the "Fisherman's House" at Punta Sabbioni (Cavallino-Treporti):</u> the creation of an operational centre for the Fishermen's Cooperative will contribute to create a stable reference point for the sale and consumption of fish, supporting the Cooperative's activities economically. <u>Identification of potential gastronomic uses of lagoon edible wild vegetation:</u> Studying potential gastronomic uses of lagoon wild edible vegetation can favour both an income integration for fishermen and/or farmers, and new gastronomic offerings related to typicality.
39-RTU	Not applicable
40-CITAG	Not applicable
41-HARL	Expansion of the Koplopergroep Circular Restaurants with concrete projects and collaborations Drawing up a food vision for Haarlem with a focus on the protein transition. Haarlem starts or intensifies (in a regional context) several collaborations with various parties in the food chain. Implementation City Deal Sustainable and Healthy Food Environment. Haarlem actively shares its experience in the field of circular food systems with entrepreneurs, knowledge institutes and other government authorities, for example in the network of Food Connects. Haarlem is committed to a stronger lobby towards the government to stimulate the protein transition.

4.3 Financial and market exploitation plans

Table 16 shows the partners' plans, which are in line with the Cities2040 CRFS investment framework which is defined in chapter 1.4 in the Grant Agreement. CITIES2030 aims to define a route for continuing the operations of Cities2030 by exploiting selected most promising Key Exploitable Results through a network for follow-up, created and run by the Cities2030 project partners.

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The financial and market exploitation plan can embrace actions such as:

- “Go-to-market” strategy and plan. In this task, partners will develop a practical go-to-market plan that will be the basis for future activities in commercialising the selected KERs. The plan will be partly based on the outcomes from T5.2 and T5.3, outlining the most potential target segments and potential customers identified. The plan will give a detailed overview of the timeline, incl. additional development needs and financial needs associated with exploiting the KERs.
- IPR Protection Strategy. An IPR Protection Strategy will be developed that will suggest the most appropriate IP protection means (patenting, trademark protection, trade secrets, copyrights etc). that helps to protect the KERs. This strategy will ensure long term strategic protection and a competitive advantage on the market.
- Actions to raise additional funds for the exploitation of results and further commercialization:
 - Mobilising Private and Public Funds
 - Mobilising European Funds
 - Mobilising Structural Fund through connecting with Regional and National Authorities

Table 16: Financial and market exploitation plans

Partner	Financial and market exploitation plan
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? ● Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). ● Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
1-UNIVE	Not applicable
2-EPC	Not applicable
3-BRUG	WP5 'Intergenerational Cooking'
3a-BRUG	Not applicable
3a-BRUG	Not applicable
4-VIVES	Not applicable
5-IAAD	Not applicable
6-INAG	WP5:We will further exploit the training material made for workshop techniques and utilize them in projects with private partners to better elucidate their needs and align them with the needs of food producers.
7-UNRF	Not applicable
8-VEGO	WP4 -PL - "Farmers market" or some other alternative model of distribution of local products A survey conducted among consumers and producers indicated the need to establish a suitable model for better accessibility of local products.The plan is to define a feasible solution adapted to the requirements of both consumers and producers.
9-INVE	WP4 -PL - "Farmers market" or some other alternative model of distribution of local products A survey conducted among consumers and producers indicated the need to establish a suitable model for better accessibility of local products.The plan is to define a feasible solution adapted to the requirements of both consumers and producers
10-VEJLE	Not applicable
11-QUA	Not applicable

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Partner	Financial and market exploitation plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
12-INTO	<u>WP5/Healthy Snacks</u> : The aim is to encourage sport clubs' kiosks to make their businesses out of the healthy snacks and food. In addition, there is a purpose to ask if the firms could develop new healthy snack products that are suitable for the sport clubs' purposes.
13-AGRI A	<u>WP5/The Food Business Club</u> : The aim is that the youngsters will have their own food businesses and that they can create new food products and food-related services to the local markets.
14-SLEA N	SLEAN has leveraged Cities2030 practices and results in new Horizon Europe projects such as PoliRuralPlus and KijaniSpace. Also Cities has given input and ideas for INTERREG Baltic Sea Region project ChangeKnow.
15-BRH	Not applicable
16-TTZ	Not applicable
17-BIOZ	Not applicable
18-QUAR	Not applicable
19-SINN O	To be updated in next editions when next proposals might be successful or when additional fundings from involved living labs were available
20-UPM	Not applicable
21-WIT	Not applicable
22-MATI S	Not applicable
23-FFI	The Living Lab is intended to collect additional fundings thanks to public and private partnerships that we value also through multi-stakeholder events, meetings, activities.
24-VPR	Not applicable
25-LLF	Is going to support local action groups to attract investments for development of food short supply chains. Government is planing to invest in this topic 16 mil. EUR.
26-GGP	Not applicable
27-AGFT	Not applicable
28-IASI	"Iașul în bucate tradiționale, ecologice, montane și artizanale" (The fair of Iași in traditional, bio, mountain, and artisanal dishes) is a fair addressing local producers and consumers. Here consumers can meet, learn about, and purchase high-value products on the shortest food supply chain.
29-ARFI	"Iașul în bucate tradiționale, ecologice, montane și artizanale" (The Fair of Iași in traditional, bio, mountain, and artisanal dishes) is a fair where local producers show and sell their products to consumers. Here consumers can meet, learn about, and purchase high-value products on the shortest food supply chain.
30-ICTM	Involved solution providers will be helped in order to reach new market opportunities. Also development of the traceability app, will be a subject of further exploitation. Exploitation plan is also addressing the project outcomes that will be taken into new project applications in order to advance the results in either a regional aspect or also nation wide.
31-CORR	Our business model target hyper growth and we aim to raise additional funding through private investors, venture capital and/or public financing. This is done through participation in events, seminars and networks such as Websummit, Eureka events as well as networking and activities targeting national and international private and public opportunities. Our current IPR strategy includes trademarks, copyright

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Partner	Financial and market exploitation plan
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	and secrecy source code.
32-VIZ	Not applicable
32a-LaVi	Not applicable
33-IVM	Not applicable
34-MOM S	Not applicable
35-Uni.lu	Grants and Funding: Actively apply for academic and industry grants that align with the research focus, effectively turning research proposals into revenue-generating activities.
36-UCC	Not applicable
37-PRIM	Not applicable
38-IUAV	Not applicable
39-RTU	Not applicable
40-CITAG	Not applicable
41-HARL	Making the circular transition measurable, for example using the sustainability budget. Collaborate with financial service companies (banks) to reach and guide businesses in Haarlem. Working together in knowledge sharing. Stimulating entrepreneurship with impact. Implementation lies with the Action Program Impact Entrepreneurship 2020 - 2024 (Action Line 4). Haarlem will start in 2024 with a subsidy to stimulate circular business operations. Haarlem is investigating whether fees can be reduced to stimulate circular activity.

4.4 Societal exploitation plans

Acceleration through the public sector contributes to the exploitation of Cities2030 results by raising awareness across the CRFS arena, addressing, in particular, the lack of awareness of citizens of the benefits of taking measures towards the transition to sustainable CRFS.

In the table 17 partners foresight how to exploit results in multi-actor and participatory solutions e.g. Citizen Sensing, Citizen Science, Living Labs, social spaces, ethics, gender balance, RRI etc.

Table 17: Societal exploitation plans

Partner	Societal exploitation plans
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
1-UNIVE	Not applicable
2-EPC	Not applicable
3-BRUG	We will keep targeting elderly in the implementation of our social welfare plan and food policy & use the

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Partner	Societal exploitation plans
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	experiences in the living labs (WP5) to do so. More specific info on learnings in the next editions.
3a-BRUG	We communicated with multiple stakeholders and members of the target population, where we raised awareness concerning healthy food for elderly, accessibility of food, food delivery systems..
3a-BRUG	Our experiences with the living lab experiments (WP5) will be further shared in other service centres. More specific info on experiments to be updated in next editions.
4-VIVES	We communicated with multiple stakeholders and members of the target population, where we raised awareness concerning healthy food for elderly, accessibility of food, food delivery systems..
5-IAAD	Not applicable
6-INAG	<u>Raising awareness & communication:</u> Agrotopia receives visitors and stakeholders and has developed information and stakeholder engagement approaches under the project (WP3, WP and WP7) and will continue to update and use this <u>Educational activities:</u> school packages to visit Agrotopia have been developed (WP7) and will continue to be updated and used
7-UNRF	Not applicable
8-VEGO	WP4 - PL - Analysis of existing grants and supporting schemes (local, regional and national); Exploitation plan: review of criteria and method of evaluation, definition of new indicators with the guidelines to relevant institutions for improving monitoring measures and methods. Target group - small agricultural producers, citizens of the rural area. IPR not applicable
9-INVE	WP 4 & WP5: Robin Food - social supermarket and the importance of donating food. Exploitation plan - a series of conferences on the topic of food donation - legislation, possibilities and obstacles. Additionally, the activities should be linked to the food waste reduction plan - the result described in table 15. Target groups - representatives of regulators, traders and trade chains, manufacturers, civil associations. IRP not applicable
10-VEJLE	WP5: the event "Fjorden på bordet/ from inlet/sea to table" - the goal of this is to spread awareness/knowledge to the general public that the ecosystem is in dire straits in Vejle Inlet. Also inspire people to do something about this problem. Culinary Institute is hosting cooking competitions to strengthen innovation amongst professional chefs and also children in the public school system. Our focus is on strengthening local companies and their products.
11-QUA	Not applicable
12-INTO	<u>WP5 / Healthy Snacks:</u> Communication to stakeholders is to develop understanding of children's healthy nutrition and to equip sport clubs with tools to manage their healthy snacks canteens, with a focus on the importance of nutrition and the empowerment of youth. The living lab results to be exploited combats the current gap of healthy hobby but wrong snacks provided via the providing sport club. The content developed for the healthy snack canteen includes a free activity plan for "Sustainable and Healthy Snacks Canteen", the concept idea, logo, posters, social media content and video series. The plan is to exploit WP5 results of the Seinäjoki Living Lab Mahtikiska/Healthy Snacks. As told above, Mahtikiska is a ready-made concept that stakeholders can utilise in their actions easily. Target group of the result will be stakeholders, who can exploit the result into their actions, such as the City of Seinäjoki who could involve the concept or the idea into their city strategy planning to develop youths' health. We're planning on spreading the concept with the help of an illustration made from the living lab concept (found here on row 165). We're also planning to spread the results to different health organisations such as Ruukku Ry (a Finnish food education society). IPR doesn't have an impact on spreading the results.

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Prepared by P14, P28, all partners | Edited by P14 | Checked and reviewed by ExeCom | Approved by P1

Version V.3 –21.11.2023

Partner	<p>Societal exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
	<p>During the spring of 2024 we have also shared the ideology of Mahtikiska healthy snacks concept to sports clubs via Mahtiseura-contest. In the contest sports clubs are posting pictures of their healthy snacks to social media, and get points in the competition by doing so. The competition started in February and is ongoing until the end of July. More information (written in Finnish for the sport club representatives) is found here. Shared file to the competitions social media materials is found here. IPR doesn't have an impact on spreading the results.</p>
13-AGRI A	<p><u>WP5/ Food business club</u>: The youngsters grow to be active citizens in the society from the early age. They learn skills that are needed in all ages (networking, co-working, taking responsibility, to meet challenges, measure and take a risk). There are niche markets that youngsters can take over to serve marginal groups of consumers. <u>WP5 / School canteens into school restaurants</u>: The societal benefit is to have the youngsters to learn to eat proper healthy food with a good eating rhythm and understand the other aspects of food expect for energy and nutrition. To make this happen the ones who decide how school lunches are organized are in the key role of change. The youngsters are involved in the planning process. <u>WP5/ Kids' food festival</u>: The children learn how food is grown and processed before it is on the plate. The children are more aware as consumers of local food. The festival, in which the food education is done, is free of charge for the attendees.</p>
14-SLEA N	<p>Lahti Living Lab bokashi experiment good practice: "Timely, versatile, and multi-actor nudging framework to promote food waste reuse and circulation to the new regime." SLEAN aims to exploit the experience of multi-actor nudging addressed to local (Päijät-Häme region) policymakers, authorities, businesses and households. The nudging promotes FOOD2030 policy. Lahti Living Lab open innovation environment provides a good environment for exploitation. No IPR concern.</p> <p>WP5/1: SLEAN will exploit the concept of Extended Innovation Pattern (EIP) or parts of it, the associated Handbook, and the experience of executing and implementing task 5.2 in the context of the Cities2030 consortium. Multi-actor target group in Päijät-Häme e.g. Regional Council of Päijät-Häme, 11 regional municipalities, NGOs e.g. Mallusjoki Youth Association. The idea is to combine practical grass-root level activities with systemic transition missions. The pathway to exploitation is to initiate a common project which contributes to topics like food waste recycling, sustainability, carbon neutrality, and multi-actor engagement and empowerment. The aim is to contribute to the FOOD2030 policy and local stakeholders participation. No IPR concern.</p> <p>WP5/2: SLEAN will take into use some of the brainstorming tools that were presented in the LL Innovation Facilitator's training. Brainstorming tool for consulting assignments e.g. industrial and service companies, and households. No IPR concern.</p>
15-BRH	Societal improvement and public knowledge to food related innovations of potential at city level
16-TTZ	Societal improvement and public knowledge to food related innovations of potential at city level
17-BIOZ	Societal improvement and public knowledge to food related innovations of potential at city level

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Prepared by P14, P28, all partners | Edited by P14 | Checked and reviewed by ExeCom | Approved by P1

Version V.3 –21.11.2023

Partner	<p>Societal exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
18-QUAR	<p>App for food value chain, WP5 and WP6/111), Food Value Chain Living Lab: The developed and tested Blockchain solution is susceptible to exploitation as its use among consumers and farmers is quite feasible and could be expanded in society. It is a user-friendly application, open to the public and whose ultimate goal is the transfer of information on products, their origin and traceability from farmers to consumers. Target users/groups: -Farmers of the Valencian citrus sector. However, it may be replicable in other sectors. -Final consumers. Pathways to exploitation: Its function and usefulness has been highly accepted by suppliers, and it would only be necessary to promote its use among consumers for the App to be deployed. This would be quite feasible since, increasingly, consumer interest in knowing the origin of food and buying local products is growing. In addition to promoting its use, another pending task to be included in the exploitation plan would be the introduction of the improvements and proposals requested by the suppliers (basically farmers). After that, the application would have a close, local and proximity character. By scanning the QR code of a food product, the consumer would be able to know the origin and traceability of the product and, therefore, the entire food value chain. Besides that, it would have a human dimension, as the consumer would be able to see a picture and a short story, as well as the field of the farmer from whom the fruit, vegetable or meat comes. This innovation has a strong exploitation potential as the app is already created so it does not require a considerable investment.</p> <p>Identification of invaders of lands", WP4 and WP5/159, Food Value Chain Living Lab: A group of 16 urban farmers has been identified and engaged in the project with the collaboration of LIMNE Foundation. Once the legal urban gardens in the municipality are enabled, these will be the first to acquire them, giving them absolute priority in the allocation of the lots. Target users/groups: 16 invaders of lands as urban farmers. Pathways to exploitation: They have a potential to leverage their involvement and willingness to practise urban agriculture in Quart de Poblet. They could participate as a target group or working group in future initiatives of the City Council of Quart de Poblet and the LIMNE Foundation.</p> <p>Briefing session: Engagement of invaders of lands, WP4 and WP5 160, Food Value Chain Living Lab. Target users/groups: 16 invaders of lands as urban farmers. Pathways to exploitation: The availability of 16 urban farmers is susceptible to exploitation in new urban gardens that are not being exploited or have been abandoned in the Municipality of Quart de Poblet.</p> <p>Co-creation for new urban gardens", WP4 and WP5/161), Food Value Chain Living Lab. Target users/groups: 10 invaders of lands as urban farmers. Pathways to exploitation: The 10 invaders who have participated in the co-creation of a solution to relocate the gardens elsewhere after vacating the natural park of the River Túria, will be given absolute priority in the allocation of the 40 urban gardens owned by the City Council. In this way, we can ensure that they will no longer occupy public spaces to convert them into illegal allotments and, at the same time, practise ecological urban agriculture in the municipality.</p>
19-SINNO	<p>Societal improvement and public knowledge to food related innovations of potential at city level. SINNO will participate in the Arganda LAB with UPM and will launch another Living Lab in 2023 dealing with breweries with small producers in Spain and Europe under a new start up called CERVEZANAS.</p>

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Partner	<p>Societal exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
20-UPM	<p>Results of the Arganda Lab related to these two challenges: "Monitoring of relevant environment parameters of food production processes" and "Facilitating food transparency in supply chain" will be disseminated to interested parties, which are food consumers, workers of food processing company and other participants in the food supply chain. The aim is to obtain recommendations for the current results to improve this application and adapt it to real food production scenarios. Some press releases have been generated so far.</p>
21-WIT	<p>SETU will promote the project's results at agri-food events in Ireland. This includes promotion at the "International Ploughing Championship", and various sustainable food events organised in Ireland. These results will also be incorporated into teaching materials in courses such as "Sustainable Farm Management and Agribusiness" to highlight the benefits of a regional approach to food production.</p>
22-MATIS	<p>Not applicable</p>
23-FFI	<p>The Living Lab aims to start from the lessons learnt from the experiments, actions, and achievements of these months to increase its impact in length, width, and depth. In terms of women empowerment, programs such EWA (Empowering Women in Agriculture) by EIT Food, runned in Italy from Future Food Institute or the one with Circe, that connected forward looking female agro-preneurs with the local context, can ease the realization of the first Gender library in Pollica. Also other activities, such as the realization of a calendar with the faces and recipes of the Mediterranean grandmothers will be concrete examples to collect traditional and sustainable mediterranean recipes and better connect the local territory. Better protecting the Mediterranean environment and fostering human health will also be the objective of the Cilento Air Quality Lab, a centralized data collection and visualization platform that can be installed also in local schools to foster environmental and wellbeing parameters. Additional activities to increase the sense of active citizenship and active engagement will be organized, starting from the power of food, through educational courses on regeneration, digital academy, workshops with local producers and children to sensitize and increase adherence to the Mediterranean Diet, direct collaborations with local and journals, but also strengthening the relationship between members of other Emblematic Communities of the Mediterranean Diet. Spaces and places will be improved and rethought: starting from the results achieved by the Pollica digital week and community engagement in designing processes (such as the first community hackathon to improve local services), the Living Lab will continue fostering events, conviviality moments, photo marathons in the village to increase awareness on Mediterranean Diet.</p>
24-VPR	<p>Latvian LL pilot tackle the existing challenges in the REGIONAL FOOD SUPPLY SYSTEM in the territory of the Vidzeme Planning Region. The experience gained during implementation of the LL will be used for further initiatives, aimed to engage stakeholders, to create productive dialogue among different groups in order to search and find solutions on how to develop and strengthen sustainable and resilient food supply chains. Target groups are: municipalities, farmers, food processors, retailers, as well consumers.</p>
25-LLF	<p><i>Local food for healthy kids</i>: The aim of active workshops in rural areas with local producers and kids from kindergarten was to promote a healthy lifestyle, to introduce kids with local products and to develop responsible consumption behaviours to reduce the food waste in kindergartens. <i>Green procurement - an instrument to support local food producers</i>. To encourage local governments to form clusters of joint cooperation, involving local food producers and processors, caterers, nutritionists, school representatives, in order to promote the development of short food supply chains in the territory, to reduce food waste and support a local circular economy.</p>
26-GGP	<p>Good practice dashboard (WP7) will be shared with the network of stakeholders in Cities2030 Alliance and beyond for potential replication in local context.</p>
27-AGFT	<p>Increase public awareness and engagement by educating the public about innovative business models and their benefits (WP3 - Contributing to Cities 2030 Observatory by identifying local good practices).</p>

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Partner	<p>Societal exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
28-IASI	<p>Healthy food for healthy kids: Demonstration workshops with local producers addressing schoolchildren from Iași. The overall aim is to raise the trust level in healthy food products and develop responsible purchase and consumption behaviours.</p>
29-ARFI	<p>Gust de Iasi (Taste of Iași) integration with Cities2030: Building an umbrella brand for local producers who bring added value to the urban food system. The producers will be selected according to a multi-criteria selection tool that comprises the following categories: environmental protection, durability, nutritional value, accessibility, continuity, cultural value.</p> <p>Integration of local producers with cyclo tourism networks: integration actions of urban food consumers with local producers through the development of local cyclo tourism networks of gastronomic inspiration from and around Iași city.</p>
30-ICT M	Not applicable
31-COR R	Correlate are developing digital tools to collaborate, share and publish context resulting from scattered files and content.
32-VIZ	<p>The Municipality of Vicenza intends to exploit the results achieved in the first part of the project mostly to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) raise awareness about the importance of a sustainable and healthy food system and improve involvement/active participation of citizens in the framework of a co-creation process. In synergy with WP5 living labs, particular attention will be devoted to school canteens directly managed by the Municipality of Vicenza to foster a greater collaboration between the local administrators and the families 2) encourage the involvement of local food related retailers and SMEs in local experiments to promote km0 and the farm-to-fork approach, to reduce food waste and support a local circular economy 3) develop initiatives in the field of a more sustainable tourism which could in turn support a more sustainable food economy 4) explore the opportunities for improving the visibility and awareness on the food related issues which are particularly close to the female perspective so to reduce the impact of stereotypes and promote a new narrative and greater understanding
32a-LaVi	<p>The results achieved so far through awareness will be used by the International Library La Vigna as an engine for maintaining and developing further relationships and collaborations with local educational institutions, promoting renewed activities related to the themes of the CRFS.</p> <p>Furthermore, the plan sees the continuous search for local networks and partnerships to disseminate and raise awareness among citizens for an increasingly sustainable food model.</p>
33-IVM	Not applicable
34-MOMS	Awareness rising and communication activities.
35-Uni.l u	<p>Public Awareness and Education</p> <p>Community Outreach Programs: Conduct workshops, seminars, and awareness campaigns to educate the public on technologies like Sentiment Analysis and Blockchain, and their societal applications.</p> <p>Online Resources: Develop accessible online tutorials, articles, and webinars aimed at demystifying complex technologies for the general public.</p> <p>Social Innovation</p> <p>Environmental Sustainability: Use Blockchain technology for ensuring transparency and traceability in supply chains for sustainable products.</p> <p>Data Privacy and Security: Educate the public and government agencies on the importance of data privacy, and how technologies like Blockchain can provide solutions.</p>
36-UCC	Not applicable

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Partner	<p>Societal exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
37-PRIM	Not applicable
38-IUAV	<p><u>The Venice Lagoon Food Festival</u>: the festival will be a widespread event in the area that will seek to involve the entire lagoon system, creating a meeting point between producers, restaurateurs, traders, citizens associations, and citizens eager to fully understand the history and culture of food in the Venice Lagoon. The festival will also strengthen the sense of belonging and to engage individuals of all ages in a discussion about the food system.</p> <p><u>A cultural project to disseminate the cultural heritage of fishing in the lagoon</u>: Fishing heritage is considered an asset linked to tradition, local economies, and knowledge and it should be protected and promoted to ensure its survival. Activities will contribute to the enhancement of fishing cultural heritage and to raise awareness for the population and visitors.</p> <p><u>Cultural platform on the relationship between food and the lagoon</u>: the platform will share a new socio-cultural relationship between food and lagoon by promoting the territory through its food-related elements of typicality. Activities will raise awareness and will disseminate local knowledge about gastronomy.</p>
39-RTU	<p>Awareness rising and communication activities by creating ROAD GAME in 2023 in digital format and onsite in RTU student campus in Kipsala (lively area in Riga city, capital). The game will include various questions/puzzles to be solved by players regarding the food system, short food chains, impact and project Cities2030 partnership. Players will visit the project web page to find answers.</p> <p>Main target group/users - youth aged 18-30; RTU students and international students located at Kipsala campus; general public interested into ROAD GAMES.</p>
40-CITAG	<p>CITAG cooperates with an important number of stakeholders. This is true both for its Cities2030 related activities as well as for its other projects. These existing links with civil society, local authorities and local businesses present great opportunities for future exploitation of the WP4 and WP5 results.</p> <p>WP4, guide Capri : the guide from the Capri urban farm is thought as a guide to help urban farmers and urban food projects learn from the Capri experiment, and will thus be shared on a national level through stakeholders networks (AFAUP, RMT, RENETA, etc.). WP4, farm land in Marseille : CITAG's participation in Sols Vivants collective, a multi stakeholder dynamic in Marseille, is delivering important inputs and will be shared with a larger audience in 2024 (citizens, policy makers). WP5 : local CRFS observatory : the collected and processed data will be shared with stakeholders in public events and conferences to enhance citizen knowledge and engagement in the Marseille lab.</p>
41-HARL	<p>Everything Haarlem does to stimulate a circular economy explicitly mentions how we ensure that everyone can participate. Haarlem continues to focus on integrated cooperation and strengthens the link between the social and physical domains within the municipality. We do this, for example, through the Sustainable and Healthy Food Environment City Deal and the Impact Entrepreneurship Action Programme. Affordable circular solutions are actively stimulated and safeguarded in the city. Examples include tailors, cobblers, thrift stores, and repair shops. Haarlem has annual campaigns with a focus on combating food waste and stimulating a circular food choice. Think of vegetable, organic, seasonal and local products. In addition, the campaign focuses on stimulating biodiversity through urban farming initiatives. Haarlem works closely with Haarlem entrepreneurs and city makers. Haarlem works intensively with (residents) initiatives and entrepreneurs to realise a sustainable food system.</p> <p>Examples are Haarlem Food Future, the Plukweide , Ecoring, We grow vegetables, Free waterland, These initiatives have started various projects to increase biodiversity, among other things. In the coming years we will intensify cooperation with initiatives in Haarlem.</p>

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

4.5 Policy and governance exploitation plans

In Table 18 partners outline how they could exploit project results in the policymaking and -implementation. For instance to feed regional and national policymakers to bring CRFS issues into policy agenda, conduct policy analysis, and analytics, explore decision-making pathways to generate structured materials for enactment, and evaluate policy performance and impassiveness. Governance exploitation plan e.g., to liaise with a vast number of global, EU and national level CRFS clusters, networks and communities.

Table 18: Policy and governance exploitation plans

Partner	Policy and governance exploitation plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? ● Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). ● Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
1-UNIVE	Not applicable
2-EPC	Not applicable
3-BRUG	We will share the results of the living lab in the stakeholders platform (Bruges food lab) and will share it in the MUFPP network and Glasgow food&climate network. We will learn from the experiences to further encourage external partners to implement the basic principles of our food policy, for example the experiences of Riddersstove with sustainable meal deliveries.
3a-BRUG	WP4 & WP 5: we will engage and involve policy stakeholders (such as Food Lab Bruges, the municipality of Bruges and other interest groups) in the preparation and implementation of the experimental challenges.
3a-BRUG	Our experiences with the living lab experiments (WP5) will be further used in the policies & governance of our service centres. More specific info on learnings to be updated in next editions.
4-VIVES	WP5: we will engage and involve policy stakeholders (such as Food Lab Bruges, the municipality of Bruges and other interest groups) in the preparation and implementation of the experimental challenges.
5-IAAD	Not applicable
6-INAG	Not applicable
7-UNRF	Not applicable
8-VEGO	WP4 -PL: Food waste reduction Based on the national food waste reduction plan for the Republic of Croatia based on UN Agenda Food 2030 (30% reduction till 2030), our goal is to create an implementation plan at the City level. In addition to public administration, the plan will also include stakeholders from other sectors - institutions, entrepreneurs, civil organisations. Activities will be based on the methodology and proposed indicators from the MUFPP. Part of the Plan is signing the Voluntary Agreement which will show the commitment to the mentioned plan and our part is to explore the activities and barriers to achieve the above mentioned goal. Besides, this plan will be a powerful tool for further collaboration with the City of Zagreb and Zagreb County.
9-INVE	WP4 -PL: Food waste reduction Based on the national food waste reduction plan for the Republic of Croatia based on UN Agenda Food 2030 (30% reduction till 2030), our goal is to create an implementation plan at the City level. In addition to public administration, the plan will also include stakeholders from other sectors - institutions, entrepreneurs, civil organisations. Activities will be based on the methodology and proposed indicators from the MUFPP. Part of the Plan is signing the Voluntary Agreement which will show the commitment to the mentioned plan and our part is to explore the activities and barriers to achieve the above mentioned goal. Besides, this plan will be a powerful tool for further collaboration with the City of Zagreb and Zagreb County.

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Partner	<p>Policy and governance exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
10-VEJLE	Not applicable
11-QUA	Through its institutional connections within the Veneto Region, Quantitas may be able to raise awareness on CRFS-related topics and issues, which may be reflected in political actions at a regional level. Additionally, it aims to leverage its expertise in data analytics to provide consultancy to both private and public institutions highlighting and building on the CRFS-related analytical findings emerging from CITIES 20230 - with a specific focus on CITIES 2030 Observatory.
12-INTO	Into will use results from WP4 and 5 to assist policy makers to implement a healthy and sustainable food policy in all children related actions (e.g. policies, food services, school restaurant environment, sports clubs, children's festivals, food business clubs). The aim is to integrate related food strategies into plans to improve children's health and wellbeing. Into will inform and encourage the community around children to be involved in developing, implementing and evaluating healthy eating and encourage healthy and sustainable nutrition as the norm and serve as a role model. Promoting good nutrition is a multidisciplinary collaboration between several administrative sectors, different sectors of the municipality, the business community, organisations and regional actors. Policymaking is vital for promoting health through healthy lifestyles since it contributes to the economic balance of the municipality and the region.
13-AGRIA	<u>WP5/ Food business club</u> : If the pilot will lead to good results, it can be used to widen up the existing Finnish Hobby model in order to have the same business possibilities to other youngsters in other parts of Finland/Europe. To widen up the Hobby model requires lobbying work for the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture and the steering group of the Finnish Hobby model. <u>WP5 / School canteens into school restaurants</u> : Common target is to raise the number of students that eat the free school lunch every day. The key issue that the pilot's actions can expand to other schools is to show how important the canteen's environmental planning is and how the social aspects need to be considered in planning. The pilot's results will be published and delivered to the key actors in the school sector. <u>WP5/ Kids' food festival</u> : The food education is traditionally done in kinder gardens, schools and homes. A new platform, children's festivals, is introduced by the pilot. The other children festivals will be informed about the pilot and given the idea to be used freely for common good.
14-SLEANN	Not applicable
15-BRH	BRH will use results from WPs 4 and 5 (D.4.3, D.5.3) to assist administration and policy makers to better coordinate and focus their food policies, according to the principles of the MUFPP "to develop sustainable food systems that are inclusive, resilient, safe and diverse, that provide healthy and affordable food to all people in a human rights-based framework, that minimise waste and conserve biodiversity while adapting to and mitigating impacts of climate change" which was already signed by our Lord Mayor in 2020. Target users/groups: community catering facilities, schools, hospitals, old people's homes, daycare centres, residents, pupils. Approach to exploitation: Cooperation with P16 TTZ/P17 BIOZ, use Policy Labs as a multiplier and voice to disseminate the good results from the living labs and pave the way for a CRFS also at the political level.
16-TTZ	Ttz sees itself as a transfer service provider, bringing the latest findings from CRFS and food research to policy-makers in an appropriate way. Strategies for this are constantly being tested and evaluated and will be updated on next editions.
17-BIOZ	not applicable

D7.5 Exploitable results and exploitation plans, edition 3/3

Partner	<p>Policy and governance exploitation plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
18-QUAR	<p>"Municipal urban gardens regulation", WP4 and WP5/162, Food Value Chain Living Lab. Target users/groups: 16 invaders of lands as urban farmers and citizens, associations and schools. Pathways to exploitation: Quart de Poblet already has a 6,600 plot of land containing 60 urban allotments available to the public. It is a plot of land that can be used for traditional and sustainable agriculture for leisure and self-consumption. This initiative is crucial to promote sustainable agricultural practices and healthy, sustainable and local eating habits.</p>
19-SINNO	<p>MAA Tool developed by SINNO will also consider the action plans and KPIs frequently used in innovation projects. It will consider the four types of KPIs for policies, context, output, outcome and impact. It will be offered to municipalities like Quart de Poblet and other Living labs to check if it is useful for policy monitoring</p>
20-UPM	<p>Regarding policy and governance exploitation activities, specific initiatives with partners have not yet been considered, but UPM is open to joint initiatives beyond the project's end. The knowledge and experience gained in Cities2030 have already supported the university's involvement in other research projects and proposals related to resilient and sustainable food systems and cybersecurity in the agrifood sector. Regarding Arganda Lab, UPM aims to continue leveraging their participation with CODAN (member of advisory board) in new research activities and to enhance education in the areas related to Cities2030 through integration of the project's results into UPM's PhD and master programs.</p>
21-WIT	<p>Results from a regional community survey show strong support for a Green Party Private bill on the allocation of Green public spaces for community gardening and allotments by local authorities. Preliminary results were presented at the Environ Environmental Conference March 2024, and formed the basis for a group discussion with key stakeholders on community gardening in Ireland in May 2024. We intend to submit these results will be submitted for peer reviewed publications.</p>
22-MATIS	<p>Matís will use results from WPs 3 & 4 to assist policy makers within the Icelandic capital region, incl. Reykjavík, to better coordinate and focus their food policies, aiming to have the city of Reykjavík to sign the MUFPP.</p>
23-FFI	<p>Increased connections between local municipalities of the Cilento region will be implemented, starting from a more coherent approach on the protection of the mediterranean sea, biodiversity and the role of local fishermen, given the already happened gathering of 14 local municipalities for the creation of the first Marine experimental Area of the mediterranean. The Living Lab will also play a crucial role in better connecting the Cilento food system broadly, by activating the consortium of the lands of the mediterranean diet, which has just launched. Part of the policy plan there is also the intention to ease the relationship between local, regional, national, and European political representatives and policymakers. A second edition of the RegenerAction EU agri-food week is also planned for next year.</p>
24-VPR	<p><i>GPP (green public procurement)</i> To increase capacity of regional stakeholders to organise highly efficient food and catering services procurements, thus creating preconditions for securing healthy and sustainable food and strengthening short local food chains. The aim is to integrate more local production in public catering services. Municipalities and farmers/producers/ retailers will be addressed to understand in what ways their collaboration could be strengthened and will promote these solutions and their application to other territories, integration of aspects into the laws and policies.</p>
25-LLF	<p>LLF implements capacity building activities on food policy and CRFS aspects for stakeholders of the public sector with the aim of promoting the inclusion of food policy and CSRF initiatives in the strategies and development plans of municipalities and local action groups.</p>

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Prepared by P14, P28, all partners | Edited by P14 | Checked and reviewed by ExeCom | Approved by P1

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Partner	Policy and governance exploitation plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
26-GGP	White papers on ethics, gender and RRI (WP2), Systems thinking Encyclopedia (WP3), Food System Dialogues Facilitation (WP5) will be shared with relevant policy makers in local self-government in our network for potential use in the policy and living labs, when designing and developing food strategies and in the organisation of specific roundtable discussions.
27-AGFT	Not applicable
28-IASI	P28 will provide support and advice for the City of Iasi to sign the MUFPP Pact.
29-ARFI	ARFI will administer the Food for Iasi Living Lab platform, as an umbrella hub for the collaborations of all the stakeholders within our CRFS in the scope of building tools and intelligence for local and regional strategies and policies.
30-ICTM	Not applicable
31-COR R	Not applicable
32-VIZ	<p>Results achieved at an organisational level. Vicenza intends to further enhance the multilevel and multi stakeholders organisational model developed in the framework of Cities2030, and in particular in WP4 and WP5. It includes a 3-level structure: 1) food policy office (political level) 2) technical working-group (implementation level) 3) stakeholders working-group (cooperation level). The goal is to improve its visibility and involvement in the policy making process about food related issues and to bring CRFS issues into policy agenda</p> <p>Results achieved at a policy level. Vicenza intends to capitalise on the knowledge base of the local context/food system achieved in the framework of Cities2030, with specific reference to ,WP3, WP4 and WP5, and to further improve the policy making process on the four thematic priorities, which are as follows: 1) Nutrition, sustainability and health: the female perspective and contribution 2) Growing healthy: lifelong nutrition education 3) Sustainable food supply chain in urban areas 4) Food and sustainability between ethics, legality and transparency</p> <p>Results achieved at a governance level. Vicenza intends to improve the collaboration with the local authorities/municipalities of the Vicenza province as well as with other Italian cities, which are already developing their food system (e.g. Trento, Bergamo, Livorno and Matera which participated in the event organised on october 27, 2022). The goal is to promote a local "food community" - also in close coordination with WP5 living labs - which could expand outside the urban context so as to reach and actively involve the Municipalities of the peri-urban area and the Vicenza province</p>
32a-LaVi	With regard to the policy and governance exploitation plan, the International Library La Vigna is available for the activities promoted by the Municipality of Vicenza and offers its support for further useful initiatives.
33-IVM	Not applicable
34-MO MS	Murska Sobota successfully presented the CITIES2030 project to all municipalities (27) from the region where it is located and involved several stakeholders from the region to participate in the policy lab.
35-Uni.l u	<p>Sharing results of the Cities 2030 project with a nation-wide, participative Food Policy Council (FPC) for Luxembourg. Uniting all stakeholders within the food system will bring about innovation through constructive debates and teamwork and create a more socially and environmentally just, economically sound, high quality local food system.</p> <p>Engage in public policy advocacy to promote regulations that foster innovation and ethical considerations in technology development and implementation.</p>

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Partner	Policy and governance exploitation plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What project result are you planning to exploit? Have reference to the precise results by using the code (WP number/result number) and Living Lab name and result name. Define what are the target groups of the result. What is your strategy and practice to exploit the result? • Assess the result's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). • Add as many result exploitation plans as you see pertinent.
36-UCC	Not applicable
37-PRIM	Not applicable
38-IUAV	<p><u>A situated learning program</u>: the educational activities of iuav will involve architecture and planning students and local stakeholders in the collective design of future food scenarios in close collaboration with local municipalities and public bodies engaged in food related policy making.</p> <p><u>Food Atlas of the Venice Lagoon</u>: continually implemented and discussed with stakeholders, it will represent a key tool for municipalities and policy makers who will be able to use it as an archive of good practices and projects, but also as a tool to identify criticalities and potentialities, as well as urgent aspects on which to intervene through new food policies.</p>
39-RTU	Not applicable
40-CITAG	<p>One of CITAG's core activities is counselling and advocacy on a local level. The results of WP4 and WP5 will nourish its expertise and contribute to CITAG's policy making agenda.</p> <p>WP4, guide Capri : the guide from the Capri urban farm will be used as a tool to mobilise local policy makers on the obstacles that most urban farming initiatives meet. WP4, farm land in Marseille : the farm land mapping in Marseille is already directly used by CITAG as a policy tool with local authorities. WP5, chilli pepper production : our opportunity study on a mutualized transformation tool will be translated into policies recommendations for resilient CRFS. WP5 : local CRFS observatory : the main purpose of the observatory on our local level is to give policy makers a more exhaustive and unbiased look on the CRFS state, dynamics and needs.</p>
41-HARL	<p>WP 4 , WP 5 , WP 7: By 2030, Haarlem wants to have reached 50 % off the habitants with information about more plant based, local and organic food. Haarlem works closely with (residents) initiatives and entrepreneurs to realise a sustainable food system. We focus on reducing food waste, promoting a sustainable and healthy food choice and preventing/reducing food waste and stimulating biodiversity through urban farming initiatives. Haarlem is committed to a stronger lobby towards the government to stimulate the protein transition. In the coming years we will intensify cooperation with initiatives in Haarlem. A circular economy action program will follow at the end of 2022. This is a practical translation of the goals from the Sustainability Roadmap. The Action Program encompasses the actions necessary up to and including 2025 to achieve these goals. We will have a special focus on inclusion, to make sure sustainable food is accessible for everybody.</p>

5. Business- and exploitation plans for innovations (KPI 10+)

5.1 Objectives of Task 5.3 – Evolve Exploitation Plans and Business Plans

Task 5. leads the last mile to exploitable outputs, monitors and uptakes the most exploitable outcomes e.g. contents, observations, improvements, good practices and innovations from each pilot. The task 5.3 with the support of WP3, collects data from the pilots' experiments and markets, and seeks synergies between pilots and ongoing H2020 projects. The task carries out the Exploitation Workshop (EW) series with the pilots to develop market- ready products and services. Knowledge obtained through EW series will help to form the Exploitation Plans for different types of beneficiaries (e.g. public bodies, business, consultancy,

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training) and to develop the Business Plans for innovations. The third outcome of the EW series also serves the need to build capacity on business planning and modelling.

Lead partner role: AgFutura Technologies (P27) coordinates the activities. Role of participants: all partners develop the task simultaneously in their city/country.

5.2 Carrying out the EWs

Exploitation workshops (EW) have two-fold objective: to introduce the exploitation to the Exploitation managers representing each project partner and to build capacity on business modelling for the representatives of the CRFS Labs.

Table 19: Overview of workshops

Time period	Workshop title
23 May, 2023 10:00 - 14:00 CET	EW1 & 2: Exploitation and key exploitable results within the CRFS
6 December, 2023 10:00 - 14:00 CET	EW3 & 4: Business modelling in the context of the CRFS
11 April, 2024 10:00 - 14:00 CET	EW5: Business Model Canvases of CRFS Labs *The Canvases completed by partners are included in the Annex of this deliverable

Table 20: Content of EWS 1&2

Welcome and Introduction	AGFT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop objectives - What is exploitation? Functions, purpose and objectives - How the data will be collected - Better knowing of the system for collecting data 	
Key Project Exploitable Results	AGFT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are exploitable results/outcomes? (observations, improvements, good practices and innovations) - Characterization of the ERs and prioritization - How to identify the KEY ERs? - Innovative content 	
Exploitation Plan	AGFT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General strategy - Economic factors - Scientific and technical goals 	

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- Intellectual property	
Technology Readiness levels - TRLs	AGFT
- What is Technology Readiness levels? - How to determine TR level?	
IPR Management	AGFT
- Brief overview of forms of IPR protection - Risk assessment	
Discussion	AGFT and Exploitation managers

Table 21: Content of EWS 3&4

Business modelling with focus on sustainability	AGFT
- How to develop market- ready products and services? - How to use business model canvas - Sustainable business model - Triple-layered business model canvas	
Business Model Canvas Building Blocks	AGFT
- Value Proposition - Market - Infrastructure - Finance	
Triple-layered business model canvas	AGFT
- Economic layer - Environmental layer - Social layer	
Types of Business Models for Sustainable Food Systems	AGFT
- Circular BM - Alternative, place-based and social food networks - Disruptive BM - Alternative logistics or online food distribution BM - Regional food consortia, food labs, or food hubs - Sufficiency BM - An inclusive BM - Family BM	

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- The focal company BM	
Explaining the assignment for all CRFS Labs for Exploitation Workshop 5; Discussion	AGFT and partners representing CITIES2030 Labs

Table 22: Content of EWS 5

Presentation of the sustainable BMs of the CRFS Labs	AGFT and partners representing CITIES2030 Labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AGROTOPIA LIVING LAB - ARGANDA - FOOD FOR IASI LIVING LAB - LAGOON OF VENICE - MARSEILLE - VIDZEME - MURSKA SOBOTA - PAIDEIA CAMPUS - POLLICA 2050 - REYKJAVÍK CRFS LAB - SEINÄJOKI - BRUGES - SETESDHAL.SHOP - VEJLE - VICENZA - WINE@SICÓ - HAARLEM - VELIKA GORICA - BREMERHAVEN 	
Discussion and Conclusions	AGFT and partners representing CITIES2030 Labs

5.3 Exploitation plan

The EP describes the activities that are undertaken (how and by whom) to ensure the exploitation beyond the project itself. The exploitation strategy is reflecting and is based on a sound analysis of the market trends, potential users, and financial sustainability. The target users will be precisely identified and analysed in terms of specific needs and objectives.

A good exploitation plan ensures the use and the dissemination of the knowledge achieved during the project. The exploitation plan should: organise all the exploitation process; drive the consortium to reach all the goals stated at the beginning of the project; allow to underline the added value of the project and

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boosts further scientific developments; maximise the impact of the funding granted in the market; ensure sustainable growth, more and better jobs, as well as industry competitiveness.

A complete Exploitation Plan covers four fields of interest:

1. General strategy
 - Focuses on the main results from the project (products, services,) and their commercial viability.
 - Considers new business and operating models that become possible with the project for bringing the project results to customers. Explores the role of 3rd parties (not participating in the project) in this scenario.
 - Identifies drivers for a successful exploitation and considers how those drivers can be harnessed and strengthened.
 - If there are obstacles to a successful exploitation of the project from today's perspective, addresses them early on.
 - Puts a strong focus on how European stakeholders can profit from the exploitation of the results.
 - Develops a timeline for exploitation, showing how the exploitation can be structured in phases. Identifies the prospective time frame after the end of the project to bring the results to the market.
 - Identifies concrete customer needs that are addressed with the solution and product and describes ways to quantitatively measure the success.
 - Involves marketing, product-management, and sales departments early in the process.
 - If possible, starts exploitation of intermediate results already during the project.
 - Considers synergies for exploitation with other projects, possibly also funded ones.
2. Economic factors
 - Aims at a quick access to the market. If necessary, creates new markets for successful exploitation.
 - Addresses the market for exploitation today (market analysis, prognoses, technical developments).
 - Assess the competition for the developed results, in Europe and worldwide.
 - Provides innovation in project results, ensures there are advantages compared to competitors.
3. Scientific and technical goals
 - Assess the impact of general technological progress on the exploitation scenarios.
 - Pays attention to non-technical developments (legal aspects, privacy aspects) and their influence on exploitation.
4. Intellectual property
 - Considers protecting intellectual property, for example, through patents.

Exploitable results

List of Criteria for selection of the most exploitable outcomes (contents, observations, improvements, good practices and innovations) from each pilot:

- Knowledge (data, information) has the most direct impact to the project
- Have potential for market uptake
- Specific ones
- Have potential to be used by different stakeholders as source of new and improved knowledge, solution
- They are well adaptable, understandable and applicable in different contexts
- They are presented in a format that can be easily disseminated by different channels

- They can be divided in four groups (knowledge, methods and tools, activities, innovative prototypes and new partnerships)
- IP protection requirements
- Have potential in development and marketing of product or service or process

Technology Readiness Level

The TRL scale is a metric for describing the maturity of a technology. The acronym stands for Technology Readiness Level. The scale consists of 9 levels. Each level characterises the progress in the development of a technology, from the idea (level 1) to the full deployment of the product in the marketplace (level 9). The scale is described in detailed described below.

Table 23 The TRL scale

Levels	Definition	TRL Description
1	Basic research: basic principles are observed and reported	Lowest level of technology readiness. Scientific research begins to be translated into applied research and development. Examples might include fundamental investigations and paper studies
2	Applied research: technology concept and/or application formulated	Invention begins. Once basic principles are observed, practical applications can be formulated. Examples are limited to analytic studies and experimentation.
3	Critical function, proof of concept established	Active research and development is initiated. This includes analytical studies and laboratory studies to physically validate analytical predictions of separate elements of the technology. Examples include components that are not yet integrated or representative.
4	Laboratory testing of prototype component or process	Basic technological components are integrated to establish that they will work together. This is relatively "low fidelity" prototype compared to the eventual system.
5	Laboratory testing of integrated system	The basic technological components are integrated with reasonably realistic supporting elements so it can be tested in a simulated environment. This is "high fidelity" prototype compared to the eventual system
6	Prototype system verified	The prototype, which is well beyond that of TRL 5, is tested in a relevant environment. The system or process demonstration is carried out in an operational environment. Represents a major step up in a technology's demonstrated readiness.
7	Integrated pilot system demonstrated	Prototype near, or at, planned operational system level. The final design is virtually complete. The goal of this stage is to remove engineering and manufacturing risk.

8	System completed in commercial design	Technology has been proven to work in its final form and under expected conditions. In almost all cases, this TRL represents the end of true system development.
9	Market introduction	The product, process or service is launched commercially, marketed to and adopted by a group of customers (including public authorities)

Risk assessment

A risk is any area of uncertainty that represents a possible threat to the project. To manage and mitigate risks, there is a need to identify them first, then assess the likelihood of their occurrence and finally estimate the impact they might have on the project. Actions should be taken to avoid or reduce the likelihood of events that might endanger the exploitation of the project results. The identification and consideration of risks and their prevention is an integral part of project management. The project consortium must be aware that a certain degree of risk-taking is inevitable for the project to achieve its objectives. Decisions in the project will be taken based on evidence and reasonable assumptions, but outcomes are never fully predictable. Some variables related to possible risks may be hidden at certain stages of the project, and possibly revealed in other. It will be the role of the project management to manage the exposure of the project results to risks by driving actions to improve control of uncertainty and take steps to reduce the chance of failing to achieve the stated objectives.

Risk identification – risks should be directly related to the project objectives and agreed by the whole project consortium. Risk management means identifying and managing uncertainties to delivery of objectives, not managing issues that might be constant.

- Technological risk - The technological risk is considered as a combination of technology and technical risks. Technology risk is concerning an underpinning technology necessary for a project.
- Technical risk is related to system/technology implementing and integration
- Partnership risks are the risks deriving from the other partners involved in the project.
- Market risk – It is defined as the risk of economic losses resulting from price changes in the capital markets. This includes equity risk, general and specific interest-rate risk, property risk and currency risk. Other sources of market risk include recessions, political turmoil, changes in interest rates and terrorist attacks.
- Systematic (market risk) – cannot be eliminated, unsystematic (specific risk) – can be reduced to some extent through diversification.
- IPR/Legal risk – various legal issues related to the violation of laws and/or standards and/or regulations. Or, related to the IPR (the legal costs of protecting, enforcing of IPR, defending of IP from infringement etc.).
- Management and Financial risk – management risk can be defined as the risks associated with ineffective, destructive or underperforming project management.
- Financial risk is concerned with various financial inconsistencies, insufficiency or ineffective financial management within a project.
- Environmental, Regulation, Safety and Other Risks- regulations of health, safety or environment can pose various risks for the project results exploitations

Risk evaluation – Risk evaluation is the evaluation of the impact of each risk should it occur. It aims to answer questions such as: What impact might certain risks have on benefits, time, cost, quality, reputation,

people, etc. How likely is it that these risks will occur? The probability and impact can both be scored, e.g. using a High/Medium/Low scale.

Table 24 Risk Evaluation

Consequences (impact)	Assignment	Note
1	Insignificant	Minor problems easily handled by normal day to day processes
2	Minor	Some disruption or modification of correct execution possible
3	Moderate	Moderate modification on the correct execution and results
4	Major	Results severely affected
5	Catastrophic	Results are under crucial risk not to execute or of heavy delay

Likelihood	Description
1	Rare
2	Unlikely
3	Moderate
4	Likely
5	Almost certain

Likelihood	Impact				
	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic
Rare	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Unlikely	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High
Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Very high
Likely	Low	Moderate	High	Very high	Unacceptable
Certain	Moderate	High	Very high	Unacceptable	Unacceptable

Risk prioritisation – It is crucial to estimate what is the priority of each risk. Identifying the urgency and importance of a risk is not the same thing – It is important to deal with the urgent risks quickly, and with the important risks comprehensively.

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Risk management planning - a strategy for mitigating the risks identified and preventing the project from being derailed. What actions and resources will be needed to reduce the impact and/or probability of the risk happening? The planning should consider:

- How to prevent it from happening - either by putting some counter-measures in place or putting the project in a position where it would have no impact
- How to reduce the risk - what action is needed to reduce the probability of the risk happening and/or to reduce the impact in case it is realised.
- Can you transfer the risk to a third party (e.g. take out insurance) or share it in some way (shared risk-shared gain)?
- What to do if the risk does occur - do you need a contingency plan?
- What are the implications of accepting the risk - ensuring that all the stakeholders are aware of the possible consequences?

Risk monitoring - the project's overall exposure to risk must be reviewed throughout the life of a project and where necessary actions to mitigate risks must be taken. Revisions to the project business case or assumptions must be considered, if circumstances alter.

5.4 Business Model Canvas

A business model canvas is a visual representation of a business model, highlighting all key strategic factors. In other words, it is a general, holistic and complete overview of the company's workings, customers, revenue streams and more. Other than providing a general overview of the business model, these canvases enable companies to visualise and analyse their strategy. This includes updating the model as the company evolves, such as changes in the market, new streams or expansions.

The business model canvas provides the central, common source of knowledge through which each department can add their unique input from their respective domains. It is a template that defines the business - specifically, how each section interacts with the others. For example, understanding the value proposition, the target customer and the channels through which they are engaged all need to be analysed together, not just in individual vacuums.

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Alternatively, the business model canvas can be used by organisations to plan, assess or execute new models altogether. In this way, the canvas highlights the key essentials and ensures that no vital factors are forgotten. If the canvas is incomplete, then the respective strategy is also incomplete.

A business model that follows the Business Model Canvas approach must provide information on the following elements:

Customer Segments - To build an effective business model, an organisation must identify which customers it tries to serve. Various sets of customers can be segmented based on the different needs and attributes to ensure appropriate implementation of corporate strategy meets the characteristics of a selected group of clients. Whether it is B2B or B2C, all businesses have customers. These are the people or organisations that buy the products, use the services or are otherwise essential for creating a profit.

Customers can be defined through various means, but it is important to focus on the core customers first, and then assess less critical or potential future clients. The canvas should assess, among other factors:

- Current and future needs: what are customers looking for, and what might they be looking for in the immediate future?
 - General demographic: age range, location, interests, etc.
 - Likes, dislikes and pain points: what do customers enjoy and what puts them off? Knowing this will help understand how best to approach them.
 - Relations with other segments: this is important if the business relies on multiple groups interacting. Airbnb, for example, has both property owners and guests - the business strategy only works if both are satisfied.
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- Additional segments can be listed that may utilise the product or service in the future. This will highlight future directions the strategy can go in, once success has been gained with the core, primary audience(s).

Value Propositions - The products and/or services the organisation offers in order to meet the needs of its customers. A company's value proposition is what distinguishes itself from its competitors. A company's value proposition is the sum of its various products and services, specifically in regards to how it uniquely stands out amongst the competition. In layman's terms: What is the unique factor that makes this business better than another?

The creator of the business model canvas, Alexander Osterwalder, has also stated that organisations need to offer something unique and this needs to be immediately discernible from the competition. The value proposition can be as simple as being cheaper, faster, more efficient or more readily available than the competition. However, we can roughly place all values in two broad categories:

- Quantitative. This refers to benefits that can be easily counted; from a customer's point of view, this means they can be easily compared to the competition. Examples of this can include pricing or speed. Users may very well choose a service because it's cheaper or quicker.
- Qualitative. This refers to abstract concepts such as value or experience - those that can't be readily measured by hard numbers, but nonetheless, give a strong emotional response to the audience. Examples of this can include various characteristics, such as using local products, being eco-friendly or having a personal, customer-centric approach that competitors lack.

Another way of expressing the core value is by asking what the value proposition owner wants customers to remember. When it comes to recommending a business to others, what's the essential benefit that people

should mention? This value also needs to be maintained. For instance, if the value lies in being the only service in a respective region, what will happen when a larger competitor eventually decides to move in? The business model canvas should highlight these weaknesses, in order to better plan ahead.

Channels - An organisation can deliver its value proposition to its customers through different channels. Effective channels will distribute the value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient and cost effective.

How will the organisation and their customers interact? Once customers and value proposition are defined, this will impact what channels are used. For example, if the audience is busy and on the go, a mobile-facing service will be essential. Likewise, if specific locations are targeted, perhaps a physical presence is also needed. What's important here is that the many touchpoints are considered that the customers may want and the beneficial ones are highlighted. However, it should be noted that channels can adapt over time and this is one area where the business model canvas is likely to be updated.

Customer Relationships - To ensure the survival and success of any business, an organisation must identify the type of relationship they want to create with their customer segments. For example, the way a customer interacts with the organisation through the sales and product lifecycle.

This includes how customers first came to use the respective business, how these initial customers are retained and, ultimately, how the business will grow its audience. There are a number of factors to consider here, especially in regards to the type of relationship:

- **Personal Assistance.** In these forms, customer service is essential. Clients want a personal approach from the company and, in turn, the company offers a direct approach tailored to their specific needs. This often involves having employees attached to specific customers (such as a sales or business development position) both before and after the sale process itself. This is something a bank might have for its business clients, for example. How dedicated this exact relationship depends on the nature of the service, as well as the customers.
- **Automation and Self-Service.** This can often be found in e-commerce stores. For example; customers just want to browse and shop at will, without speaking to anyone. Automation can enhance this through personalization, without the customer being aware, such as Netflix's recommended viewing.
- **Communities.** Alternatively, if the target audience is a particular niche, segment or region, the business might consider establishing a community. With this approach, the business model brings people with shared interests together, to facilitate more actions.

Revenue Streams - The way the organisation makes income from each customer segment. For example, subscription fees or licensing, etc.

Ultimately, a company has to turn a profit. On the business model canvas, this is represented by revenue streams: the various channels with which income can be generated. Here are the most common revenue streams to consider:

- **Asset or goods sales:** this is one of the oldest streams. By selling goods, the business generates revenue at each transaction.
- **Subscription:** If an ongoing service is provided or products are rented out, then these fall under subscription models; the customers pay on a regular schedule (such as per month or year) as long as they are using the service/product of the business.

- Leasing or lending: This is similar to the subscription but differs in that it's for a predefined period. Car rentals, for instance, often do this, as customers define the rental period before purchasing.
- Licensing: This is where the business sells licences to other companies or individuals to use the property. It's similar to sale but differs in that the business still owns the intellectual property; the user can't resell it.
- White labelling: Similar to licensing, white labelling is where the business provides a product or service that businesses can relabel as their own. This is typically done as a subscription or one-off licence purchase, so it can be considered an additional variant of the above.
- Advertising: Perhaps the business model is designed to attract users, but currently drives revenue from advertising opportunities? Social media networks are the most famous example of this; they do not make money through purchases or subscriptions, but through charging advertisers to benefit from this network.

It is important to note that these revenue streams are not set in stone - they will adapt and evolve as the market changes. Businesses should regularly return to the canvas to make sure each stream is as effective as it can be. This includes different pricing plans and options (especially if there are multiple streams) or adding new streams.

Key Activities - The most important activities in executing the organisation's value proposition. For example, for a product-driven business, this includes ongoing learning about new techniques to build better products. The main question is: What is needed to produce the value proposition and ensure it succeeds? This section includes the key activities needed to make the business model effective and successfully connect with customers.

This can include initial investment, such as finding a development company, or even marketing and advertising to generate that initial awareness. This section should take everything into account, including the impact each has on the overall business, to understand the absolute essentials and recommended extras.

Key Resources - The resources that are necessary to create value for the customer. They are considered assets to a company, which are needed to sustain and support the business. These resources could be human, financial, physical and intellectual.

Every organisation runs on resources: the essential assets in running the business and providing the value (defined earlier) to customers. Like the other elements, this can come in many forms.

Human resources: if a business is providing personalised value or has a model that requires a lot of staff, the cost and training of employees need to be considered.

Financial: how much investment is required to run and maintain a business before it makes a profit? The more money is needed upfront, the bigger the burden to generate ROI.

Physical: expanding the presence of a business, opening offices or buying physical space is also an asset that needs to be considered. This is mostly true for organisations that need prominent positions, such as high street retailers or hotels. For a lot of businesses, the push into a digital landscape is quickly reducing the strain of this particular resource.

Intellectual property: this can include everything needed to develop the IP (such as an app), as well as develop and maintain it. For example, subscriptions and licences survive by ensuring customers cannot use the service without a company, as this company still holds the intellectual property rights.

Key Partnerships - In order to optimise operations and reduce risks of a business model, organisations usually cultivate buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. Complementary business alliances also can be considered through joint ventures, strategic alliances between competitors or non-competitors.

Very few companies survive on their own. Identifying and preparing key partnerships is essential for long term survivability. Here are the primary partnerships that typically need to be considered:

Distributors: How will the business sell to customers? Whether it is using online stores, sales agents or other companies, some form of distribution is needed.

“Coopetition”: sometimes two businesses, that would otherwise be competitors, can join forces to take on larger markets. This works where there is enough potential gain that a joint venture makes more fiscal sense: there isn't a clear risk of one side gaining at the expense of the others. For example, smaller organisations can often team up to provide a larger, holistic offer to users, or to even attend events that are outside of either side's budget.

Suppliers: Similar to distribution, a business needs suppliers for everything from raw materials to software development. If there's something the business needs that cannot be produced in-house, then trusted suppliers need to be identified.

Existing customers: If the business has clients, it can offer some recommendation rewards, or a commission-based system, to spread awareness.

Cost Structure - This describes the most important monetary consequences while operating under different business models. For example, how do the Key Activities drive the costs.

Fixed costs are the easiest to determine as they have a singular price or a repetitive price that doesn't change. Rent is a good example.

Variable costs, on the other hand, can vary and their high peaks need to be accounted for. Factors such as temperature can often impact businesses that need to maintain a certain heat or humidity - they may spend more (or less) in the warmer months.

Economies of scale and scope, similarly, refer to decreasing costs as the business expands. This is because larger production can introduce better efficiencies (scale) while creating new partnerships and improving internal processes, as a result, can improve the wider organisation (scope). For example, a business might rely on third-party providers for immediate support, such as packaging, but move this in-house when it becomes cost-efficient to do so.

It's important to understand these variables so that the business model canvas provides a realistic view of costs right now, as well as where the company aims to be short.

Benefits of a Business Model Canvas

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Visuals at a glance - Thanks to having everything in one place, various stakeholders can gain an immediate understanding of the business model as a whole. It's easily interpretable and offers a single source of truth for the wider strategy.

Quick Improvements & Iterations - By having everything connected, organisations can see how every part of the business works with the wider structure. This is where value proposition owners can highlight flaws or identify solutions. By comparing all the factors, such as customers, revenue streams and costs, the company can begin to make strategic improvements it might not have otherwise identified before.

Shareable - Nobody wants to go through a 2-hour presentation on business strategy. The business model canvas can be easily shown to new people to help bring them up to speed, while simple changes don't require extensive explanations; people can see how they fit onto the updated canvas.

6. Conclusions

6.1 Results

The Cities2030 project aims to develop and implement innovative, sustainable, and inclusive food systems in cities across Europe. Here are the main results of the Cities2030 project associated with practical examples:

Co-creation of City Region Food Systems: Cities2030 brings together various stakeholders, including city authorities, businesses, academia, and citizens, to co-create and implement sustainable urban food systems. This collaborative approach ensures that the solutions are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of each city region.

- *The project has established and piloted 18 CRFS Living Labs, and brought together a network of food system actors called the CRFS Alliance.*
- *These achievements form the platform for an inclusive, multi-actor approach and transformation of urban food systems.*

Piloting of novel solutions in multiple cities to contribute to the food system transformation towards FOOD2030 policy: Policy and Living Labs carry out considerations, pilots and experiments which promotes such as: urban agriculture to increase local food production and reduce transportation emissions; food waste reduction and valorization e.g., composting, bokashi and upcycling; short food supply chains and local food distribution networks to support small-scale farmers and reduce food miles; digital platforms for food distribution and community-led initiatives.

- *The 18 Living Labs have reported 146 innovation actions (e.g., capacity building, experiments, external funding, other measures and system thinking pilots) which have generated 110 results (e.g., improvements, best practices, innovations, other results). The analysis and data of experiments and results are in ANNEX A, part 1 and 2.*
- *Living Labs have identified and described 22 business models which are presented in chapter 5 and ANNEX B.*
- *Three partners of Cities2030 informed of the innovations which are to be uploaded into the [EU Innovation Radar Platform](#).*

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Capacity building and training: The project offers training and capacity building programs for city authorities, businesses, and citizens to enhance their knowledge and skills in sustainable City Region Food Systems.

- *The Living Labs have reported 40 capacity building measures during the project time frame. The participants of these capacity building actions are typically local multi-actor stakeholder members.*

Use digital and ICT solutions: Cities2030 promotes the use of data, smart solutions and digital tools. The solutions are aimed at project management, open data sharing platforms, showcasing best practices and innovations in urban food systems, storyboards of policy and living lab, and solutions for tracking and tracing products in the food value chain.

- *The project has launched Cities2030 Single Click CRFS Platform which encompasses Community platform, CRFS Good Practices, SSRI Multi-Actor Approach, S2CP Dashboard, Blockchain for SFSC, Data Integration and Management, Sentiment analysis for Twitter, Geospatial CRFS web services, Cities2030 repository, Blockchain food supply chain digital twin, Blockchain tools for private communications, Realtime information representation, and CRFS Observatory.*
- *Correlate platform to support project management.*
- *Living Labs have delivered comprehensive websites such as <https://gustdeiasi.ro/>, www.linn.rdrp.org and downstream applications e.g. mobile application for biocomposting at Lahti Living Lab*

Policy briefs, recommendations and white papers: Cities2030 provides policy briefs, recommendations and white papers to support the transition towards sustainable and ethical urban food systems at the local, national, and European levels.

- *Cities2030 has issued following types of briefs and white papers: Policy Briefs #1 and #2, White Paper On Sustainable CRFS, White Paper on Ethical Cities & Regions Food Systems, Responsible Research And Innovation (RRI) and White Paper of Gender in CRFS.*

Replication and upscaling: The project aims to replicate and upscale successful solutions in other cities and regions, fostering a broader transition towards sustainable urban food systems.

- *The project has reached out and invited new cities and regions to follow up Cities2030 progress.*

Impact evaluation: Cities2030 establishes a monitoring and evaluation framework to assess the impact of the implemented solutions and ensure continuous improvement.

- *The project has conducted, in cooperation with all beneficiaries, an overarching analysis of project influences and impacts on dimensions such as politics, environment, societal, business, economics.*
- *Cities2030 contributes to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production).*

6.2 Exploitation plans and business models

WP5 Task T5.2 and Task 5.4 have set up an exploitation and business model planning programme for the partners. The programme consists of seven steps. The steps took place over 21 months, from month M25 to M46. The steps consist of a joint workshop and independent work sessions in which all consortium partners are invited to plan how they will exploit the project results and outcomes beyond the project timeframe. In total, partners attended and held 190 workshops and independent working sessions. The seven program steps are described below.

1. Partners' exploitation planning was initiated at month M25 associated with the deliverable D5.5.
2. The first edition of this deliverable D7.5 was delivered at M28.

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3. T5.3 Exploitation Workshops 1 & 2 were arranged for partners capacity building at M32.
4. The second edition of this deliverable D7.5 was delivered at M38.
5. T5.3 Exploitation Workshops 3 & 4 were arranged for partners capacity building at M39.
6. T5.3 Exploitation Workshop 5 was arranged for partners capacity building at M43
7. The third edition of this deliverable D7.5 was gathered plans up to M46.

The project partners have defined their policies, strategies and action plans for the exploitation of the project results.

- The exploitation plans address 5 pathways: academic, industrial and business, financial and market, societal, and policy and governance. The partners' exploitation plans are defined in Chapter 4. Summaries of the partners' exploitation plans are given below.
- The business modelling strategy is described in Chapter 5. The business model canvases provided by the partners are included in ANNEX B.

Academic exploitation plans: Key exploitation strategies include publishing articles in open-access journals, presenting at conferences, and creating educational materials for students at various levels. The project will also develop practical tools, such as a handbook on extended innovation patterns and a platform for tracking food products. Partnerships with universities will allow for integrating project findings into curricula and involving students in research activities. Ultimately, Cities2030 aims to bridge the gap between research and practice, fostering a more sustainable and equitable food system.

Industrial and business exploitation plans: Several initiatives focus on knowledge transfer and capacity building, including educational programmes for local producers and the creation of "gastro days" to promote food policy. Living Labs play a crucial role in these projects, serving as testing grounds for innovations such as sustainable meal deliveries and IoT-equipped food waste composters. Furthermore, the plans highlight the importance of collaboration and stakeholder engagement by involving local businesses, schools, and policymakers in the development and implementation of these initiatives. Finally, the plans emphasise long-term sustainability through the establishment of partnerships, the pursuit of funding opportunities, and the dissemination of best practices.

Financial and market exploitation plans: The initiatives range from establishing farmers' markets and promoting healthy snacks to supporting youth-led food businesses. Funding sources include government investment, private partnerships, and grants. Key goals include improving access to local products, fostering entrepreneurship, and expanding market opportunities for local producers. The plans also highlight the role of technology, such as traceability apps, and the importance of sustainability. Overall, the focus is on creating more resilient and prosperous local food economies.

Societal exploitation plans: Numerous plans are outlined, including educational programmes, community outreach, and support for local food producers. The plans highlight collaboration between various stakeholders, such as government agencies, businesses, and citizens, to achieve these goals. Examples of specific actions include developing digital tools to improve food system transparency and hosting food festivals to engage the public. The ultimate aim is to raise awareness, encourage responsible consumption, and foster sustainable practices within the food system.

Policy and governance exploitation plans: These plans highlight how partners plan to leverage the findings, specifically from WP4 and WP5, to influence policy changes promoting sustainable and resilient food systems. Key themes include promoting healthy eating habits, reducing food waste, supporting local food systems, and engaging with policymakers at local, regional, and national levels. The plans outline strategies

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for disseminating information, fostering collaboration between governmental bodies and other organisations, and integrating research outcomes into existing frameworks like the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP). Ultimately, these plans aim to translate research into concrete actions that transform food systems for greater sustainability and resilience.

Business- and exploitation plans for innovations: Chapter 5 emphasises the importance of a comprehensive exploitation plan, highlighting four key areas: overall strategy, economic factors, scientific and technical objectives and intellectual property. It also defines different Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and emphasises the need to assess and mitigate potential risks.

Chapter 5 also explains the Business Model Canvas which is the business modelling tool used by the Living Lab partners. Partners provide a total of 22 business models in the form of the Business Model Canvas. They are shared in ANNEX B of this deliverable.

WP5 - Living Labs innovation actions and results

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Introduction

This document, an annex to deliverable D7.5 of the Cities2030 project, analyses the innovation actions and results of the project's Living Labs, particularly those in work package 5 and task 5.2.

The analysis focuses on the types of innovation actions undertaken (e.g., capacity building, experiments) and their targeted beneficiaries, primarily city regions. The document then examines the 110 Living Lab results, categorising them based on type, Key Exploitable Result (KER) clusters, anticipated Intellectual Property Rights, and Technology Readiness Level.

It assesses the success, innovativeness, exploitability, and impact of these results, highlighting those with high KER indices. Finally, the document reflects on the limitations of Living Labs within the Cities2030

context, emphasising their role as open innovation environments for testing ideas and fostering systemic change in urban food systems.

It also provides a deviation analysis comparing planned and achieved targets, attributing differences to factors like fewer participating Living Labs and the unpredictable nature of innovation.

1. WP5 - Living Labs' innovation actions

The below table contains the number of innovation actions by target group (city region, internal, other) and type (capacity building, experiment, other measures).

Type of the action	City region	Internal	Other	Yhteensä
capacity building	32	3	5	40
experiment	76	6	4	86
external funding	1			1
other measures	7	2	1	10
system thinking pilot	9			9
Yhteensä	125	11	10	146

Number of innovation actions by target group and type

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Living Labs' innovation actions (capacity building, experiment, other measures)

Cities2030 - WP5: Living Labs' innovation actions

Living Labs' innovation actions status at the end of the project.

WP5 - Living Labs - Status of the Innovation action

1.1 City Region Food Systems SusTransition¹ Matrix

The figures below outline the SusTransition Matrix. The SusTransition Matrix illustrates and reflects the systemic and holistic approach of WP5 to promote the transformation of urban food systems.

The rows of the matrix are the ten (10) food system themes and the columns are the five (5) specific objectives of the project. The efforts of the Cities2030 Living Labs cover all 10 themes and 5 objectives.

As the aim is to apply system thinking and foster systemic transition in CRFS in line with FOOD 2030 policy, the strategy is that Living Labs' innovation actions will have impact on all steps of the food value chain (groups 1-6) as well as transversal themes (groups 7-10). Similarly, the strategy is that the Living Labs' innovation actions are addressed to all 5 key specific objectives which reflect FOOD 2030 pillars.

As expected, regarding 10 thematic groups, the consumption and markets are at the top, but production also ranks high. In terms of 5 key specific objectives, the top three are: Ensuring healthy and sustainable food; Strengthening circularity and local food belts; Developing food culture and skills.

¹ Sustainable Transition

D7.5, Annex A, part 1, ed. 3/3
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LLs' interventions in the 5 specific objectives

Secure healthy and sustainable food

Stop food poverty and insecurity

Protect and preserve natural resources

Enhance circularity and local food belts

Develop food culture and skills

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LLs' interventions in 10 food system themes

2. WP5 - Living Labs results

The total number of Living Lab results is 110. They are divided into improvements, good/promising practices, innovation and other exploitable results.

Result type 1	COUNTA / Result type 1
Improvement	24
Good/promising practice	50
Innovation	28
Other exploitable result	8
Yhteensä	110

In addition, 22 business models descriptions have been delivered through the work of Task 5.3

Living Labs' results

3. WP5 - Living Labs results deep-dives

In this chapter the results of Living Labs are analysed upon the data given by Living Lab operators.

In chapter 3.1 we give an overview of project innovation action outcome. The attributes of the results are analysed in order to characterise the overall achievement of the project.

In chapter 3.2 we summarise the self-assessment outcome on success rate, innovativeness, exploitability and impact of the results. In addition, we demonstrate the deviation of the results.

3.1 Characterization of the results of Living Labs

3.1.1 Living Lab results by main type

Most of the results (58%) fall into the social innovation group. The second largest group is technological innovation (12.7%).

Living Labs results by type

3.1.2 Living Labs results grouped by Key Exploitable Result clusters

More than 50% of the results are classified as other intangible results, such as good practices and social innovations. The second largest group is services (19%).

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Living Lab results by Key Exploitable Result (KER) category

3.1.3 Anticipated Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of results

The Living Labs have assessed the need to protect Intellectual property Rights (IPR). Based on the data given by LL operators there are results which for sure or probably require protection, but also results that are open.

Cities2030 - Living Lab results & Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

3.1.4 Result type 1 vs result type 2

Social innovations are mostly good/promising practices.

Result type 1	Result type 2							Total
	Business model	Other	Political innovation	Scientific innovation	Social innovation	Technology innovation		
Improvement	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Good/promising practice	4	2	0	0	13	5	24	
Innovation	2	5	0	5	34	4	50	
Other exploitable result	3	1	2	5	12	5	28	
		2	1		5		8	
Yhteensä	0	9	10	3	10	64	14	110

3.1.5 Results by Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

When the results are evaluated according to the Technology Readiness Level, the results are classified as follows: TRL 1 - TR3 is about 20%, TRL 4 - TR6 is about 13% and TRL 7 - TRL9 is about 55%. The proportion of uncoded results was 12%.

Results by Technology Readiness Level

3.2 The assessment of the results of Living Labs

3.2.1 Result Success Rate (RSR)

The Living Lab operators assess the overall success rate for each experiment result. The assessment is rough and the results are grouped into 3 groups: 1=low success, 3=medium success and 9=high success.

Based on the Living Labs' self-assessment, over 90% of the outcomes were considered to contain elements reflecting either high or medium success.

Living Lab Results Success Rate (RSR)

3.2.2 The degree of the innovation of Living Labs' results

The Living Lab operators rated the degree of innovation of each deliverable. The degree of innovation of the result is one of the three variables used to calculate the KER index. The other variables are the potential for exploitation of the result and the impact of the result. The degree of innovation of the result can have a value of 1, 3 or 9.

The Living Labs rated 27 outcomes as highly innovative, 55 outcomes as medium innovative and 24 outcomes as low innovative. The Living Labs rated 77% of the outcomes as highly or moderately innovative.

Number of results in the 3 innovation

3.2.3 The potential for exploitation of Living Labs' results

Living Lab operators' assessed the potential for exploitation for each delivered result. The potential for exploitation of the result is one of the three variables in calculation of the KER index. The other variables are the degree of innovation and the impact of the result. The potential for exploitation of the result can have a value of 1, 3 or 9.

Living Labs have assessed that 31 results are very exploitable beyond project, 47 results exploitation potential is in medium level, and 28 results exploitation potential is low. Living Labs rated 74% of results as highly or moderately exploitable.

Number of results in the 3 impact groups

3.2.4 The impact of Living Labs' results

The Living Lab operators assessed the impact of each deliverable. The impact of the result is one of the three variables used to calculate the KER index. The other variables are the degree of innovation and the potential for exploitation of the result. The impact of the result can have a value of 1, 3 or 9.

The Living Labs rated 31 of the outcomes as having a high impact on the food system, 47 outcomes as having a medium impact and 28 outcomes as having a low impact. Living Labs rated 74% of the outcomes as high or medium impact.

Number of results in the 3 impact groups

3.2.5 The KER index of the result

In order to prioritise Cities2030 results and select the Key Exploitable Results (KER) of the project, the owner of the result evaluates the result according to three criteria: Degree of Innovation, Exploitability and Impact. The criterion can receive a score of 1, 3 or 9. A score of 1 means, for example, a low degree of innovation or low potential for exploitation, 3 means, for example, medium impact and 9 means high potential for exploitation. The resulting KER index is a multiple of the scores. The KER index can vary from 1 to 729. The higher the KER index, the more innovative, exploitable and impactful the result.

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Number of results in KER index groups

The table below shows the number of Living Lab results. They are divided into four groups, namely Improvement, Good/Promising Practice, Innovation and Other Exploitable Results, and also based on the KER index. The KER indices 232 and 729 represent the most innovative, impactful and exploitable results.

The Living Labs have delivered 30 outcomes with a KER index of 243 and 6 outcomes with a KER index of 729. However, all 110 reported outcomes are relevant to the Living Labs and the transformation of urban food systems.

COUNTA / Result title	Result type 1				
	Improvement	Good/promising practice	Innovation	Other exploitable result	Yhteensä
	0				0
0	0		2	2	4
1		2	3		5
3		3	2	1	6
9		7	7	4	18
27		8	12	2	25
81		1	10	4	16
243	3		14	12	30
729				5	6
Yhteensä	0	24	50	28	110

3.2.6 Living Labs' results foster urban food systems transition towards FOOD 2030 policy

The SusTransition Matrix illustrates and reflects the **systemic and holistic approach of WP5** to promote the transformation of urban food systems. The rows of the matrix are the ten (10) food system themes and the columns are the five (5) specific objectives of the project. The efforts of the Cities2030 Living Labs cover all 10 themes and 5 objectives. In Chapter 1.1 we present a few visualisations of the matrix.

As the aim is to apply system thinking and foster systemic transition in CRFS in line with FOOD 2030 policy, the strategy is that Living Labs' innovation actions will have impact on all steps of the food value chain (groups 1-6) as well as transversal themes (groups 7-10). Similarly, the strategy is that the Living Labs' innovation actions are addressed to all 5 key specific objectives which reflect FOOD 2030 pillars.

<p>Cities2030 five key specific objectives</p> <p>A - Secure healthy and sustainable food B - Stop food poverty and insecurity C - Protect and preserve natural resources D - Enhance circularity and local food belts E - Develop food culture and skills</p>	<p>10 thematic groups</p> <p>1 - Production 2 - Processing 3 - Distribution 4 - Markets 5 - Consumption 6 - Waste 7 - Security 8 - Ecosystem services 9 - Livelihood, growth 10 - Inclusion, equity</p>
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In the following table, the author of this document presents some selected innovation activities and results of Living Labs.

The aim is to show, firstly, the diversity of innovation activities of LLs and, secondly, the innovation activities and results related to the 10 thematic groups and 5 key specific objectives.

10 thematic groups	Cities2030 five key specific objectives	Selected examples of Living Lab's innovation actions and results
1 - Production	A - Secure healthy and sustainable food D - Enhance circularity and local food belts	Food for Iasi Living Lab, Romania <u>Action:</u> The Fair of Iași in traditional, bio, mountain, and artisanal dishes is a fair where local producers show and sell their products to consumers. Here consumers can meet, learn about, and purchase high-value products on the shortest food supply chain. <u>Results:</u> 7 fairs, 82 food producers, 60 000+ visitors and beneficiaries.
2 - Processing	A - Secure healthy and sustainable food	Seinäjäkivi Living Lab, Finland <u>Action:</u> Healthy snacks kiosk: Four pilot kiosks done in different environments. <u>Results:</u> Ensure that snacks provided to children by sports clubs are good nutritional quality and sustainable.
3 -	B - Stop food poverty	Marseille Living Lab, France

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Distribution	and insecurity D - Enhance circularity and local food belts	<p><u>Actions:</u> Mobile grocery store: Sensitization and food transformation workshops for the users of the mobile grocery store. Enlarging the variety of products by introducing are local food producers to the mobile grocery store and selling their products</p> <p><u>Results:</u> Deploy a new type of distribution channel. Enhance rural-urban interaction. Enhance the access to healthy food and promote a short supply chain.</p>
4 - Markets	B - Stop food poverty and insecurity	<p>Murska Sobota Living Lab, Slovenia</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Origin Certification and Fraud Prevention of Short Food Supply Chains</p> <p><u>Result:</u> A solution for optimization of multi-stakeholder dialogue processes, in which blockchain will be employed to provide some proof of concepts of monetization processes, in a reliable and transparent way. In order to ensure transparency, traceability and trust of the local food production, blockchain technology (BC) presents the natural technology fit in the so-called SFSC.</p>
5 - Consumption	E - Develop food culture and skills	<p>Vejle Living Lab, Denmark</p> <p><u>Action:</u> The national competition "the potato award".</p> <p><u>Result:</u> The competition has put the national / local and climate-friendly potato on the agenda. The competition has inspired several restaurants to use the potato on the menu.</p>
6 - Waste	B - Stop food poverty and insecurity D -Enhance circularity and local food belts	<p>Velika Gorica Living Lab, Croatia</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Possibilities of connecting food donors and organisations for distributing food to socially vulnerable groups</p> <p><u>Result:</u> Rethink, reuse, recycle surplus and eatable food. Avoid waste of food.</p>
7 - Security	E - Develop food culture and skills D -Enhance circularity and local food belts	<p>Velika Gorica Living Lab, Croatia</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Establishing a supply chain monitoring system for short value chains and locally produced food (e.g. school scheme and city markets)</p> <p><u>Result:</u> The city/region/country procurement can monitor and assess the trends and practices and plan interventions to a lever for more consumption of local food.</p>
8 - Ecosystem services	C - Protect and preserve natural resources	<p>Haarlem Living Lab, Netherland</p> <p><u>Action:</u> To combat deep-growing root weeds, the experiment tested the use of pigs to eat the weeds plus the roots. Pigs dig up the soil and eat the weeds and roots.</p> <p><u>Results:</u> So a good and sustainable alternative for both weed killing and soil cultivation. The natural soil structure is preserved and it prevents weeds from growing.</p>
9 - Livelihood, growth	A - Secure healthy and sustainable food	<p>Vidzeme Living Lab, Latvia</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Collaboration network establishment between various stakeholders for sustainable local food consumption (including promoting public catering)</p> <p><u>Result:</u> An open innovation environment which applies a multi-actor approach and participatory approach.</p>

D7.5, Annex A, part 1, ed. 3/3
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10 - Inclusion, equity	E - Develop food culture and skills	<p>Bremerhaven Living Lab. Germany</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Local bread for local kids - A multidisciplinary team developed a bread baking mix that focuses on transparency and regionality.</p> <p><u>Result:</u> The involvement of young people increased understanding and appreciation for local products among them. The experiment provides inspiration and motivation for future developments, with transparent traceability of local raw materials as a primary objective.</p>
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3.2.7 External SMEs participation in Living Labs innovation activities

Many of the Cities2030 Living Labs have invited and engaged SMEs to join the effort to transform urban food systems. The table below provides an insight into the Living Lab actions where SMEs are involved and, where possible, beneficiaries of the innovation actions.

In addition to SME business development, the Living Labs have provided a common social space for city region policy makers, authorities and SMEs. The aim of the multi-stakeholder approach is to stimulate public-private partnerships (PPP) in the context of city region food systems.

SME	Living Lab, Country	A brief of the innovation action
CODAN S.A.	Arganda, ES	CODAN is a Spanish SME based in Arganda, leader in the production of pastries. CODAN has participated in the Arganda lab, providing its production infrastructure for the testing of industry 4.0 solutions. Specifically, it has actively participated in the experimentation stage, facilitating the integration of the S2CP platform (Cities2030 WP6) for the collection of information in real time, and thus being able to evaluate the optimal nature of the working conditions in its facilities.
Zelena Točka Trans, z.o.o.	Murska Sobota, SI	Zelena Točka Trans, z.o.o. is a Slovenian SME who is a short food supply chain operator in the region of Pomurje. Within the Murska Sobota living lab, they have been included in the experiment of implementing blockchain traceability within the supply chain. Together with ITC, they have updated their processes to digitalize the process of product manipulation through the supply chain. Finally, QR codes in their store allow consumers/citizens to receive rich data about the product life cycle (from the farm to the shelf in the store).
Neo-Eco	Marseille, FR	Neo-Eco is a French SME working on soils and circular economy in the construction sector. It aims to recreate living soils in the city using soil waste and rocks from construction operations. It has been working with the Marseille LL for the past year to map wastelands in Marseille and their soil characteristics. It has led to a joint workshop at the Cities2030 final event and to the integration of Neo-Eco into the future governance of the Marseille LL.
Biolan Oy	Lahti, FI	Biolan Oy is a Finnish SME that manufactures bio-composters. In the

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		<p>experiment, we tested a digitised food waste bio-composter, which enables remote monitoring of the composting process and intervention. Biolan Oy is eager to use the experiment results and is considering the next steps.</p>
Magazia Moraritei	FILL, Food for Iasi Living Lab, Romania	<p>Certified producer of artisan bread with maya or yeast, baked on the hearth, pies, sardelles, homemade biscuits, and other pastries. All the products are made with natural ingredients, without additives or flavour enhancers. FILL facilitated knowledge transfer for Magazia Moraritei to implement organic procedures. FILL also facilitated the access to the urban market in Iasi for Magazia Moraritei.</p>
Made in Iasi Local Producers Association	Food for Iasi Living Lab, Romania	<p>FILL facilitated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Building a Community of practice within the Association ● Access to the urban food market for the members of the association ● Multi-actor activities for the members of the association and other regional stakeholders.
Thimus	Quart de Poblet, ES	<p>Thimus is a company dedicated to developing innovative solutions to study individual food choice behaviour. Their mission is to responsibly demystify the complexities of human experience. By accurately understanding the emotions and experiences people have in association to the foods they eat, they devise proactive, actionable plans to engage humans in the sustainable/regenerative food movement.</p>
Bon Aire	Quart de Poblet, ES	<p>Bon Aire restaurant has been located in the Albufera area since 1982. Its cuisine is based on traditional Valencian gastronomy, which they aim to recover but with an innovative component, as they adapt the richness of the tradition they defend to new formats.</p>
Clinica Eva Moreno	Quart de Poblet, ES	<p>Clinic established in the municipality of Quart de Poblet, which offers different services, including nutritional counselling. The nutritionist in charge of this service is a nutritional educator and has extensive experience in the field of children.</p>
26 food producers	Agrotopia, BE	<p>Together with these growers, we looked into which other alternative water sources could be used in their greenhouse management. We sampled and tested different water sources in our own cultivation. This knowledge allows them to be more sustainable and minimise the amount of groundwater that is used.</p>
Kytos	Agrotopia, BE	<p>Kytos is a start up company that wants to use flow cytometry as a diagnostic tool to track irrigation quality and offer an extra tool to help food producers in their water quality management.</p>
Moj gruntek d.o.o.	Velika Gorica, Croatia	<p>Showcased as a good example of CSA in our CRFS in 2nd core team and in Cities2030 food conference in Velika Gorica and Degrowth</p>

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		conference in Zagreb
Promet i prostor d.o.o.	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Showcased their GIS platform and layer of local food producers to 2nd core team of Lab Velika Gorica
VeeMee d.o.o.	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Showcased as a best online local platform for presentation of local food producers
10 local food producers	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Local food producers, presented their certified (by Zagreb city) products on one of the Cities2030 food conference in Velika Gorica
Wolt Zagreb d.o.o.	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Presented their innovative business model for food delivery management for Velika Gorica's small food producers on one of the Cities2030 food conference in Velika Gorica
Algo eko d.o.o.	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Presented types of certificates of quality and other city/region support services for local food producers on one of the Cities2030 food conference in Velika Gorica
Tempus savjetovanje, obrt za usluge i trgovinu	Velika Gorica, Croatia	Established connection with Agrotopia via our lab regarding project idea on development of special farm of black soldier fly larva as food for chicken
Urban Pergola UG	Bremerhaven, Germany	The start-up "urban pergola" is involved in the activities in the Goethequartier, we have organised 1 workshop together. CITIES2030 has raised awareness and strengthened networking with local stakeholders. We supported the "Leher Pergolinchen" project: A green oasis in the open playground and meeting point of the Goethequartier "Leher Pausenhof" in Bremerhaven.
Roval GmbH	Bremerhaven, Germany	The first agricultural algae farm in Germany! Innovative and sustainable farming is the reason for our enthusiasm for microalgae. Open and direct contact between producers and customers. We used the company's products for the "local bread for local kids" experiment. The company is part of our travelling exhibition "local heroes" and gains visibility through CITIES2030. The exhibition will be handed over to our local food council at the end of the project and will continue to be used and expanded in 2025 and 2026. In addition they presented its activities in the regional system as a short talk at our "Science goes PUPlic" event in summer 2022. We organised the event as a CITIES2030 team together with the EU project "NextGenProteins". Benefit: Increased awareness in the region,

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		networking with other companies that were on site, contact with the science scene
EntoSus GmbH	Bremerhaven, Germany	<p>Insect farm in Bremen. The <i>acheta domestica</i> are cultivated according to the guidelines of the Naturland cultivation association. Furthermore, SME acts according to the principles of the regional circular economy. For example, the residues from the farm are fed back into agriculture as fertiliser.</p> <p>We have used the company's products, it is part of our "local heroes" exhibition and presented itself at the "Science goes PUPlic" event. See above for details.</p>
Roland Beans GmbH	Bremerhaven, Germany	<p>ROLAND BEANS GmbH is a joint venture founded in 2019 by the companies RAISA and ROLAND MILLS UNITED. We thus combine our complementary expertise in the cultivation, raw material supply, processing and application technology of field beans along the value chain in an ideal way.</p> <p>We have used the company's products, it is part of our "local heroes" exhibition and presented itself at the "Science goes PUPlic" event. See above for details.</p>
Noble mushrooms by Wolters Hof	Bremerhaven, Germany	<p>Former pig farm that now grows mushrooms.</p> <p>The company is part of our travelling exhibition "local heroes" and gains visibility through CITIES2030. The exhibition will be handed over to our local food council at the end of the project and will continue to be used and expanded in 2025 and 2026.</p>
BIO LandGut von der Lieth	Bremerhaven, Germany	<p>Hens for hire: You hire a hen from us and receive six eggs a week for 50 weeks at a collection point of your choice.</p> <p>The company is part of our travelling exhibition "local heroes" and gains visibility through CITIES2030.</p>

4. Conclusions

Observations on innovation actions of Living Labs

18 Living Labs are active. They have implemented innovation actions in their city regions.

Living Labs have implemented their action plans (ref. D5.1, D5.5) and initiated 106 experiments, other actions and systems thinking pilots and 40 capacity building events. The total number of innovation actions reported by Living Labs is 146.

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As expected, regarding 10 thematic groups, the consumption and markets are at the top, but production also ranks high. In terms of 5 key specific objectives, the top three are: Ensuring healthy and sustainable food; Strengthening circularity and local food belts; Developing food culture and skills.

Observations on the number and character of the results of the Living Labs

The innovation actions have generated 24 improvements, 50 good/promising practices, 28 innovations and 8 other exploitable results. More than 200 000 participants have been involved in the LL actions.

22 business canvas model descriptions have been delivered through the work of Task 5.3

Most of the results (58%) fall into the social innovation group. Social innovations are mostly good/promising practices. The second largest group is technological innovation (12.7%).

More than 50% of the results are classified as other intangible results, such as good practices and social innovations. The second largest group is services (19%). The Living Labs have assessed the need to protect Intellectual property Rights (IPR). Based on the data given by LL operators there are results which for sure or probably require protection, but also results that are open.

When the results are evaluated according to the Technology Readiness Level, the results are classified as follows: TRL 1 - TR3 is about 20%, TRL 4 - TR6 is about 13% and TRL 7 - TRL9 is about 55%. The proportion of uncoded results was 12%.

Observations on the assessment of the results of Living Labs

Based on the Living Labs' self-assessment, over 90% of the outcomes were considered to contain elements reflecting either high or medium success in the implementation.

Living Labs rated 77% of the outcomes as highly or moderately innovative.

Living Labs rated 74% of results as highly or moderately exploitable.

Living Labs rated 74% of the outcomes as high or medium impact.

The KER indices 232 and 729 represent the most innovative, impactful and exploitable results. The Living Labs produced 30 results with a KER index of 243 and 6 results with a KER index of 729. The share of the two highest KER index groups is 33%.

Reflection on systemic transition towards FOOD 2030 policy

The below graphic illustrates what systems change is about with reference to phase transitions and tipping points. It emphasises that if we aim to change systems then we need to think about the emergence of a new pattern (new paradigm) not only solutions to problems or challenges.

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Source: New paradigm and Tipping Point, Joss Colchester, Systems Innovation Network, <https://www.systemsinnovation.network/spaces/11594882/page>

In Cities2030, we have implemented numerous place-based interventions in urban food systems to support the shift from the old paradigm to the new and emerging paradigm. We aim to reach out the critical mass and cross the tipping point, not only in pilot cities but beyond.

Old paradigm of City Region Food System	New paradigm of City Region Food System
<p>The old paradigm of City Region Food Systems emphasises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Industrial agriculture ● Long food supply chains ● Urban-rural divide ● Limited stakeholder engagement ● Environmental degradation ● Food insecurity ● Limited policy coherence. 	<p>The new and emerging paradigm for City Region Food Systems emphasises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holistic and integrated approach ● Territorial focus ● Multi-stakeholder approach ● Sustainable and resilient food systems ● Social and economic equity ● Urban-rural linkages and interaction ● Policy coherence.

Reflection on System Thinking in the context of systemic transition towards FOOD 2030 policy

System Thinking is an approach that considers the interconnections and interdependencies among various components of a system, recognizing that changes in one part of the system can have ripple effects throughout the entire system. The following principles are essential for System Thinking approach:

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- System Thinking enables a holistic understanding of the urban food system, recognizing that it is a complex and dynamic system that involves various actors, processes, and interactions. The holistic understanding of the city region food systems has been evolved through implementing e.g., Problem Based Learning, CRFS Logic Framework and Extended Innovation Pattern.
- System Thinking highlights the interconnectedness of different components of the urban food system, such as steps of the food value chain: production, processing, distribution, consumption, and waste management.
- System Thinking encourages a multi-actor and participatory approach that involves various stakeholders in the decision-making processes related to urban food systems. A Living Lab provides an arena and platform for multi-actor and participatory approach.
- System Thinking promotes a long-term perspective that considers the sustainability and resilience of the food system over time.

4.1 Deviation analysis

The Deviation analysis focuses on measurable targets related to the innovation activities and outcomes of the Living Labs. The Cities2030 grant agreement defines the key performance indicators for the performance of the Living Labs. The gap analysis considers the gap and possible causes of the gap.

Living Labs' innovation actions

Deviation analysis considers Key Performance Indicator (KPI) that is set at the grant agreement vs the actual achieved result that has been reported by Living Labs.

KPI defined in the GA table 2.1.b

The target is to reach out 50*2 Living Lab experiments. The number 50 refers to 50 cities which are the arena for experiments. The associated KPI is defined in the GA table 2.1.b

KPI vs actual result analysis

In reality, there were only 18 operational Living Labs, targeting their actions to 18 city regions. 18 Living Labs have reported 146 innovation actions, the majority of which are experiments or closely related to experiments, such as capacity building actions.

The initial target set in the General Agreement (Table 2.1.b) was for 50 Living Labs to carry out 2 experiments. In practice, 18 operational Living Labs carried out an average of 5 experiments and innovation actions.

Living Labs' results

Deviation analysis considers Key Performance Indicator (KPI) that is set at the grant agreement vs the actual achieved result that has been reported by Living Labs.

KPI - defined in the GA table 2.1.b

100+ documented improvements, 50+ good practice documents and 10+ innovations. In total 160+ deliverables. There is also a target of 10+ business models.

KPI vs actual result analysis:

Living Labs documented 24 improvements, 50 good practices, 28 innovations and 8 other exploitable results. In total 110 results. In addition, the project has defined 22 Business Model Canvases as a result of T5.3.

The potentials reasons for the deviation are as follows:

- The KPIs are set on a very optimistic basis. The rationale behind the KPIs is that if 50 cities and corresponding 50 Living Labs carry out well researched, grounded and planned experiments, they should deliver innovative results.
- The first reason for the deviation is that the number of operational Living Labs was 18 instead of 50. This means that the arena and potential for innovative ideas was more limited.
- The second main reason is that the outcome of an innovative experiment is unpredictable. The result may or may not match the hypothesis and assumptions. The mission of the Living Labs was not to "deliver" results on demand, but to initiate innovative experiments and identify the exploitable results.
- The third reason for the discrepancy regarding the low number of 'improvements' may be that the Living Labs operators are too ambitious to report the 'improvements'. For example, improvements in participants' capacities and competences were rarely mentioned, although these are very relevant improvements for systemic change. Instead of "improvements", partners preferred to report "best practices".

4.2 Limitations of Living Labs in the context of Cities2030

When considering the results of the Cities2030 Living Lab, it's important to understand the limitations and nature of the working environment. The following issues need to be considered:

Living Lab is an open innovation environment: Cities2030 Living Labs are - by default - open innovation environments, which doesn't necessarily encourage participating organisations, especially for-profit companies, to openly share their best ideas. It may be that the innovation activities of the Living Labs in the local settings have driven exploitable outcomes, innovations and business models that the Living Labs have not been able to identify and report. In other words, the true impact of Living Lab activities on the businesses of participating companies is not known.

Living Labs mobilise and engage multi-stakeholder community members in innovation actions: The exploitation of the results of the Living Labs is of course a tool to promote the systemic transformation of the urban food system, but equally important are the activities mobilised by the Living Labs, such as stakeholder engagement, capacity building actions, dialogues, meetings and activities related to the experiments.

Living Labs are place-based and aim to deliver solutions in their own locality: The outcomes of Living Labs are - by default - place-based and thus linked to the conditions of the city and the country. When assessing the potential for exploitation of the result, Living Labs have considered the potential levels of exploitation/replication of the result: local, regional, national and EU-wide. However, guidance on exploitation assessment, e.g. from the EU, does not give explicit guidance on how to approach the different

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levels of exploitation. This leads to an exploitation assessment of results that isn't comparable with other results, but is indicative.

The results of the Cities2030 Living Labs reflect the profiles of the consortium partners: The majority of partners contributing to the Living Labs were public bodies or non-governmental organisations. Their capacity and competence to deliver, for example, high-tech food products or industrial solutions is low. Instead, they have typically focused their efforts on social innovation and best practice. The consortium includes some partners focused on food technology.

The Living Lab experiment can fail, but learning is imperative: A Living Lab is - by default - an experimental laboratory. The lab tests hypotheses and some hypotheses seem to be true and others fail. Living Lab experiments can fail, and the result is simply a lesson learned, which is valuable in itself. Living Labs are NOT machines that produce usable results, but they are participatory and open environments for ideating, building, testing and learning.

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CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
9-IASI	Romania	Building the Gust de Iasi recommendation mark and index for the most valuable local products. The recommendation mark will be given to the local producers if they comply with high scores in sustainability, durability, social value, traditional values, biocircular economy and so on.	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 2 –	9	9	9	729	No
9-IASI	Romania	Knowledge & Action Ecosystem	Innovation	Scientific innovation	Scientific or Technolo	9	Yes	TRL 4 –	9	9	9	729	Yes
7-Quart de Poblet	Spain	Co-creation session with land users in which possible alternatives to start the transition of the lands to ecological urban gardens are presented; new alternatives are proposed and a vote is taken.	Innovation	Political innovation	Policy Related Result	3	No	Other	9	9	9	729	No
15-Marseille	France	City finances partly the innovation ---> the concept how to co-operate with the city	Other exploitable result	Social innovation	Policy Related Result	9	No	TRL 9 –	9	9	9	729	Yes
14-Cilento Region	Italy	Manifesto on the first Experimental Marine Area of the Mediterranean	Innovation	Political innovation	Policy Related Result	9	No	TRL 7 –	9	9	9	729	Yes
13-Venice	Italy	Protection of salt marshes and populations of endangered plant species, creation of a method for the identification of new plant edibles, enhancement of edible heritage in the lagoon, development of sustainable economies in areas with high depopulation rates.	Innovation	Business model	Other	3	Yes	TRL 2 –	9	9	9	729	Yes
9-IASI	Romania	Strengthening the trust of the urban consumers in local producers.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Yes	TRL 4 –	3	9	9	243	No
9-IASI	Romania	Establishing cycloturistic routes to give urban consumers the possibility to visit local producers.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Yes	TRL 4 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
9-IASI	Romania	Raise awareness to the benefits of digital payments for local producers to raise their access to the urban market.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Yes	TRL 4 –	3	9	9	243	No
9-IASI	Romania	Stakeholders Facilitator Toolkit. In the research activities of the Romanian living lab, we are developing a set of tools for facilitators in their action to build project stakeholder communities. The toolkit consists of a set of recommendations, good practices, methodologies, models for knowledge management, digital tools, hub integration support (support for integration in our research hub within RDRP Knowledge Ecosystem).	Good/promising practice	Scientific innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 4 –	9	9	3	243	Perhaps
9-IASI	Romania	Food for Iasi Living Lab integrated innovative platform	Innovation	Other	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 9 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
9-IASI	Romania	Research project: Scientific research for shortening the food chains and increasing the access to the markets for the local producers. The research project is developing in Urban & CRF Systems Laboratory within Food for Iasi Living Lab	Innovation	Scientific innovation	Scientific or Technolo	3	Yes	TRL 4 –	3	9	9	243	Perhaps

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CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
9-IASI	Romania	"Iașul în bucate tradiționale, ecologice, montane și artizanale" (The Fair of Iași in traditional, bio, mountain, and artisanal dishes) is a fair where local producers show and sell their products to consumers. Edition 1. TOTAL: 7 Editions.	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 8 –	3	9	9	243	Perhaps
9-IASI	Romania	Scientific article: Implications of COVID-19 pandemic on sustainable consumption patterns. Evidence from Iasi County, Romania	Innovation	Scientific innovation	Scientific or Technolo	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	9	9	3	243	Perhaps
7-Quart de Poblet	Spain	Identification of invaders of lands	Improvement	Social innovation	Policy Related Result	9	No	Other	9	9	3	243	No
7-Quart de Poblet	Spain	Briefing session: Engagement of invaders of lands	Improvement	Social innovation	Policy Related Result	9	No	Other	9	9	3	243	No
7-Quart de Poblet	Spain	Approval of a municipal regulation concerning the use of Municipal Urban Gardens.	Other exploitable result	Political innovation	Policy Related Result	3	No	Other	3	9	9	243	Yes
6-Bremenhaven	Germany	Lehe in progress" co-create a part of the participatory oasis „Pergolnchen“	Good/promising practice	Technology innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	No	TRL 9 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
6-Bremenhaven	Germany	Casual Learning/Scavenger Hunt	Good/promising practice	Other	Other Intangible Resu	9	No	TRL 9 –	9	3	9	243	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	The local competition "Local cooking" - the result is that focus has been placed on local ingredients, local producers have been highlighted. The event has created visibility in relation to using local ingredients in restaurants around the region	Innovation	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	3	Perhaps	Other	9	3	9	243	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	The "Vejle Championship in hotdog" event. The result is that the students have gained knowledge about sustainable food. We have set the framework for the students to strengthen their innovative power.	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Perhaps	Other	9	3	9	243	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	the national competition "the potato award". the result is that the competition has put the national / local and climate-friendly potato on the agenda. The competition has inspired several restaurants to use the potato on the menu.	Innovation	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
4-Vejle	Denmark	the competition "the potato sprout". The result is that many students have worked with innovation in relation to production of sustainable dishes. the students have gained knowledge about the climatefriendly benefits of eating potatoes.	Innovation	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
4-Vejle	Denmark	Gastronomic Underground - potatoes. The result of event was four innovative dishes create by young chefs with focus on potatoes. The chefs were challenged to take climate and sustainability in consideration and mediation on sustainability and potatoes enlightened the guests at the event.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	3	9	9	243	Yes

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CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
4-Vejle	Denmark	The national competition "The Potato Award". The result is that the competition has put the national / local and climate-friendly potato on the agenda. The competition has inspired several restaurants to use the potato on the menu.	Innovation	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
4-Vejle	Denmark	The competition "The Potato Sprout". The result is that many students have worked with innovation in relation to production of sustainable dishes containing potatoes. The students have gained knowledge about the climatefriendly benefits of eating potatoes.	Innovation	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 7 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
19-Setesdal (NO)	Norway	60 farmers learned to become commercially autonomous in terms of BtoB and BtoC for their own products and created an autonomous community of producers	Improvement	Business model	Other Intangible Resu	9	No	TRL 9 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
19-Setesdal (NO)	Norway	Payment system	Innovation	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	9	Yes	TRL 9 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
14-Cilento Region	Italy	Promote and support a holistic and integrated approach to sustainable development in line with the "Mediterranean Diet" way of life	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Policy Related Result	9	No	Other	3	9	9	243	Yes
13-Venice	Italy	Establish an operations centre that supports fishermen in their activities and strengthens the sense of belonging to the Cooperative in sharing a "home". Support and greater synergy with the Fishermen's Cooperative, redevelopment of the area in terms of architecture and visibility in the area.	Good/promising practice	Technology innovation	Scientific or Technolo	3	Yes	TRL 3 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
13-Venice	Italy	Definition of possible strategies for abandoned areas. Mapping of land, constraints, potential. To reactivate abandoned areas. To enhance the potential of the territory in terms of ecosystem services.	Good/promising practice	Business model	Policy Related Result	3	No	TRL 1 –	9	3	9	243	Yes
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Wij telen groente' (We grow vegetables) and farm 'De Herkomst' (The Origin) puts pigs for natural grazing to maintain the soil instead of using machines.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	No	TRL 7 –	3	9	9	243	Perhaps
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Through an Orbisk pilot with five restaurants from the frontrunner group of Sept / Nov 2022, their food waste was measured using a software monitor.	Innovation	Technology innovation	Scientific or Technolo	3	Perhaps	TRL 7 –	9	9	3	243	Yes
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Collaboration 'OOGST' to stimulate local food by a store with products directly from farms. Acces store by app.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Perhaps	TRL 7 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Collaboration 'Mealtip' to provide people with less money access to organic food and food that comes to experiation date to provide food waste.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Perhaps	TRL 4 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
1-Brugge	Belgium	Intergenerational cooking sessions	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	3	9	9	243	Yes
9-IASI	Romania	To build a Communicators Community as a good model for dissemination management.	Good/promising practice	Other	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 4 –	3	9	3	81	No
6-Bremenhaven	Germany	Local bread for local school kids	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	3	9	3	81	Perhaps

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CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
6-Bremenhaven	Germany	Kindergarten waste minimization	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results	9	No	TRL 9 –	3	9	3	81	No
6-Bremenhaven	Germany	Potato Workshop	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results (Ex. citizens engagement)				3	9	3	81	Perhaps
5-Seinäjoki	Finland	The Healthy Snacks Kiosk	Good/promising practice	Business model	Services (Ex. research)	3	No	TRL 9 –	3	9	3	81	
4-Vejle	Denmark	The event "Fjorden på bordet". (All the three event together / from the slite "innovation action") the result is that we have gained knowledge about the environmental problems that take place in the inlet near vejle. We have submitted an innovative idea for how the problem can be solved.	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results	3	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	9	3	3	81	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	the international event about taste. the result is that we have created knowledge about how we create flavor in plantbased dishes. We have made it clear how important the good taste if people are going to eat more plantbased food.	Good/promising practice	Other	Services (Ex. research)	9	Perhaps	Other	3	3	9	81	No
4-Vejle	Denmark	"The Christmas calendar about foodwaste". The result is that we have given inspiration to the general citizen on how to reduce food waste during the Christmas season. We have made four episodes, which are shared on SOME.	Other exploitable result	Other	Services (Ex. research)	1	Perhaps	Other	3	3	9	81	No
4-Vejle	Denmark	Young talents have learned specific kitchen skills and now functions as ambassadors for the culinary world.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results	3	Perhaps	TRL 7 –	3	9	3	81	Yes
18-Lahti	Finland	SMARTY: IoT-equipped food waste composter	Innovation	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	9	9	1	81	No
14-Cilento Region	Italy	Co-designing better natural resources and value of the Mediterranean diet by fun	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results	3	No	TRL 6 –	3	9	3	81	Yes
14-Cilento Region	Italy	Tik Tok campaign challenge on Mediterranean biodiversity	Innovation	Technology innovation	Other Intangible Results	3	No	TRL 3 –	9	3	3	81	No
13-Venice	Italy	Develop a shared language and a series of diverse communicative tools to discuss the city-region food system through a series of workshops and open talks and the production of the archive.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Results	3	Yes	TRL 3 –	9	9	1	81	Perhaps
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Making plant food granules from wool for which there is no other destination. Define a plan for upscaling.	Innovation	Business model	Other Intangible Results	1	Yes		1	9	9	81	Perhaps
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Food Waste Challenge - 8 restaurants in Haarlem participate , collaboration Rabobank and Haarlem Food Future	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research)	3	No	TRL 7 –	3	9	3	81	Perhaps
1-Brugge	Belgium	Culinary upgrade food on the spot (community center)	Improvement	Social innovation	Other	9	Perhaps	TRL 3 –	3	9	3	81	Yes
All LLs	All	LL Innovation Facilitators Training Package: Interviews, needs analysis, trainings, training material for 3 session, hosting community platform forum discussion, mentoring of facilitators, case study examples	Good/promising practice	Other	Services (Ex. research)	9	No	TRL 9 –	1	9	3	27	No

WP5 Results of Living Labs - D7.5, ed. 3, Annex A part 2

CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
All LLS	All	A work force of 10+ Living Lab Innovation Facilitators	Other exploitable result	Other	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 7 –	1	9	3	27	No
All LLS	All	Elaboration of technical KPI framework for performance monitoring of the S2CO platform	Good/promising practice	Technology innovation	Scientific or Technolo	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	3	3	3	27	Perhaps
9-IASI	Romania	Cities2030 Facebook Network. Social Media Supporting Document	Good/promising practice	Other	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 8 –	3	3	3	27	No
9-IASI	Romania	Healthy food workshops in schools. 6 workshops with local producers in schools.	Other exploitable result	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	3	3	3	27	Yes
9-IASI	Romania	7 Local producers fairs and weekend mobile fairs in Iasi. Zilele recoltei la USV (2 editions), Piata volanta din Tatarasi, Festivalul cireselor, Festivalul iei, Festivalul dulciurilor, Satul in bucate. Over 60 000 direct beneficiaries.	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 8 –	3	3	3	27	Yes
5-Seinäjäjoki	Finland	The School Canteens into restaurants	Improvement	Social innovation	Other	1	No	TRL 1 –	3	9	1	27	No
5-Seinäjäjoki	Finland	The Childrens's food education in an art and culture event "Pikkuprovinsi"	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 3 –	3	9	1	27	No
5-Seinäjäjoki	Finland	Sports clubs have been reached and they are participating actively in the competition on social media	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other	3	No	TRL 9 –	3	9	1	27	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	Gastroday - potatoes: the food professionals got more insight on using potatoes with a historical perspective	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	1	9	3	27	Perhaps
4-Vejle	Denmark	"Potato celebrations": people got insight in the climate and health advantages of potatoes and furthermore how to minimize food waste with potatoes.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	3	3	3	27	No
4-Vejle	Denmark	The "Vejle Championship in hotdog" event. The result is that the students have gained knowledge about sustainable food. We have set the framework for the students to strengthen their innovative power.	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Perhaps	Other	3	3	3	27	No
18-Lahti	Finland	Timely, versatile, and multi-actor nudging framework to promote food waste reuse and circulation to the new regime.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 7 –	3	9	1	27	No
18-Lahti	Finland	Extended target group for SMARTY	Improvement	Business model	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	3	3	3	27	No
18-Lahti	Finland	Inbuilt scalability	Improvement	Business model	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	3	3	3	27	No
15-Marseille	France	New knowledge on finance	Improvement	Other	Other	9	No	TRL 8 –	3	3	3	27	No
14-Cilento Region	Italy	New service provided for the community to support the digitalization and the social proudness of the territory	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	No	Other	1	3	9	27	Yes
13-Venice	Italy	Organise a large widespread event that involves the actors of the food arena to strengthen the sense of belonging and to engage individuals of all ages in a discussion about the food system.	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Yes	TRL 7 –	1	9	3	27	Perhaps

WP5 Results of Living Labs - D7.5, ed. 3, Annex A part 2

CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
13-Venice	Italy	Engage in a continuous discussion at the planning and policy level with diverse stakeholders, developing innovative planning scenarios for the Venice Lagoon (food system) through a series of workshops and a Design Studio (1-semester course).	Good/promising practice	Scientific innovation	Services (Ex. research)	9	No	TRL 8 –	3	3	3	27	No
13-Venice	Italy	To put cuisine at the centre of the dialogue between nature and culture. Raising awareness and dissemination of local knowledge about gastronomy. Creation of a wider research community that brings forward an innovative relationship between food and the lagoon territory.	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	Yes	TRL 7 –	3	3	3	27	Perhaps
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	The 'Wilde Oogsten (Wild Harvest)' is investigating how biodiversity can be increased by means of vegetable garden techniques (regenerative agriculture) and cooperation with livestock farming (for natural grazing and tillage of the land).	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 7 –	3	3	3	27	Perhaps
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Foodlab uses the 'Train the trainer' program to train neighbors with a passion for cooking to give children sustainable and healthy cooking classes in their own neighbourhood.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research)	9	Perhaps	TRL 7 –	1	9	3	27	Perhaps
1-Brugge	Belgium	Repetative communication focusgroups with the target population	Improvement	Social innovation	Other	3	No	TRL 1 –	3	9	1	27	Yes
8-Vidzeme	Latvia	Innovation no 1	Innovation	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 4 –	9	1	1	9	
8-Vidzeme	Latvia	Improvement	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 4 –	9	1	1	9	
8-Vidzeme	Latvia	Practose	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	Perhaps	TRL 4 –	9	1	1	9	
7-Quart de Poblet	Spain	App for food value chain	Innovation	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	3	Yes	TRL 7 –	3	3	1	9	Perhaps
2-VelikaGorica	Croatia	CSA presentation of good examples	Good/promising practice	Scientific innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 6 –	1	1	9	9	Perhaps
18-Lahti	Finland	A force of 10 experts of experience who are volunteers to give their insight to bokashi beginners on request.	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 7 –	1	9	1	9	No
18-Lahti	Finland	Revised SMARTY	Improvement	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	1	3	3	9	No
18-Lahti	Finland	SMARTY third parties	Improvement	Business model	Other Intangible Resu	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	1	3	3	9	No
16-Arganda	Spain	Validation of Real-time data monitoring component, of S2CP platform. This component provides a system for receiving events produced by sensors. This S2CP component can collect information generated in a city, farm or other food-related organization, so that information can be later represented for real-time visualization or monetization.	Improvement	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	1	3	3	9	Perhaps
13-Venice	Italy	To design, develop and implement activities that contribute to the enhancement of fishing cultural heritage. To study and raise awareness for the population and visitors	Innovation	Social innovation	Scientific or Technolo	9	No	TRL 3 –	1	3	3	9	Yes

WP5 Results of Living Labs - D7.5, ed. 3, Annex A part 2

CRFS Living Lab	Actor's country	Result title	Result type 1	Result type 2	KER category [1]	RSR [2]	IPR [3]	TRL [4]	Assess degree of innovation	Assess the potential for exploitation	Assess Impact [7]	KER index [8]	Potential target for investment
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Workshop with partners who started experiments to share results so far and experiences.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	9	No	TRL 7 –	1	3	3	9	No
12-Haarlem	Netherlands	Plukweide (Flower Garden) grows oyster mushrooms on wood chips (residual material) from the Maak site as a basis for compost. In addition, they are conducting tests for an even more fertile compost with worms and food leftovers in Bokashi containers.	Good/promising practice	Technology innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 9 –	1	3	3	9	No
1-Brugge	Belgium	Buddy moments, bringing the elderly together within the community center.	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	TRL 3 –	3	1	3	9	Perhaps
1-Brugge	Belgium	Delivery of meals by bike	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	1	No	TRL 1 –	3	3	1	9	Yes
1-Brugge	Belgium	Vehicle sharing platform	Innovation	Business model	Other Intangible Resu	1	Perhaps	TRL 1 –	3	3	1	9	Yes
1-Brugge	Belgium	Focusgroup with the target population concerning food and delivery	Improvement	Social innovation	Other	3	No	TRL 1 –	3	3	1	9	Yes
1-Brugge	Belgium	focusgroup with the target population concerning inclusion	Improvement	Social innovation	Other	1	No	TRL 1 –	3	3	1	9	Yes
All LLS	All	System Thinking Methodology	Good/promising practice	Scientific innovation	Other Intangible Resu	1	No	TRL 7 –	3	1	1	3	No
5-Seinäjoki	Finland	The Food Business Club	Improvement	Other	Services (Ex. research	1	No	TRL 7 –	1	3	1	3	No
4-Vejle	Denmark	Workshop: mediation of sustainability and cooking of potatoes for local school	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research	9	Perhaps	TRL 9 –	1	3	1	3	Perhaps
18-Lahti	Finland	Focused metrics	Improvement	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	9	Yes	TRL 7 –	1	3	1	3	No
1-Brugge	Belgium	Plant based protein enhancement	Innovation	Scientific innovation	Other Intangible Resu	1	No	TRL 1 –	3	1	1	3	Perhaps
All LLS	All	Extended Innovation Pattern, Handbook, training material, guidance concepts.	Good/promising practice	Scientific innovation	Other Intangible Resu	1	No	TRL 7 –	1	1	1	1	No
18-Lahti	Finland	Open data file (www.avoindata.fi) and mapping the food waste operators in Finland (Power Bi application)	Improvement	Technology innovation	ICT Software Digital s	3	No	TRL 7 –	1	1	1	1	No
10-Murska Sobota	Slovenia	Promotion and uptake of the local food in the region	Improvement	Social innovation	Other Intangible Resu	3	No	Other	1	1	1	1	No
11-Vicenza	Italy	Youth engaged in Sustainable Eating through Intergenerational Learning	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research			TRL 8 –				0	Yes
11-Vicenza	Italy	Inclusion of the experiment as a proposed laboratory Territorial Training Offer Plan for the year 2023-2024	Good/promising practice	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research			TRL 8 –				0	Yes
11-Vicenza	Italy	Inclusion of the experiment as a proposed laboratory Territorial Training Offer Plan for the year 2023-2024	Other exploitable result	Social innovation	Services (Ex. research			TRL 8 –				0	Yes

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

AGROTOPIA LIVING LAB

Designed by:

Simon Craeye, Maarten Ameye

Date:

29/02/2024

Version:

1

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>-growers -grower associations -Government (local, regional, national) -technology providers</p>				
<p>Key Resources </p> <p>Mail, website, newsletter, visual tools on location (touch screens), physical meetings at Agrotopia and on location (in house, trade shows, knowledge exchange events) Maximal integration in existing communication channels</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Agrotopia uses dynamic pricing for their activities. Specifically based on the needs and wishes of the parties. Through negotiation, the pricing and contract may be adjusted to better align the project goals.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

ARGANDA

Designed by:

Ramon Alcarria

Date:

10/03/2024

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Some objectives are related to a niche market (production optimization or supply chain) but others are related to a broader audience (citizens as food consumers, and CODAN clients).</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>The aim is to study a business model in which consumers are willing to pay a little more to obtain accurate information about manufacturing processes.</p> <p>On the other hand, the innovation manager is willing to pay to introduce improvements in their manufacturing processes. The Arganda pilot allows experiments to be carried out to determine if these improvements are possible, and to calculate the impact and costs of implementing them.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

BREMERHAVEN

Team "local bread for local kids";
L. Böhm

08/04/2024

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>- Tourism, - special events such as Christmas presents for local companies and institutions</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>The story behind is the most important purchase argument.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

BREMERHAVEN

Urban Pergola, Lina Becker

11/04/2014

1.0

<h3>Key Partners </h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal constructions - Private sector / private households - Education 				
<h3>Cost Structure </h3> <p>Private loans → 250 euros each</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1000 euros founding capital (limitation: liability issues) - price awards → 40,000 euros - funding from climate city office (2021) - no university support 				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

BRUGES

Designed by:

Barbara Plovie, Annelies
FLeurbaey

Date:

06/12/2023

Version:

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Elderly individuals who still live at home within the region of Bruges. -Additional individuals with mental or physical disabilities from the region -Chefs from the culinary school <p>a diversified customer base</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>fixed price customers pay, transaction revenues, Implementation in the budget of the service care Taking into account economic inflation</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

HAARLEM

Designed by:

Christiana van Lammeren

Date:

05/04/2023

Version:

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>In Haarlem: citizens, entrepreneurs, initiatives, students, educational institutions.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Does not apply.</p> <p>As a municipality, we act in the interests of society and our city, even if this is not (yet) popular. We are also a launching customer to make the transition possible. We are dependent on political goodwill and political mandate. Our job is to ensure this properly.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

Designed by:

Date:

Version:

IAȘI

Bianca Ghica

15.03.2024

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>We do not have customers. we have beneficiaries and partners. All the system actors and agents are our beneficiaries and our partners.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Our clients are paying for their involvement in their development together with a healthy and resilient food system. We do not sell anything. We invest in knowledge supply chains: knowledge production, knowledge management, knowledge transfer, knowledge consolidating, strategic knowledge, circular knowledge.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

LAGOON OF VENICE

Designed by:

Marta De Marchi,
Alessandra Marcon

Date:

14/03/2024

Version:

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Our base of interlocutors is a segmented, diversified and multilateral platform. They range from entities that carry out forms of social and corporate innovation, to mainstream food networks that operate on a large scale. At the same time, associations, individual citizens, schools and other subjects outside the economic supply chain (but who constitute consumers) may be interested in the Food Atlas and the related digital platform (as well as in the public events that we will continue to organize in the lagoon).</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>For what value are our customers really willing to pay? For what do they currently pay? How are they currently paying? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues?</p> <p>TYPES: Asset sale, Usage fee, Subscription Fees, Lending/Renting/Leasing, Licensing, Brokerage fees, Advertising FIXED PRICING: List Price, Product feature dependent, Customer segment dependent, Volume dependent DYNAMIC PRICING: Negotiation (bargaining), Yield Management, Real-time-Market</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

MARSEILLE

Designed by:

Jean-Baptiste Rostaing

Date:

02/04/2024

Version:

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Inhabitants of poor neighborhoods in the city where there is a lack of access to sustainable, healthy and affordable food</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Grocery selling: dynamic pricing with different prices depending on the household income</p> <p>Subsidies from municipality, region and state Different solidarity pricing for richer consumers</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

MURSKA SOBOTA

Designed by:

Tomaz Zadavec

Date:

07/12/2023

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food producers (Farmers, cooperatives, processors, ...) - Food supply chain actors (distributors, retail, Wholesale) - Consumer (no direct generator of revenue) 				
	<p>Key Resources </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dedicated facilitators/marketing experts - Living lab demonstration environment Green Point - Posts on social media, Events and publications 			
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customization and deployment fee (one-time fee) - Subscription fee 				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

PAIDEIA CAMPUS -
POLLICA 2050

Designed by:

Virginia Cepollina, Elisa Carioli

Date:

28/02/2024

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Local community, in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food (local restaurants) - Agriculture (regenerative farmers network) - Hospitality (Albergo Diffuso) - Startup (Farzati tech) - Education (schools, teachers) 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fees for educational activities & events (customized on the target) - Sponsorship and donations - Projects funds - Castel facility rent 				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

QUART DE POBLET

Designed by:

Alberto Martínez

Date:

04/04/2024

Version:

1

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizens - Local producers - Consumers - Companies - NGO and local associations 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Consumers can access the model for free, and it does not generate any financial revenue.</p>				
<p>Key Resources </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal communications through the WhatsApp messaging service - Meetings with local associations - Official channels of the municipality - Social Media 				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

REYKJAVÍK CRFS LAB

Designed by:

René Groben

Date:

05/03/24

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Local authorities (cities, towns, communities) responsible for creating and implementing food policies within their jurisdiction but lacking the expertise and/or resources to do so.</p>				
<p>Key Resources </p> <p>Electronic communication for routine updates, in person meetings for milestones (beginning, end). Lobbying in person at relevant events to get new customers interested and using contacts of previous (happy) customers. Follow-ups (e.g., by e-mail) after longer time frames to see if new services are needed.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Consultancy service; CRFS Scan of the local system with recommendations for improvements. One-time fixed costs for service (final report and in-person presentation and discussion of results). Costs lower than hiring and training of dedicated staff by the authorities. Currently, these tasks are often not done or not done properly and efficiently by smaller authorities. Contacting customers again after a certain time (1-3 years) to see if new service is required (changed circumstances, impact assessment of implemented changes, etc.)</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

SEINÄJOKI

Designed by:

Laura Sainio, Asta Asunmaa, Terhi Väälisalo

Date:

03/04/2024

Version:

1

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Youth, parents and the suppliers of the snacks.</p> <p>Youngsters are the most important customers, but they can only be reached through the suppliers of the healthy snacks.</p> <p>The healthy snacks is a niche market at the moment and unhealthy snacks are the wide market. Our aim is to change the point of view to be the opposite.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Aim is to help the customer with the ready concept so that they don't have to create it themselves. Therefore, the costs are fairly little for the customer.</p> <p>Costs for the customer doesn't come from the concept itself, but from their own business model that they use to make the concept. Profits of the kiosk might end up being lower due to the bigger costs of making the healthier options and the food waste of the fresh products.</p> <p>It's more about the will and readiness to make the change in the public's snacking habits.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

SETESDAL.SHOP

Designed by:

Ole Goethe

Date:

07/04/2024

Version:

1

<p>Key Partners </p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Local food, service and experience producers create content and are actively participating in a more welded online community. 2) Local food, service and experience producers get to structure their services and products that are sold and can further use this for communication and marketing. 3) Local food, service and experience producers and partners can monitor and actively participate in the analysis of purchase processes and customer journeys. 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monthly subscriptions from local producers and companies 2. % of each sale 3. Consultant fees for extended services such as photographers, retail designers, etc. 				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

VEJLE P10

Designed by:

Sofie Bjerg Hougaard

Date:

22/02/2024

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>We create value for food professionals in the public kitchen and therefore for the receiver of the meals: children and elders in the municipality. We are shaping the food choices of the future generations which will create value on many levels and will strengthen the whole food sector. We also create value for food producers and policy makers that wants a stronger food sector.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Workshops to up qualifying skills on sustainable cooking for food professionals and schools do not pay as it happens inside the organization. Customers attending our events where young chefs cook and work on talent development pay a fair amount (and the money is donated). Larger food production companies that want aid on food product development or strategic mentorship pay. Smaller startups do not pay.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

VELIKA GORICA

Designed by:

V.Crnogaj; B.K.Walaitis

Date:

07/03/2024

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Act. 2.1. Policy makers; City Utility Company</p> <p>Act. 2.2. NGSs involved in the process, intermediaries in the food donation chain, Food insecure households</p> <p>Act. 2.3. Consumers</p> <p>Act 2.4. Employees in the institutions involved</p> <p>Act 2.5. Public, other interested parties</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>The model is free for consumers and does not generate financial income.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

VICENZA

Designed by:

Chiara Guglielmi - Mara Mignone

Date:

27.02.2024

Version:

v.4

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Citizens, Consumers, Students: Individuals interested in healthy eating, sustainability, and supporting local food systems.</p> <p>Local food producers and distributors: Farmers, markets, cooperatives, and other actors involved in the short supply chain.</p> <p>Restaurants and food businesses: Establishments looking to reduce waste and promote sustainable practices.</p> <p>Public institutions and NGOs: Local policy makers/administrators, organizations working on food-related initiatives, education, and social initiatives.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Public and private financing Sponsorships and collaborations Loyalty Funded projects/initiatives</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

VIDZEME

Designed by:

Aiva, Zane, Lienīte

Date:

DD/MM/YYYY

Version:

X.Y

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local municipalities - Citizens of Vidzeme region - Local producers, farmers, caterers. - Policy makers - Local Action Groups, NGOs. 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>As we are an NGO and Planning Region, we do not have any income from activities we do. The product is round table discussion and mentoring the change/process. At the moment they do not pay for anything except with their time.</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: organizing the round table discussions, materials and tutoring. DYNAMIC PRICING: extra tutoring, extra events, extra experts.</p>				

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

WINE@SICÓ

Designed by:

Pedro Caridade

Date:

03/04/2024

Version:

0.1

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Wineries (all sizes) interested in improving yield, grape quality, and resource management.</p> <p>Wine consultants and viticulturists seeking data-driven insights for their clients.</p> <p>Sustainability-focused organizations and certifications looking for data verification.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subscription fees: Tiered subscription plans based on data access, analytics tools, and vineyard size. - Data analysis services: Offer customized reports and in-depth vineyard analysis for a premium fee. - Integration with vineyard management software: Partner with existing software providers to offer data integration and seamless workflow. - Social economy in production associations. 				